

e-HIGHWAY 2050

Modular Development Plan of the Pan-European Transmission System 2050

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D2.3	System simulations analysis and overlay-grid development		

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Written by	Dries COUCKUYT, Elia Dragana ORLIC, EKC Kenneth BRUNINX, KU Leuven Alessandro ZANI, RSE Anne-Claire LEGER, Eric MOMOT, Nathalie GRISEY, RTE	16.04.2015
Checked by	Thomas ANDERSKI, AMPRION Dragana ORLIC, EKC	30.04.2015
Approved by	Gerald SANCHIS, RTE Nathalie GRISEY, RTE	30.07.2015

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Document information

General purpose

This document presents the work carried out in the task 2.3 of the e-Highway2050 project. The methodology for grid development at 2050 is detailed and the results for each of the five studied scenarios are presented.

Change status

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Executive summary

Introduction

The European target to drastically reduce the CO₂ emissions by 2050 could create new major transmission needs in Europe; their identification is one of the main objectives of the e-highway2050 project. In deliverables D1.2 and D2.1 of the project, five scenarios of generation, demand and storage were defined to encompass a wide range of possibilities to reach the CO₂ reduction target in 2050. The task 2.3 described hereafter aims at identifying the required grid architecture for each one of these five scenarios. That is to say the additional transmission corridors (including their target capacities) to be developed on top of a starting grid. These architectures are allocated a cost and a benefit following a methodology explained in depth in the document.

Main assumptions

The accuracy of the results illustrated in this report depends strongly on the used input data and the used methodology. It must be kept in mind that the system simulations and therefore the development of reinforcements follow these basics. Real future developments that deviate from the assumptions made in the scenarios, especially the generation mix, might lead to other propositions of grid reinforcements.

Given the time horizon of this study (2050) and the size of the playfield, a zonal approach (clustering) was chosen in WP2. Consequently the granularity of the results presented here is not as accurate as in a study that would tackle a closer time horizon and use a full grid model (TYNDP for instance, where detailed consistency of projects is given). The clustering approach enables focusing on transmission needs between clusters, only, thus does not reveal needs for intra-cluster reinforcements. Another consequence is that the priority has been set on the detection of major electric energy transportation issue. That is to say long distance and large capacity reinforcements (often greater than 2GW) and does not assess if smaller reinforcements would prove necessary.

The analyses in this task pursue a conservative approach to assess new transmission corridors. Only corridors that are required and beneficial even under difficult circumstances are suggested. The definition of the initial grid transmission capacities (GTC) within the cluster model has been taken from deliverable 2.2. Here an approach focusing on the thermal capacities between clusters was applied. Since this does not give credit to operational issues of the grid, defined GTCs tend to be higher than one could expect in daily grid operation. Therefore the given architectures per scenario present the minimum required grid reinforcements in each scenario – “no regret investments”. Beyond those, further reinforcements can be required and beneficial. The starting grid, assumed in the analysis, builds on a full realization of the TYNDP 2014 projects. Without their realization, the proposed reinforcements would be different.

It should be kept in mind that the generation capacities were defined following a top-down approach that ensures a European consistency; in particular there are no excessive extra generation capacities to secure independent national system adequacy. To realize such objectives, a very strong collaboration between countries is required in some scenarios. This coordinated development may differ from the combination of national development plans or from ENTSO-e’s Ten Years Network Development Plan visions. Only grid solutions have been implemented to solve the identified issues. Other solutions like more storage or more generation were not considered.

The architectures proposed hereafter can be understood as additional capacity requirements that are required beyond the grid expansion plan that has been issued in ENTSO-e’s Ten Years Network Development

Plan 2014 (TYNDP '14). Some of these projects set already a basis for a future e-Highway system as they are comparable in use, capacity and distance, e.g. the HVDC corridors in Germany and southwest France and from UK to continental Europe.

For the proposed architectures no detail is given into this work package on the timing of their implementation. This will be further analyzed in WP4.

The results provided in this document offer a cross vision of the grid development expectations in 2050 for the five scenarios. This enables the identification of shared solutions between scenarios, and thus this can put into light robust reinforcements that could be refined and derived into real projects in more detailed studies.

Methodology

For the purpose of grid development, “system” simulations are performed with Antares¹. They combine a detailed modelling of generation, demand and grid :

- The **unit commitments** and the use of storage are **optimized to minimize the overall cost** of the system. The European system is optimized in one shot and a perfect market is assumed.
- Simulations are **probabilistic** : they are carried out for 99 Monte Carlo years that present the combination of 11 different solar & wind “years” with 3 different demand “years” (temperatures) and 3 different hydrologies (e.g. dry, average, wet “years”).
- The optimization takes into account **grid characteristics**: equivalent impedances and equivalent physical capacities. As a result, both Kirchhoff’s laws are respected.
- The time step resolution is **one hour** and simulation covers a period of **one year**.

Within the study, network constraints effects are measured by the difference between two simulations:

- **“Copperplate” situation** - Case in which transmission grid is assumed to be without constraints i.e. where network capacities are set to infinite
- Simulation with grid constraints : Case in which capacities are limited to
 - o the **“starting grid”**² at first,
 - o the “starting grid” + Transmission Requirements (TR)³ in the reinforcement process.

The “copperplate” simulation gives the upper limit of what could be achieved by grid reinforcement to ensure system security and optimize operating costs. On the contrary, the “starting grid” simulation gives the lowest level of system security than can be achieved with the 2030 transmission network status after implementation of 2050 demand and generation development.

The purpose of the grid development is to minimize the effects of grid limitations at least cost. In that perspective, “transmission requirements” (TR) are defined: they represent the needed increase of capacity between two clusters. At this stage, they do not presume the technological option and detailed route.

Given the complexity of the study, the analysis is carried out in two parts :

¹ Antares is a sequential Monte-Carlo system simulator developed by RTE.

² Starting grid 2030 based on the actual grid and the TYNDP2014 enlargements (see D2.2 and annex B for more details)

³ Transmission requirement (“TR”) : needed increase of capacity between two clusters to solve SoS-issues and/or to optimize dispatch. Transmission requirements are called “reinforcements” in this report as well. They do not presume the technological option and detailed route.

- The constraints analysis
It identifies the issues: their significance, their localization and the most critical periods of the year. This enables a focus on the major issues.
- The grid development process
Transmission requirements are suggested and tested in an iterative process. Once all the reinforcements are identified, they are transposed into possible technologies to assess their cost and verify the profitability of the complete set of reinforcements (called an “architecture”).

Final architectures and common corridors

Fig. 2 provides an overview of the transmission requirements developed in each scenario. At first glance one can easily identify the predominance of “North to South” corridors. Indeed in all scenarios there are a lot of reinforcements that collect energy from the north of the system (North Sea, Scandinavia, UK, Ireland) to transport it to the continental synchronous area (northern Germany, Poland, Netherlands, Belgium and France) with opportunity for submarine routes. Major corridors also enable to collect energy from Southern countries like Spain and Italy but also to support them with the generation coming from the North. The scenarios *100%RES* and *Large Scale RES* induce much more transmission requirements (size and distance) than *Small & Local* and *Fossil Fuel & Nuclear* scenarios. *Large scale RES* and *100% RES* show important needs in major infrastructures in the middle of the continental system on top of the peripheral network required in all scenarios : the volumes of renewable in both scenarios, especially coming from North Sea, are such that full corridors from these sources to major load centers need to be reinforced. The following map (Fig. 2Fig. 183) presents the similarities between scenarios only keeping the corridors that have been reinforced in at least two scenarios. The map also displays a reminder of the range of the size of the corridors developed.

Fig. 1 : Common reinforcements (widths are according to average reinforcement capacity $[(Cap(X5) + Cap(X7) + \dots + Cap(X16)]/5$ and the color represents the number of scenarios where the reinforcement is needed)

Large scale RES

Big & market

100% RES

Fossil & nuclear

Small & local

Fig. 2 : Transmission requirements identified in each scenario (GW)

Overview of costs and benefits

The figure below gives the total investment costs for each scenario as well as their corresponding annuities. For the three less critical scenarios (*Big & market*, *Fossil & nuclear*, *Small & local*), the total cost ranges between 120 and 220b€ depending on the public acceptance of new overhead lines and therefore the available reinforcement technologies. In the scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES*, the architectures are almost twice as expensive with a total cost around 250 b€ in the case of new grid acceptance and around 390 b€ with DC cables in case of status quo.

Fig. 3 : Investment costs and annuities of the final architectures for each scenario

When analysing the impacts of the architectures in each scenario, with a focus on SoS, and optimal dispatch it can clearly be seen, that the grid reinforcements provide a large benefit. (see following figure)

Fig. 4 : Unsupplied energy, extra spillage and increase of operating costs in the different scenarios, before and after grid reinforcements

For all scenarios, almost all ENS has been solved, and generation redispatch has been drastically reduced. The total annual benefits in each scenario can be compared to the annuities of investment. Even with the strategy “status quo” (DC cables) and with an ENS cost of 1000 €/MWh, the architectures identified in each scenario are profitable. Assuming a cost of ENS of 10 000€/MWh, the archi-

tectures in the scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES* are even profitable within one year, what is explained by the tremendous amount of congestions. The reinforcements are more significant in those two scenarios - the investment cost is doubled compared to the others, but they are also much more profitable : their benefits are three to nine times higher.

These investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary for the proper functioning of the system. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

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1. Introduction

The European target to drastically reduce the CO₂ emissions by 2050 could create new major transmission needs in Europe, their identification is one of the main objectives of the e-highway2050 project. In deliverables D1.2 and D2.1 of the project, five scenarios of generation, demand and storage were defined to encompass a wide range of possibilities to reach the CO₂ reduction target in 2050. The task 2.3 described hereafter aims at identifying the required grid architecture for each one of these five scenarios. That is to say the additional transmission corridors (including their target capacities) to be developed on top of a starting grid.

These architectures are allocated a cost and a benefit following a methodology explained in depth in the document.

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Given the time horizon of this study (2050) and the size of the playfield, a zonal approach (clustering) was chosen in WP2. Consequently the granularity of the results presented here is not as accurate as in a study that would tackle a closer time horizon and use a full grid model (TYNDP for instance, where detailed consistency of projects is given). The clustering approach enables focusing on transmission needs between clusters, only, thus does not reveal needs for intra-cluster reinforcements. Another consequence is that the priority has been set on the detection of major electric energy transportation issue. That is to say long distance and large capacity reinforcements (often greater than 2GW) and does not assess if smaller reinforcements would prove necessary.

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For the proposed architectures no detail is given into this work package on the timing of their implementation. This will be further analyzed in WP4.

The results provided in this document offer a cross vision of the grid development expectations in 2050 for the five scenarios. This enables the identification of shared solutions between scenarios, and thus this can put into light robust reinforcements that could be refined and derived into real projects in more detailed studies.

The grid development study is carried out in two parts :

- A comprehensive "constraints analysis", which assesses the reduction of the security of supply (SoS) and of the non-optimal dispatch due to network limitations ;
- An iterative assessment of the grid architectures, which determines the transmission requirements⁴ in an iterative approach, transposes them into possible technologies and assesses their associated cost in order to finally verify the profitability of the architecture (simplified analysis – a more comprehensive toolbox for the cost and benefit analysis applicable to a reinforcement project is proposed in WP6).

The reinforcements are meant to minimize the effects of grid limitations. Their benefits are made of the decrease of operating costs and reduction of Energy Not Served (ENS) cost. To assess the effect of grid limitations and the benefits provided by a given set of reinforcements, simulations of the interconnected system are performed with a sequential probabilistic tool (Antares), that optimizes the generation dispatch on the whole system while respecting both network and generation constraints.

The document presents in detail the method used to assess and define the required reinforcements (or TRs).

The results for each one of the five scenarios as defined in D2.1 are then presented.

Finally a cross analysis of the final architecture for each scenario is proposed.

⁴Transmission requirement ("TR") : needed increase of capacity between two clusters to solve SoS-issues and/or to optimize dispatch. Transmission requirements are called "reinforcements" in this report as well. They do not presume the technological option and detailed route.

2. Methodology

2.1. Goals and main steps

For the purpose of grid development, “system” simulations are performed with Antares⁵. They combine a detailed modelling of generation, demand and grid :

- The **unit commitments** and the use of storage are **optimized to minimize the overall cost** of the system. The European system is optimized in one shot and a perfect market is assumed.
- Simulations are **probabilistic** : they are carried out for 99 Monte Carlo years that present the combination of 11 different solar & wind “years” with 3 different demand “years” (temperatures) and 3 different hydrologies (e.g. dry, average, wet “years”). Thus this set of 99 MC years captures the variability of the solar, wind and hydro generation, availability of power plants, as well as the level of demand.
- The optimization takes into account **grid characteristics**: equivalent impedances and equivalent physical capacities. As a result, both Kirchhoff’s laws are respected.
- The time step resolution is **one hour** and simulation covers a period of **one year**.

Within the study, network constraints effects are measured by the difference between two simulations:

- **“Copperplate” situation** - Case in which transmission grid is assumed to be without constraints i.e. where network capacities are set to infinite
- Simulation with grid constraints : Case in which capacities are limited to
 - o the **“starting grid”**⁶ at first,
 - o the “starting grid” + Transmission Requirements (TR) in the reinforcement process.

The “copperplate” simulation gives the upper limit of what could be achieved by grid reinforcement to ensure system security and optimize operating costs. On the contrary, the “starting grid” simulation gives the lowest level of system security than can be achieved with the 2030 transmission network status after implementation of 2050 demand and generation development.

The purpose of the grid development is to minimize the effects of grid limitations at least cost. In that perspective, “transmission requirements” (TR) are defined: they represent the needed increase of capacity between two clusters. At this stage, they do not presume the technological option and detailed route. TRs are also called “reinforcements” in this document.

Given the complexity of the study, the analysis is carried out in two parts :

- The constraints analysis

⁵ Antares is a sequential Monte-Carlo system simulator developed by RTE. More details can be found in : M.Doquet, C.Fourment,J.M.Roudergues “Generation&Transmission Adequacy of Large Interconnected Power Systems : A contribution to the renewal of Monte-Carlo approaches”, PowerTech2011, IEEE Trondheim

⁶ Starting grid 2030 based on the actual grid and the TYNDP2014 enlargements (see D2.2 and annex B for more details)

It identifies the issues: their significance, their localization and the most critical periods of the year. This enables a focus on the major issues.

- The grid development process

Transmission requirements are suggested and tested in an iterative process. Once all the reinforcements are identified, they are transposed into possible technologies to assess their cost and verify the profitability of the complete set of reinforcements (called an “architecture”).

2.2. Constraints analysis

The set of results at hand in such a probabilistic approach is immense (8760 hours x 99 MC years for each cluster (~100) and each link (>200)). To perform the analysis of this very large database, the process used and described in detail hereafter, relies on a progressive approach in both time and space dimensions. This approach aims at understanding **where**, **when** and **how** bottlenecks in the system occur.

2.2.1. Key indicators

The following indicators are analyzed in depth **for each scenario** at different time and geographical scales :

- **ENS** (Energy not served or unsupplied energy) represents the volumes of energy not served due to network limitations. (NB : Given the top-down approach followed to build the scenarios -see D2.1-, it is natural to encounter ENS : the scenarios were not built so that countries secure independently their load.)
- **Extra spillage or delta spillage** depicts the must run energy (e.g. Renewables) that cannot be consumed due to the congested grid.
- **Thermal redispatch** :
 - **Positive redispatch** in a given cluster means that local thermal generation is, due to grid constraints, increased to secure the load. This generation (more expensive) substitutes RES energy and competitive thermal generation available in other clusters but that cannot be relieved due to network limitations.
 - Conversely, **negative redispatch** means that thermal generation optimized in the copper plate simulation is, due to grid constraints, reduced. Negative redispatching occurs in countries/clusters with capacities in competitive technologies, e.g. nuclear and biomass and mainly countries/clusters with excess of energy.
- **Marginal Cost Variation (MCV) of the links** :

This indicator (marginal) displays the potential benefits for the system for an extra MW available on a given inter-cluster link. It points out the 1st bottlenecks in the system.

To analyze the key hourly indicators over the year, “heat maps” are used in this report. They show the hourly distribution of the values per weeks (week 1 to week 52) and hours during 7 days in each week. Midnight and noon are indicated as 0 and 12. The values displayed are averages over the 99 MC years. By this display, seasonal and daily patterns of the indicators can be detected. All indicators are presented in MW (or MWh/h) on all diagrams, but scales are different and particular attention should be paid to that.

Fig. 5 : example of « heat map »

2.2.2. Progressive identifications of the issues

The first analyses focus on the yearly indicators for the whole system to illustrate the overall effect of congestions. Then all indicators are scrutinized at smaller time and space resolution in order to locate and quantify volumes congested.

The following steps have been implemented :

Fig. 6 : Process of the constraint analysis

At the end of this process, specific weeks of interest are selected thanks to their criticality and their representativeness regarding ENS, spillage and redispatch. They are analyzed in average over the

99MC years but also for specific Monte-Carlo years to assess the synchronicity and amplitudes of the phenomenon.

For those weeks, synchronous surplus and deficit areas are identified. “Surplus areas” correspond to area in which there are unused renewable and/or cheap thermal generations that could be released by grid reinforcement. On the contrary, “deficit areas” face ENS and/or positive redispatch due to grid limitations. It is necessary to ensure the synchronicity of those phenomena as they can occur in different Monte-Carlo years or different periods of the day and thus connecting these areas cannot solve the problems.

2.3. Grid development

Once the constraints in the starting grid are identified, transmissions requirements are suggested and tested in an iterative approach:

Fig. 7: Iterative process to define the reinforcements

2.3.1. Proposal of reinforcements

Based on the constraints analysis of the characteristic weeks, reinforcements are suggested to connect areas in surplus to areas in deficit. Their sizes are set based on the identification of synchronous volumes at stake. The possibility to stop in the different clusters to collect or distribute energy along the path is considered.

Fig. 8 : Example of map with average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in a characteristic week and reinforcements

The reinforcements are not tested one by one or all at once : at each iteration of the process, a set of reinforcements (called a “step”) is studied. The interest of this approach is to fasten the process but the risk is to over-invest. The “steps” aim at solving only one issue or several **independent** issues, in order to avoid adding, in a same step, redundant reinforcements; especially, the more the issues are in the center of the continental Europe, the more the reinforcements may have interactions between each other.

During the first steps, the focus is mainly on solving ENS for the most critical weeks. Indeed, ENS has a very high cost and thus reinforcements are likely to be very profitable. Due to this fact, a sensitivity analyses on the profitability of the proposed grid architecture has been executed for two different levels of ENS costs (10 000 €/MWh and 1 000 €/MWh). Moreover, areas with ENS in the most critical weeks usually face high positive redispatch in other weeks and are thus very good candidates for profitable reinforcements over the whole year.

2.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

Grid reinforcements are modelled in the simulations as DC links. Once a set of reinforcements have been tested (and potentially refined) in the characteristic weeks, an annual simulation is performed on the 99 Monte-Carlo years to assess the global impact.

Annual gains on ENS, spillage and redispatch are calculated. The annual benefit of the “step” is calculated as the sum of generation costs savings and ENS costs reduction. Within the project, ENS costs are estimated on the level of 10 000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe but a cost of 1000 Euro/MWh is also considered in a sensitivity analysis. The generation costs include fuel costs (scenario dependant) and CO₂ cost (270€/t in all the scenarios), they are recalled in the table below (see D2.1 for more details).

€/MWh	Large Scale RES	100% RES	Big & market	Fossil & nuclear	Small & local	CO ₂ cost included
OCGT	189	203	172	172	203	132
CCGT without CCS	131	NA	118	118	141	88
CCGT with CCS	NA	NA	46	46	NA	5
Coal without CCS	180	NA	NA	NA	196	167
Coal with CCS	NA	NA	47	47	NA	23
Lignite without CCS	180	NA	NA	NA	200	172
Lignite with CCS	NA	NA	29	29	NA	12
Nuclear	14	NA	14	14	14	0
Biomass1	20	10	20	20	10	0
Biomass2	135	20	135	135	20	0

Fig. 9 : Marginal costs for thermal plants (€/MWh)

The cost of the tested set of reinforcements is then roughly assessed considering only DC cables, as the most expensive case. It is compared with the benefits, to verify that the investments are profitable whatever technology is used – “no regret investments”. Some reinforcements may be modified if

they are inefficient or over-sized (over-sizing characterized by very small remaining MCV or flows well below capacity).

Based on the remaining constraints in the characteristic weeks, a new iteration of reinforcement is then defined. If there are no more significant issues (which means only small and spread volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatch remain), the iterative process stops.

The final grid proposal is made of all the transmission requirements (reinforcements) defined in the different steps and defines the **final architecture**.

2.4. Technological and cost assessment

As explained previously, Transmission Requirements (TR) are not related to any specific technology as they represent the major grid reinforcement needs. However, they are transposed into possible technologies in order :

- to ensure that there are technical solutions available,
- to better assess the cost of the final architecture.

The selection of technologies in 2050 will be highly impacted by the level of public acceptance towards new lines, this will impact the costs of the architectures. Thus, three strategies are considered to encompass a large range of possible costs :

- **Status Quo** : the public opposition against new infrastructure prevents any new OHLs. Only refurbishment of existing lines or new DC cables can be implemented.
- **Re-Use of Corridors** : the public accepts new OHL as long as they are close to existing lines. Therefore new AC or DC Overhead-lines can be implemented when they are in the existing corridors.
- **New Grid Acceptance** : the public accepts new OHL and also the development of new corridors. DC cables are also possible but OHL are preferred when possible due to their lower costs.

The levels of acceptability for the three strategies considered are summarized in the following table:

Strategy	Social assumption	Technical description	Cables	Up-grade of OHL's	New OHL	New OHL on <u>non</u> existing corridors
New grid acceptance	Public acceptance for new OH Lines.	The most efficient (cost & technical) solution is selected.	X	(X)	X	X
Re-use of corridors	Public acceptance for new lines in existing infrastructure corridors.	Re-use of existing infrastructure corridors or construction of underground cable otherwise	X	(X)	X	
Status Quo	No public acceptance for new OH Lines.	Only up-grade of existing lines with same visual impact, or construction of underground cables otherwise	X	X		

Table 1 : Levels of acceptability for the 3 strategies

The strategies and selected technologies do not change the structure of the grid architecture, but only its cost. It is assumed that technology choice does not impact the benefit of the reinforcements⁷.

The cost of the final architecture, or total investment cost is assessed for the three strategies, based on the available technologies and their costs, and on the following assumptions :

- Use of the database developed by WP3 (ref : D3.1), which gives available technologies, capacities and costs,
- A 5% discount rate is assumed to calculate the annuities of investment
- As the substations and the detailed routes are unknown, the distances are calculated between the clusters centroids,
- Within T2.3, the operability of the grid is not tested but :
 1. A criteria is used to ensure a minimum robustness to N-1,
 2. Limitations of distances for AC connections are considered.
 3. A shift to higher DC voltage levels on longer distances can be decided to reduce transmission-losses

The data of the technology database from WP3 have been processed to derive investment costs for Overhead lines (OHL), underground cables, converter stations and transformers. The information about investment costs, thermal capacities and lifespan has been used to define proper technical solutions per transmission requirement and calculate their annual investment costs. The following figures show the investment costs per technology given by length and capacity:

Fig. 10 : investment costs per technology – OHL and cable

⁷ In the simulations, the benefits were assessed for DC connections. AC lines could result in different benefits. However, to make sure these reinforcements are at least as profitable, the cost of AC was penalized by 20% to take into account either load-flow control devices or parallel additional reinforcements.

Fig. 11 : investment costs per technology – transformer and converter

For OHLs a lifespan of 100 years has been assumed. The lifespan for cable-solutions (AC and DC), AC-transformers and DC-converters is given with 40 years.

It should be noted that a given transmission requirement can of course be realized through many parallel lines, especially due to the capacity limit of a single line and the N-1 robustness. These different lines could follow different routes between the clusters and be connected to different substations, but this is out of the scope of this report.

Strategies “Status Quo” and “New Grid acceptance” provide the upper and lower limits of the possible costs. The three strategies are only used to have a rough assessment of costs, they do not represent necessarily the best technological solution. Especially, innovative solutions like superconductors, partial undergrounding or higher voltages were not assessed even though they are very promising. Indeed the precision of the study does not allow a complete comparison of the different technological solutions. For example, a definitive choice of the most suitable technology for a refurbishment requires very detailed information about the existing line. Therefore only a short view of this issue is given in the annex E, and an exhaustive discussion of available options and their advantages is made in D 3.2.

2.5. Cost/benefit analysis

A simplified analysis is carried out here, while a more comprehensive toolbox for the cost and benefit analysis applicable to a reinforcement project is proposed in the dedicated WP6.

For the three strategies, the investment annuity⁸ of the final architecture is compared to the annual benefit of it, to measure the level of profitability (example in Fig. below).

⁸ Investment annuity is calculated as discounted annual costs respecting economic lifetime of the equipment defined in WP3 and discount rate of 5%.

Fig. 12 : Comparison of investment annuities and annual benefits for final architecture and the 3 strategies

This assessment of the profitability encompasses the whole architecture and does not evaluate profitability of partial packages of reinforcements (the profitability of each reinforcement depends strongly on the other reinforcements thus it is difficult to assess the profitability of a single project).

3. Grid model

3.1.1. European grid

For the system simulations, the European power system is modelled through a hundred clusters as shown in Figure 7. Demand and installed capacities for each technology per clusters within each country has been defined within Scenario Quantification process and presented in Deliverable D2.1.

Fig. 13: Countries and clusters + North Sea and North Africa

Fig. 14: Equivalent transmission network

As a result of this clustering, the transmission network is also simplified (see Fig. 14). Details can be found in Deliverable D2.2⁹. The starting grid has been derived from ENTSOE-e CIM dataset. In it, in addition to today situation (2015), already significant investments that will be included up to the year 2030 are considered, for example:

- HVDC corridors in Germany and southwest France, from UK to continental Europe and UK to France,
- AC reinforcements in central Europe and Baltic states.

More details on the projects included are given in Annex B. These reinforcements are not re-evaluated.

3.1.2. Connections with North Africa

Connections from North Africa to Europe are considered as already in service, their development is out of the scope of the e-Highway2050 project. Other studies have been launched to perform an assessment of their interest : Desertec initiative, Medgrid, MedTSO.

PV and CSP generation from North Africa is presented as the sum of the PV and CSP generation from:

- Morocco (MA, 102MA)
- Algeria (DZ, 103DZ)
- Tunisia (TN, 104TN)
- Libya (LY, 105LY)
- Middle East (MI, 101MI)

Considered interconnections graph is presented in Fig. 15:

Fig. 15: Connections with North Africa

⁹ The method for deriving the capacities between the clusters (GTC Method) in the starting grid (TYNDP 2014 – horizon: 2030), focuses on the installed capacity of cross-border lines and not on for the available market capacity (NTC). Some countries can't fully use their installed cross border capacity, because of smaller transport capacity inside their countries. E.g. for Switzerland the method yields approximately 15 GW GTC at its northern borders (to Germany, France and Austria), although the Swiss import capacity in the TYNDP 2014 grid from Germany, France and Austria is significantly lower (about 10 GW). In these cases where the GTC values are overestimated, the need for reinforcements between 2030 and 2050 will tend to be underestimated - consequently some needed reinforcements might not be identified.

Connections with North Africa have capacities that depend on the scenario (according to the assumption of solar power development in North Africa, see D2.1) and are fixed to the following values:

Links - countries	Links-cluster names	Large Scale RES Capacity (MW)	100% RES Capacity (MW)	Big& market Capacity (MW)	Fossil& nuclear Capacity (MW)	Small& local Capacity (MW)
Middle East - Bulgaria	101_mi - 66_bg	1 500	1 500	1 500	1 500	1 500
Middle East - Greece	101_mi - 68_gr	2 000	2 000	2 000	2 000	2 000
Middle East - Greece	101_mi - 69_gr	2 000	2 000	2 000	2 000	2 000
Morocco-Portugal	102_ma - 13_pt	5 000	1 500			
Algeria- Spain	103_dz - 10_es	6 000	2 000			
Algeria- France	103_dz - 16_fr	12 000	4 000	2 000		1 500
Algeria – Italy	103_dz - 98_it	11 000	4 000	1 500		1 000
Tunisia - Italy	104_tn - 56_it	8 500	3 000	1 000		1 000
Libya – Italy	105_ly - 56_it	8 500	3 000	2 000		1 000
Libya - Greece	105_ly - 69_gr	6 000	2 000			
Morocco - Spain	102_ma - 09_es	12 000	4 000	2 000		1 500

Table 2 : Initial transmission capacities of the connections to North Africa

3.1.3. Connections with clusters of wind farms in North Sea

The map with localization of the clusters in North Sea and initial status of the connections between these cluster and UK and continental Europe are given in Fig. 16 and in Table 3 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**(see D2.2 for details on the North Sea modelling and sources used). These capacities are applied in starting grid situation assuming that these connections are in operation in 2030. These capacities of the links are only around half of the installed off-shore wind capacities since further development of North Sea connections with UK, continental Europe and Nordic countries (in the form of meshed grid connections or not), is analyzed in the project.

Fig. 16: Map with clusters in North Sea

Link	Large Scale RES Capacity (MW)	100% RES Capacity (MW)	Big& market Capacity (MW)	Fossil& nuclear Capacity (MW)	Small& local Capacity (MW)
106_ns - 90_uk	8 000	8 000	5 000	5 000	885
107_ns - 92_uk	6 000	5 580	4 350	2 550	442
108_ns - 93_uk	1 000	930	725	425	74
109_ns - 94_uk	1 000	930	725	425	74
110_ns - 28_be	1 000	1 500	1 000	1 000	1 095
111_ns - 30_nl	4 500	7 950	3 500	2 600	100
112_ns - 31_de	8 000	8 000	5 000	5 000	3 800
113_ns - 38_dk	8 000	8 000	5 000	1 500	652
114_ns - 72_dk	3 900	3 200	2 375	500	218
115_ns - 79_no	300	1 500	247	1	1
116_ns - 88_se	300	1 500	247	150	100
Wind off-shore NS installed capacities (MW)	99600	114800	74100	41200	10200

Table 3 : Initial transmission capacities of the North Sea connections

4. Scenario Large scale RES (“X-5”)

4.1. Presentation of the scenario

In this scenario, a European agreement for climate mitigation is achieved and fossil fuel consumption is generally low worldwide. Therefore, fuel costs are relatively low. On the other hand, the CO₂ costs are high due to the existence of a global carbon market. The EU's ambition for GHG emission reductions is achieved: 80-95% GHG reduction.

The strategy focuses on the deployment of large-scale RES technologies, e.g. large scale offshore wind parks in the North Sea and Baltic Sea as well as solar power in North Africa. A lower priority is given to the deployment of decentralized RES (including biomass) solutions.

The scenario Large Scale RES is characterized with high demand that reaches 5200 TWh, the highest demand among analyzed scenarios. The European energy mix (without grid constraints) is presented in Fig. 17.

The most significant RES technology is wind with 20% coming from just one area: North Sea. Similar is with hydro for which 35% comes from Nordic countries and PV for which 50% comes from North Africa. Connections of these three areas with continental Europe are certainly very important.

Installed capacities, demand and imbalances per country are presented in Fig. 17.

Fig. 17 : European energy mix, installed capacities and imbalances per country – Large scale RES

4.2. Constraints analysis

4.2.1. Annual results for the whole system

Overview of results

The comparison of the two situations (“copperplate” and “starting grid”), presented in the table below allows overview of how far the network without reinforcement is from copperplate situation in terms of unsupplied energy, non-optimal dispatch, spilled energy, CO₂ emissions.

Annual data, expected	Units	„copper plate“	„starting grid“	Difference
Total generation	TWh	5 237	5 783	545
<i>Demand</i>	<i>TWh</i>	<i>5 194</i>	<i>5 194</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Run-of-river generation</i>	<i>TWh</i>	<i>430</i>	<i>430</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>WIND generation</i>	<i>TWh</i>	<i>2 084</i>	<i>2 084</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>SOLAR generation</i>	<i>TWh</i>	<i>717</i>	<i>717</i>	<i>0</i>
BIOMASS generation	TWh	288	333	45
NUCLEAR generation	TWh	1 048	957	-91
GAS generation	TWh	248	812	564
Coal generation	TWh	0	22	22
Lignite generation	TWh	0	5	5
<i>Hydro reservoir generation</i>	<i>TWh</i>	<i>423</i>	<i>423</i>	<i>0</i>
Unsupplied energy	TWh	0	23	23
Spilled energy	TWh	38	609	571
Loss of Load Duration	H	0	3 200	3 200
Overall costs of system operation	mil. Euro	62 288	383 066	320 778
CO ₂ emission	Mt	81	292	211

Table 4 : Annual results for the whole system – X-5

Level of security and spillage

In the “starting grid” situation and compared to the copper plate situation:

- Non supplied demand reaches 23 TWh,
- Loss of Load duration is 3200 hours, more than 35% of the year
- Spillage of RES generation is also high: 12% of total demand and 17% of available RES generation: there is 571 TWh of spilled energy more than in “copperplate” situation.

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

Looking at dispatch able generation, as it can be seen from the graph below (Fig. 18), gas generation is comparable to spilled RES generation while variations of other technologies generation are not significant.

Fig. 18: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation for the whole system – X-5

There is 545TWh of thermal redispatching due to congestions: expensive generation is generating instead of cheap or must run sources, as it can be seen from Fig. 18.

Costs of the system operation

Higher level of thermal generation as well as costs for unsupplied demand increase total costs of the system operation in starting grid situation. Difference in total costs is on the level of 321 billion Euro, where 87 billion is due to thermal redispatching while 234 billion is due to unsupplied demand¹⁰. This difference in costs means that there is room for reinforcements.

4.2.2. Annual results for the main countries at stake

Level of security and spillage

Particular attention is paid to the countries with high unsupplied demand (ENS) and high spillage variations (difference between spillages in starting grid and copper plate situations). With respect to this, countries with high ENS (>1 TWh, Table 5 : Countries with annual ENS > 1 TWh – X-5

) and high spillages variation (>10TWh, Table 7), as well as spillage variation in North Sea and North Africa (Table 6) are particularly analyzed :

Areas	ENS (TWh)	LOLD (h)
DE	10.3	1,134
PL	4.5	1,211
ES	4.0	1,186
FR	2.4	1,482
IT	1.2	1,383

¹⁰ Within EH2050, ENS costs (costs for unsupplied demand) are estimated on the level of 10,000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe.

SUM	22.4	
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Table 5 : Countries with annual ENS > 1 TWh – X-5

Areas in North Africa and North Sea	SPILLAGE VARIATION (TWh)	ANNUAL AVAILABLE GENERATION (TWh)
North Sea	202.9	424.1
Algeria (103DZ)	55.8	165.1
Libya (105LY)	44.5	79.3
Morocco (102MA)	10.0	85.4
Middle East (101MI)	0.8	8.8
Tunisia (104TN)	20.0	28.2
SUM	334.1	790.9

Table 6: Spillage variation in areas outside Europe – X-5

Areas	SPILLAGE VARIATION (TWh)	AVAILABLE RES GENERATION (TWh)
NO	75.5	245.0
SE	27.9	158.7
FI	20.2	107.5
GR	22.2	96.8
FR	13.3	315.4
LV	12.6	33.6
IE	12.2	48.0
LT	11.0	36.3
UK	10.4	322.2
SUM	205.3	1363.5

Table 7: Countries with annual spillage variation > 10 TWh – X-5

The results point to the following:

- ➔ Countries with **high ENS**: DE, PL, ES, FR and IT. Sum of ENS in these 5 countries is 22 TWh, of total 23 TWh (94%). Germany accounts for almost 50% of total unsupplied demand.
- ➔ Countries with **high spillage variation**: Nordic Countries, GR, FR, LV, IE, LT, UK, with sum of 205 TWh of total 571 TWh (36%).
- ➔ Areas with **high spillage variation**: North Africa with 130TWh (23%) and North Sea with 200TWh (35%).

High spillage variation especially in North Sea is provoked by very constrained connections with UK and continental Europe. Further reinforcement will release this excess of generation. In case of exchange with North Africa, connections with continental Europe are not the bottlenecks, but links inside Europe.

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

There is high **positive thermal redispatching** in Germany, Spain, Italy and Poland but also in Belgium and Netherland. The sum in these 6 countries is 500 TWh of total 648 TWh (77%).

Fig. 19: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation in countries with high positive thermal redispatching – X-5

High **negative thermal redispatching** happens in Sweden, Finland, UK, Denmark, Greece and Baltic countries with total of 100 TWh. In these countries, there are cheap units, mainly biomass and nuclear plants that are not used to their potential, due to the inability of the transmission grid to bring this power down to West and South Europe. It should be pointed out that potential thermal generation exist in (almost) same countries as spillages, which points to these countries/areas as important “sources” of energy.

Fig. 20: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation in countries with high negative thermal redispatching – X-5

Conclusion :

Deficit areas	Surplus areas
Germany	North Sea
Poland	North Africa
Spain	Norway
France	Sweden

Italy	Finland
	United Kingdom
	Greece
	France
	Denmark

Table 8: Surplus and Deficit Areas – X5

4.2.3. Hourly results for the whole system

ENS and spillage issues are not only geographically concentrated, but they are also confined to specific periods of the year. Therefore, time distribution of hourly ENS and spillage volumes in the whole European power system (expected values over the 99 Monte Carlo years) are presented in this section. This allows us to limit the scope of the study later in this analysis to specific, critical period of the year.

Level of Security

Hourly distribution of the system’s unsupplied demand (ENS) shows that there is high ENS in winter, in weeks 46-13. (Fig. 21).

Fig. 21: ENS hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

During critical period, ENS is distributed during whole day with higher concentration in evening hours, during peak load periods. Maximum hourly value of ENS (calculated as the maximum of average hourly values) is 33 GW and it is noted in week 48 (Thursday, 19h). Outside of the period with highest ENS (outside winter season), hourly ENS is below 5GW with highest values during night and morning hours.

The sum of the ENS in 10 most critical weeks is 15TWh (64% of total 23 TWh) as presented in Table 9: . The most critical week with respect to ENS is week 48.

Weeks	ENS (GWh)
Sum of these 10 weeks	15 226
48	2 979
47	1 709
2	1 585
6	1 572
4	1 514
46	1 358
5	1 269
3	1 090
7	1 084
50	1 066

Table 9: Weeks with the highest ENS – X-5

Level of Spillage

The hourly distribution of the spillage variation (Fig. 22) shows daily characteristic with the highest spillages during day-light period. Maximum spillage variation happens in weeks 20-26, with maximum in week 25. Maximum “expected” hourly spillage variation (calculated as maximum of average values) is higher than 100 GW.

Fig. 22: Spillage variation, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

Thermal redispatching is in all hours higher than 0 and on the level of the whole system only positive thermal redispatching is noted (Fig. 23). Thermal redispatching shows seasonal characteristics with highest difference during summer when there is also maximum spillage variation, although not in the same periods of the day.

Fig. 23: Thermal redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

Hourly distribution of gas redispatching resembles to hourly distribution of ENS (Fig. 21), with maximum during winter and minimum in summer, especially during weekends, as presented in Fig. 24.

Fig. 24: Gas redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

There is also hydro redispatching that shows similar shape to spilled energy and shows that grid constraints provokes high hydro generation during daylight .

Fig. 25: Hydro redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

Fig. 30: ENS in Italy (5% of total ENS), hourly values (MW)

- **Germany:** There is a maximum ENS in week 48 with 1.4 TWh which represents 14% of whole year (total annual ENS for DE is 10.3 TWh) . Weeks 2 to 6 also see huge volume of ENS.
- **Poland:** Second highest annual ENS happens in Poland, with weekly maximum in week 4: 0.5TWh (annual ENS is 4.5TWh). There is ENS during whole day with maximum during evening hours and similar to Germany. Weeks 2 to 6 also see huge volume of ENS.
- **Spain:** ENS in Spain on the annual level is 4 TWh, maximum week is week 2 with 0.6 TWh. Weeks 2 to 6 also see huge volume of ENS.
- **France:** ENS in France on the annual level is 2.4 TWh, maximum week is week 48 with 0.5 TWh. During winter ENS happens in the evening hours (due to high load) while during summer, there is a low level of ENS but mostly around midnight.
- **Italy:** ENS in Italy is almost constantly distributed along the year with maximum in week 10 and hourly maximum of 3GW. ENS is happening during the whole day except around noon in all seasons.

Level of Spillage and thermal redispatching

Fig. 31: Spillage variation in Norway (13% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

Fig. 32: Spillage variation in Sweden (5% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

Fig. 33: Thermal redispatching in Sweden, hourly values (MW)

Fig. 34: Spillage variation in Finland (3.5% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

- **Norway:** Spillage variation at the end of spring/ beginning of summer (May-June, weeks 21-28) is the highest due to high RoR generation in that period as the consequence of snow melting.
- **Sweden:** Like in the case of Norway, spillage variation at the end of spring (May-June, weeks 22-28) is the highest due to high RoR generation in that period. In terms of thermal redispatching, almost constant potential of additional 6GW of thermal generation in Sweden during winter season (week 1-5 and 47-52) which can be released by grid reinforcement. Minimal values are expected in spring (April-May, weeks 17-22) when there is an increase in demand and still low RoR generation, and thermal units are needed to supply the load.
- **Finland:** Spillage variation at the end of summer (late September, weeks 38-44) is the highest with also high values reached in week 21-28, but especially low during first 3 months. Beginning of the year in Finland is characterized by low RoR generation and low spillages. Thermal redispatching in Finland is not as high as in Sweden and also not so constant during winter

season although the maximum values are again reached in that season (weeks 1-5 and 47-52). Minimal values are expected in spring-(April-May, week 17-22) .

- **Greece:** Spillage variation in Greece shows daily profile (maximum during daylight and minimum around midnight) since it is provoked by excess of PV generation.
- Analyzing the surplus of energy, particularly interesting are areas of North Sea and North Africa. Spillage variation in North Sea is particularly high during winter season: weeks 1-6 and 40-52.
- Spillage variation in **North Sea** is very high, in both aspects: total energy and maximum hourly values:
 - Annual spillage variation is 203 TWh (47% of total available generation)
 - Maximum hourly value is 47 GW
 - Spillage variation doesn't have daily profile, just seasonal, with higher values during winter season when higher wind generation is available.
- Spillage variation in **North Africa** is also high:
 - Annual spillage variation is 131 TWh (36% of total available generation)
 - Maximum hourly value is 39 GW
 - Spillage variation has obvious daily profile but also seasonal characteristic. Maximum is reached during spring/summer and around noon.

4.2.5. Conclusion

The reduction of efficiency in operation due to grid constraints in the starting grid is summarized in Fig. 39 below.

Fig. 39 : Operation efficiency reduction in starting grid – X5

The analyses of the transmission requirements are further focused on characteristic weeks that are recognized on the basis of the above analyses:

Week	ENS	Spillage variation or redispatching
2	High ENS (6.8% of total), particularly high in Spain, similar to week 47	
5	High ENS (5.4% of total), particularly high in Central & East Europe (FR,DE,PL), similar to week 48	
10	High ENS (4.1% of total), particularly high in Italy	
25		High spillage variation
40	Some ENS in central Europe	High spillage variation
47	High ENS (7.3% of total), particularly high in Spain	
48	High ENS (12.7% of total), particularly high in Central & East Europe (FR,DE,PL)	

Detailed analyses of the constraints in the starting grid for those weeks are presented in Annex of this report.

4.3. Grid development

4.3.1. Introduction

The reinforcement process is based on the results of the constraint analysis. The final architecture is determined through an iterative process and evaluation of the annual benefits of the proposed reinforcements in each step. Process is stopped when remaining issues (ENS, spillage, redispatching) are sufficiently small and distributed.

4.3.2. Step 1

4.3.2.1. Constraints in starting grid and reinforcements in step1

At the end of the constraint analysis, a first set of transmission requirements was defined which is implemented as grid reinforcement in this step1.

The map below presents:

- the main indicators for the starting grid in winter week (week 48, on which the first set of transmission requirements was mainly defined),
- the first set of reinforcements

Fig. 40 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 in the starting grid, and reinforcements in step 1 – X5

The target of these first reinforcements is to:

- solve ENS in Germany from Norway and Sweden (where high spillage and cheap thermal generation exist)
- solve ENS in Poland from Finland and Baltic states (where high spillage and cheap thermal generation exist)
- solve ENS in France from UK & IE
- solve ENS in Spain from Portugal and France, but also transporting solar energy from North Africa
- solve ENS and enable more economic dispatch in Italy from Greece (where high spillage and cheap thermal generation exist), but also transporting solar energy from North Africa

4.3.2.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 41 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS by 23TWh (or 97% of total ENS)**, the main reduction being in Germany (10TWh decrease), Poland (4,5TWh) and in Spain (3,5TWh decrease),
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 300TWh (or 50% of total spillage)**, the main parts being a reduction of 83TWh in NS, 75TWh in Norway and 50TWh in North Africa,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 300TWh**, the main reduction being in Germany (88TWh gas decrease), Spain and in Italy (per 45 TWh each),
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 50TWh**, the main increase being in UK (23TWh).

NB : At each step, and before moving to the next one, the cost of the tested set of reinforcements is roughly assessed and compared with the benefits to verify that the investments are profitable.

4.3.3. Step 2

4.3.3.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 1 and definition of reinforcements in step 2

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying reinforcements proposed in step 1 (like in step 1, winter week 48 is the most characteristic week among the ones selected in the constraint analysis for assessing ENS remaining problems, although other 3 weeks were also studied in each step).

Fig. 42 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 after step 1, and reinforcements in step 2 – X5

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step2 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map above) :

- reinforcements at NS-UK, north UK– Ireland and UK –Belgium and Netherlands, to optimize thermal redispatching
- reinforcement of the UK-France-Spain corridor, to transport spillage from NS and cheap thermal from UK toward Spain
- reinforcements at south of France and France - Spain are added to allow transport of energy from North Africa towards Spain (to solve ENS in Barcelona area),
- reinforcement NS-DE is added to use wind from NS to reduce gas generation in Germany
- reinforcement of the links towards Italy (from Greece, Sicilia, Sardinia), further implemented to transport still existing excess of generation from North Africa to north Italy.

4.3.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step2 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

The main goal of step 1 was to connect distant areas with energy in excess to continental Europe, while the main goal of step 2 is :

- to refine step 1 where it was not sufficient,
- to consider further reinforcements on the periphery and **inside** continental Europe to solve problems of ENS (Spain) but also to utilize spillages (Scandinavia and Baltic countries, North Africa and North Sea) and to reduce expensive gas generation (central continental Europe and Italy). There is positive thermal redispatching in central continental Europe (North and North East of France, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Italy).

There is still reservoir of spillage in NS clusters close to UK, Denmark and north west Germany as well as spillage in North Africa.

Fig. 43 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS (from 0,7TWh to 0,04TWh)**, the reduction being almost completely in Spain (from 0,53TWh to 0,02TWh),
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 110TWh**, the main parts being a reduction of 50TWh in NS and 30TWh in North Africa,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 110TWh**, the main reduction being in Italy (40TWh decrease) and Spain (20TWh decrease).
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 17TWh**, the main increase being in France (9TWh).

4.3.4. Step 3

4.3.4.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 2 and definition of reinforcements in step 3

The map below shows average values for winter week after applying reinforcement implemented in step1 and step 2. This time it is week 2, since the focus is on reduction of spillage and expensive gas generation that are more indicative in week 2.

The main goal of step 3 is :

- to reduce spillage and expensive gas generation
- to refine step 1+2 where it was not sufficient,
- to deal with remaining problems inside continental Europe.

In winter week 2, there is almost no ENS remaining in any cluster.

There is still a reservoir of spillage and of cheap thermal generation in Ireland, Scandinavia and Baltic states and a reservoir of cheap thermal generation in UK and Central East Europe.

There is positive thermal redispatching remaining in Spain and Central South Europe (Germany, Switzerland, Hungary, and Italy).

In the characteristic winter week 2, there is still spillage in NS clusters close to Denmark and UK, as well as in North Africa.

Fig. 44 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 after step 2, and reinforcements in step 3 – X5

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 3 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map above):

- reinforcements NS cluster to Denmark and Germany, as well as reinforcement inside Germany to transport spillage to south Germany to reduce gas generation
- reinforcement of the corridor Poland to North Italy to replace gas generation by cheap thermal generation
- refinement of the already made reinforcement between NS clusters and UK

4.3.4.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step3 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 45 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- pursued the steady reduction of spillage (reduction by 62TWh), the main part being a reduction of 46TWh in NS,
- reduced the amount of gas generation by 61TWh, the main part being a reduction of 22TWh in Germany,
- allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 10TWh, with main increase in Sweden (4TWh),
- almost finished the solving of ENS problems : ENS in Spain has been reduced from 0,02TWh to 0,01TWh, the total remaining European ENS is 0,02TWh

4.3.5. Step 4

4.3.5.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 3 and definition of reinforcements in step 4

At this stage the ENS has been almost solved, and the further reinforcements are aimed at reducing the cost of generation by replacing expensive thermal generation by RES or cheaper thermal generation that is close enough to remain profitable.

The map below shows average values for winter week 2 after applying steps 1, 2 and 3 reinforcements (this week is again the most characteristic week to illustrate the reasons for reinforcements of step 4, but determination of these reinforcements was based on all the characteristic weeks).

Fig. 46 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 after step 3, and reinforcements in step 4 – X5

There is still positive thermal redispatching in Spain, Portugal, Italy, Germany, while there remains cheap generation in UK and Sweden and spillage in Finland and Baltic countries. There is still a reservoir of spillage in NS and North Africa.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 4 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below):

- further refinement of the reinforcements from Denmark to Germany
- reinforcement UK-France-Spain has been increased,
- reinforcement from south Finland to Sweden, then to Poland , to transport spilled RES and cheap thermal to southern Europe(at the right moment)
- reinforcement from Sardinia and Sicilia to Italy has been added to transport cheap energy (solar) from North Africa to reduce positive thermal redispatching in Italy

4.3.5.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step 4 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 47: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the spillage from 101TWh to 50TWh**, the main part being a reduction of 24TWh in North Africa,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation from 95TWh to 59TWh**, with main decreases in Italy (14TWh), Netherlands (6TWh),
- **allowed an small increase of nuclear generation by 2TWh**

After all 4 steps, significant issues have been solved with almost all ENS suppressed (only 0,006TWh remains), and a level of spillage drastically reduced from 609TWh to 88TWh (38TWh in copperplate situation). Remaining volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatching are small and spread, which left no room for easily detection of profitable new reinforcements.

4.3.6. Final grid proposal for the scenario – final architecture

4.3.6.1. Map with final architecture

The final grid proposal for the scenario is shown on the map below, where reinforcements higher than 1 GW are presented :

Fig. 48: Map of the final grid proposal for the scenario X5

Final grid proposal encompasses 452 GW of reinforcements that are in total more than 31000 km long.

4.3.6.2. Annual benefit assessment

The table below summarizes the evolution of annual ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO₂ emissions and benefit of the reinforcements on these values :

	Copper plate	Starting grid	Final grid	Benefit (final – starting)
ENS (TWh)	0	23	0	-23
Spillage (TWh)	38	609	88	-521

Operating cost	62	149	70	-79
CO ₂ (Mt)	81	292	100	-192

Table 10: Annual values of ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO₂ emissions – X5

The annual reduction of total costs is made of :

- 79b€ reduction of operating costs,
- 230b€ reduction due to avoided ENS if the assumed cost of cost of ENS equals 10k€/MWh, or 23b€ if it equals 1k€/MWh.

So annual benefit is equal to 309b€ or 102b€, depending on the assumption for ENS cost.

4.3.6.3. Technology selection and cost/benefit analysis

The cost of the full architecture is calculated for 3 strategies (see details in chapter 2) : “new grid acceptance,” “re-use of corridors”, “status quo”. Then, the annuity of each strategy is compared to the annual benefits (see graphs below).

Fig. 49: Total investment cost and cost/benefit comparison – X5

Investment costs in strategy 3 are the highest since this strategy considers only DC cables and refurbishment of the existing OHLs, where possible. Investment costs in strategy 3(384b€) is around 50% more expensive than the strategy 1 (255b€).

Significant share in investment costs refer to subsea cables that is the same in all three strategies. In this scenario, investment costs of subsea cables are 202b€ (same in all three strategies) and investment costs for onshore reinforcements are between 52b€ and 182b€, depending on applied technologies and public acceptance of new lines.

Whatever the strategy and the cost of ENS (10k€/MWh or 1k€/MWh), the annual benefits (102b€ to 309b€) exceed easily the total investment annuities (14 to 22b€).

However, these investments don’t take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

5. Scenario 100% RES (“X-7”)

5.1. Presentation of the scenario

In this scenario, the strategy to achieve the 80-95% GHG reduction target is based on the use of only renewable energy. To reach this target, both large scale and small-scale options are used: offshore wind parks in the North Sea and Baltic Sea and solar projects in North Africa, combined with EU-wide deployment of de-centralized RES (including Biomass) solutions.

A European energy system based entirely on renewable energy means that the units that can support the variability of the system are biomass power plants, hydro plants and “peaking units” that represent additional biomass units, storage solutions or demand side management. This scenario is characterized with a demand that reaches 4300 TWh. The European energy mix (without grid constraints) is presented in Fig. 50.

The most significant RES source is wind and 50% of total load is supplied from wind farms—with 21% of total wind generation coming from North Sea. 50 % of hydro comes from Nordic countries and 12% of PV comes from North Africa. Connections of these three areas with continental Europe are certainly very important.

Installed capacities, demand and imbalances per country are presented in figure below.

Fig. 50: European energy mix, installed capacities and imbalances per country – 100% RES

5.2. Constraints analysis

5.2.1. Annual results for the whole system

Overview of results

The comparison of the two situations (“copperplate” and “starting grid”), presented in Table 11: allows overview of how far the network without reinforcement is from copperplate situation in terms of unsupplied energy, non-optimal dispatch, spilled energy, CO2 emissions.

Annual data, expected	Units	„copper plate“	„starting grid“	Difference
Total generation	TWh	4516	5026	509
Demand	TWh	4298	4298	0
Run-of-river generation	TWh	442	442	0
WIND generation	TWh	2238	2238	0
SOLAR generation	TWh	1021	1021	0
BIOMASS generation	TWh	366	699	333
NUCLEAR generation	TWh	0	0	0
“Peaking units” generation	TWh	1	177	176
Coal generation	TWh	0	0	0
Lignite generation	TWh	0	0	0
Hydro reservoir generation	TWh	449	449	0
Unsupplied energy	TWh	0	51	51
Spilled energy	TWh	208	772	565
Loss of Load Duration	H	0,97	3865	3864
Overall costs of system operation	mil. Euro	5 674	555 739	550 065
CO2 emission	Mt	0	86	86

Table 11: Annual results for the whole system – X-7

Level of security and spillage:

- Unsupplied demand reaches 51 TWh,
- Spillage of RES generation is also high (17% of available RES generation ; there is 565TWh of additional spilled energy compared to “copperplate” situation).

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

This additional spillage of renewable generation is partly compensated by additional 333TWh bio-mass generation and 176TWh “peaking units” generation.

Fig. 51 – Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation

Costs of the system:

Higher level of biomass and “peaking units” generation as well as costs for unsupplied demand increase total costs of the system operation in starting grid situation. Difference in total costs is on the level of 550 billion Euro, where 48 billion is due to biomass and “peaking units” redispatching while 507 billion is due to unsupplied demand¹¹. This gives room for network investments to relieve the congestions.

5.2.2. Annual results for the main countries at stake

Level of security and spillage

Particular attention is made to the countries with high unsupplied demand and high spillage variations (difference between spillages in starting grid and copper plate situations). With respect to this, countries with high unsupplied demand (>1 TWh) and high spillages variation (>10TWh), as well as spillage variation in North Sea and North Africa are particularly analyzed:

Areas	UNSUPPLIED ENERGY (TWh)	Shares of total ENS	LOLD (h)
FR	12.4	24%	2032
DE	9.6	19%	1189
UK	6.3	12%	1099
BE	4.8	9.5%	1120
IT	4.6	9.1%	1316
ES	4.5	8.9%	1237
NL	3.8	7.5%	594
IE	1.7	3.3%	1300
AT	1	2%	549
SUM	48.7		

Table 12: Countries with unsupplied energy variation greater than 1 TWh.

¹¹ Within EH2050, ENS costs (costs for unsupplied demand) are estimated on the level of 10,000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe.

Areas	SPILLAGE VARIATION (TWh)	Shares of total Spillage variation
NO	94.9	17%
FR	32.8	5.8%
SE	29.5	5%
GR	26.4	4.6%
UK	22.7	4%
ES	17.6	3%
IT	17.3	2.9%
PL	16.8	2.9%
PT	13.2	2.3%
LV	12.5	2.2%
LT	11.2	2%
IE	11	1.9%
SUM	305.9	

Table 13: Countries with spilled energy variation greater than 10 TWh

Areas, North Africa and North Sea	SPILLAGE VARIATION (TWh)	Shares of North Africa and North Sea spillage
North Sea	197	87%
Algeria (103DZ)	12.4	5.5%
Libya (105LY)	10.2	4.5%
Morocco (102MA)	0.4	0.17%
Middle East (101MI)	0.1	0.04%
Tunisia (104TN)	4.6	2%
SUM	224.7	

Table 14 – spillage variation in North Africa and North Sea

The results point to the following conclusions:

- ➔ Countries with high unsupplied energy are France, Germany, United Kingdom, Belgium, Italy and Spain. Sum of ENS in these countries is 42 TWh, of total 50.72 TWh, thus 82 % of total ENS
- ➔ Countries with high spillage variation are Norway (95TWh and 17% of the total amount (565TWh)), France, Sweden, Greece and United Kingdom. In North Sea zone, the spillage variation is 197 TWh, which represents 35% of the total variation. This means that it is really important to further connect these zones to the mainland, so that this energy can be exploited.

Thermal and other generation redispatching :

There is high **positive thermal redispatching** in United Kingdom, Spain, Germany, Poland, France and Italy. The sum in these 6 countries is 390 TWh of total 509 TWh (76%).

Fig. 52 – Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation in countries with high positive thermal redispatching – X-7

High **negative thermal redispatching** happens in Sweden, Portugal, Norway, Finland, Denmark and Greece; similarly to X-5 scenario, potential thermal generation exist in (almost) same countries as spillages, which points to these countries/areas as important energy surplus areas.

Fig. 53 – Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation in countries with high negative thermal redispatching – X-7

Conclusion

Deficit areas	Surplus areas
France (24% of total ENS)	North Sea (35% of total Spillage)
Germany (19% of total ENS)	Norway (17% of total Spillage)
United Kingdom (12% of total ENS)	France (5.8 % of total Spillage)
Belgium (9,5% of total ENS)	Sweden (5 % of total Spillage)
Italy (9.1 % of total ENS)	Greece (4.6 % of total spillage)
Spain (8.8% of total ENS)	United Kingdom (4 % of total Spillage)
Netherland (7.5% of total ENS)	

Table 15: Surplus and Deficit Areas – X7

5.2.3. Hourly results for the whole system

ENS and spillage issues are not only geographically concentrated, but that they are also confined to specific periods of the year. Therefore, time distribution of hourly ENS and spillage volumes in the whole European power system (expected values over the 99 Monte Carlo years) are presented in this section. This allows us to limit the scope of the study later in this analysis to specific, critical period of the year.

Level of Security

Hourly results give more information about hourly distribution of the operation indicators (ENS, spillages, generation redispatching ...) and their simultaneity. Hourly distribution of the system's unsupplied demand (ENS) points out that there is high ENS in winter season, in weeks 46-13:

Fig. 54 – Variation of Energy not Supplied (MWh): classified by 168 hours (7x24h, horizontal axis) and 52 weeks (vertical axis)

Sum of the ENS in 12 most critical weeks is 36,6TWh (of total 50,7 TWh). The most critical week is week 2, in which occurs a really high level of unsupplied energy. In critical period, ENS is distributed during the whole day with higher concentration in evening hours. Maximum “expected” hourly value of ENS (calculated as maximum of average MC year) is 45 GW and it is noted in week 2

Weeks	Unsupplied energy TWh
2	4
4	3.5
6	3.4
5	3.4
50	3.2
7	3.1
3	3
47	3
1	2.9
48	2.6
46	2.3
49	2.2

Table 16 : variation of unsupplied energy (TWh).

Concerning energy not supplied, the three most representative weeks are the week 2, week 50 and week 46.

Level of spillage

Spillage occurs mainly at the beginning and the end of the year.

Hourly distribution of the spillage variation (see Fig. 55) shows maximum spillage variation around noon during winter season. Maximum hourly spillage variation is higher than 140 GW. In summer, it shows maximum spillage variation during the night. The spillage variation in summer is low because the spillage is already very significant in the copperplate situation.

Fig. 55 –spillage variation (GWh): classified by 168 hours (horizontal axis) and 52 weeks (vertical axis)

The weeks of interest regarding spilled energy are week 52, 49 and 2. It has to be noticed that these weeks are also the most representative regarding energy not supplied .

In summer, a lot of increase of spillage can be observed in week 25 so this week is also retained for detailed analysis.

Peaking units and biomass redispatching

Regarding peak units, it can be seen in Fig. 56 that their usage is mainly located in the winter period : they are exploited in this period at their maximum possibilities in order to limit the amount of energy not supplied and to replace high amount of spilled energy.

Fig. 56 – Peak units redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-7

Fig. 57 – Biomass redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-7

Positive biomass redispatching is higher during summer and autumn, with maximum reached at night. They are exploited in this period in order to compensate the spillage.

Fig. 58: Hydro redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-7

Hydro generation is used to compensate spillage around noon. As a consequence, its generation is reduced in the evening and replaced by thermal generation.

Conclusions for the hourly results for the whole system are:

- The most critical season is winter: during this period highest spilled and not supplied energy occur.
- Week 2 is the most critical for the whole system, with really highest values of energy not supplied, spillage and biomass and peaking units redispatch.
- Ten most critical periods are weeks around New Year; these weeks are the ones with the most critical load level. In these weeks occurs 72% of energy not supplied variation.
- During winter season, there is ENS during whole day with maximum during evening hours.
- ENS outside winter season is significantly lower and happens during night hours as a consequence of network limitations.
- Spillage variations are the highest during days in winter

In weeks between 1-7 and 45-52 occurs 85% of total energy not supplied and 40% of spillage. For this reason week 50 and week 2 have been selected as two representative weeks. In the summer period, in week 25 a lot of spillage can be observed, so also this week has been taken into account for the analysis.

5.2.4. Hourly results for the main countries at stake

Unsupplied energy

As shown above, the five main countries with high ENS values are: France, Germany, United Kingdom, Belgium and Italy. These countries are analyzed and hourly distribution of the main indicators is presented below. For the all 5 countries, ENS presents the same seasonal and hourly pattern, similar to the whole system pattern : in winter, ENS is distributed during the whole day with higher concentration in evening hours during peak load periods.

The weeks of interest are week 43 and week 2.

- Spillage variation in North Sea is very high, in both aspects: total energy and maximum hourly values:
 - Annual spillage variation = 197 TWh
 - Maximum hourly value= 48.6 GW
 - There is no hour with spillage variation less than 1 GW

Spillage variation has seasonal profile, with higher values during winter season.

for summer and 35 for fall.

Fig. 66: Spillage variation in France (5.8% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

Regarding spillage in France, the weeks of interest are week 48 and 50.

Fig. 67: Spillage variation in North Africa (5% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

The results show that:

- Spillage variation in North Africa is also high:
 - Annual spillage variation = 26.7 TWh
 - Maximum hourly value= 10.6 GW

Fig. 68: Peak unit variation in France, hourly values (GW)

Fig. 69: Peak unit variation in United Kingdom, hourly values (GW)

5.2.5. Conclusion

The reduction of efficiency in operation due to grid constraints in the starting grid is summarized in the figure below.

Fig. 70 : Operation efficiency reduction in starting grid – X7

The analysis of the transmission requirements is further focused on characteristic weeks that are recognized on the basis of the above analyses. Detailed analyses of the constraints in the starting grid for those weeks are presented in Annex of this report.

Week	ENS	Spillage variation
2	High ENS (8% of total), particularly high in Central Europe (FR,DE), but also in Spain	
50	High ENS (8% of total), particularly high in Central Europe (FR,DE), but also in Spain	
25		High spillage variation

5.3. Grid development

5.3.1. Introduction

The reinforcement process is based on the results of the constraint analysis. The final architecture is determined through an iterative process and evaluation of the annual benefits of the proposed reinforcements in each step. Process is stopped when remaining issues (ENS, spillage, redispatching) are sufficiently small and distributed.

5.3.2. Step 1

5.3.2.1. Constraints in starting grid and reinforcements in step1

At the end of the constraint analysis, a first set of transmission requirements was defined which is implemented as grid reinforcement in this step1.

The map below recalls:

- the main indicators for the starting grid in winter week (week 2, on which the first set of transmission requirements was mainly defined),

- the first set of reinforcements

The target of these first reinforcements is to

- Transport available hydro energy from Scandinavia to central Europe;
- Exploit wind energy from North Sea;
- Reinforce internal UK network in order to reduce spillages and ENS inside the country;
- Enable transfer of RES energy from Baltic states towards continental Europe;
- Reinforce Italian network in order to reduce internal congestions and to bring energy from south (Greece) to central Europe.
- Enable transfer of the available energy from south-east Europe towards central Europe
- Enable exchange of the available energy between Ireland and France

Fig. 71 : Hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 with the starting grid, and reinforcements in step 1 – X7

5.3.2.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 72 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS by 32TWh (or 64% of total ENS)**; the main reduction being in Germany (5,25TWh decrease, there remains only 80GWh of ENS) and in France (4,15TWh decrease),
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 200TWh (about 27% of total spillage)**, the main parts being a reduction of 51TWh in NS and a reduction of 85TWh in NO,
- **reduced the amount of peaking units generation by 62TWh (or 64% of total peaking units redispatching)**, the main reduction being in Germany (20TWh decrease) and 11TWh in France
- **reduced biomass generation by 100 TWh**, with main reduction in Germany.

NB : At each step, and before moving to the next one, the cost of the tested set of reinforcements is roughly assessed and compared with the benefits to verify that the investments are profitable.

5.3.3. Step 2

5.3.3.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 1 and definition of reinforcements in step 2

The map below shows average values for winter week 2 after applying reinforcements proposed in step 1 (like in step 1, winter week 2 is the most characteristic week among the 3 selected in the constraint analysis for assessing ENS remaining problems, although other 2 weeks were also studied in each step).

The main goal of step 1 was to exploit energy in excess present in the periphery; while the main goal of step 2 is to:

- Transport energy from UK and NS to France, Belgium and Netherland;
- Collect more spillage in Greece and North Africa and transfer it to central Europe;
- Reduce spillage in Portugal and southern France and transfer excess of generation to Spain;
- Create a corridor from Finland that reaches east Germany.

Fig. 73 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 after step 1, and reinforcements in step 2 – X7

There are positive peaking units redispatching in central continental Europe (Germany, Czech Republic, France, Hungary, Italy, Spain and Romania) which is expected to be reduced by further grid reinforcements.

There is still a lot of spillage in UK, in North Sea clusters, in Scandinavian peninsula.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step2 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below) :

- reinforcements at IE-FR and UK-FR corridors in order to solve ENS in southern UK and bring spilled energy to the continent,
- reinforcements inside Spain and at France - Spain corridor are added to allow transport of energy from Spain to France,
- reinforcements of interconnection between Sweden and Poland in order to exploit more hydro energy from Scandinavia,
- reinforcement of east corridor from Finland through Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Poland in order to create a bigger corridor,
- reinforcement of Italian network and IT-GR interconnection.

5.3.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step2 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 74 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- reduced further the amount of ENS (from 17TWh to 9TWh),
- reduced the amount of spillage by next 160TWh, the main parts being a reduction in NS and North Africa,
- reduced the amount of peaking units by 50TWh and the amount of biomass redispatch by 64 TWh.

5.3.4. Step 3

5.3.4.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 2 and definition of reinforcements in step 3

The map below shows average values for winter week 2 after applying reinforcement implemented in step1 and step 2.

The main goal of step 3 is to:

- Reinforce North Sea network due to still available energy.
- Reinforce German network in order to transport energy from the periphery up to central Europe
- Reinforce again Italian network in order to exploit more spillage from Greece and North Africa

In winter week 2, there is ENS remaining in UK, France, Italy and Spain. There is high positive thermal redispatching remaining in Germany, Poland and Spain.

There is still a reservoir of spillage in Greece, in some clusters inside Spain, in NS clusters, in Scandinavian peninsula and in the northern part of UK.

Fig. 75 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 after step 2, and reinforcements in step 3 – X7

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 3 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below):

- Reinforcements again in the Italian network and interconnection between Italy and Greece, reaching German clusters,
- Reinforce interconnection between Denmark, NS clusters and Germany,
- Reinforce the upper part of the eastern corridor in order to exploit more energy still available in Finland

- Interconnect Greece with Bulgaria in order to exploit spilled energy in Greece and reduce other non-res generation in south-east Europe
- Reinforce the interconnection between Ireland and France in order to allow the spilled energy of Ireland to be used in France and in continental Europe.

5.3.4.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step3 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 76 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced again the energy not supplied (halved),**
- **reduced the spillage (reduction by 70TWh),**
- **reduced the amount of peaking units generation and biomass generation by 100TWh, with reduction distributed in Germany, Italy and UK**

5.3.5. Step 4

5.3.5.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 3 and definition of reinforcements in step 4

At this stage the ENS is still present. The map below shows average values for winter week 2 after applying steps 1, 2 and 3 reinforcements (winter week 2 is still the most characteristic week to illus-

trate the reasons for reinforcements of step 4, but determination of these reinforcements was based also on all characteristic weeks).

There is still a lot of spillage, but this is inevitable in a scenario with 100% RES generation. To assure sufficient energy in **all hours of the year** significant amounts of installed capacities are required that in consequence lead to over-production in several times.

Fig. 77: Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 2 after step 3, and reinforcements in step 4 – X7

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 4 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below):

- Further reinforcement of the three corridors from Scandinavia to continental Europe.
- Reinforcement of the direct interconnection between Norway and UK in order to direct the hydro energy available in Scandinavia also to and through UK down to France,
- Reinforce the grid in east part of France to allow that the cheap energy can reach Spain

5.3.5.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step 4 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 78: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- Reduced ENS to acceptable level,
- reduced the spillage to 308TWh (compared to 208 TWh in copper plate)
- reduced the amount of generation from peaking units and biomass redispatching by 100TWh, with main decreases in France and Spain.

After all 4 steps, significant issues have been solved with almost all ENS suppressed (only 0,02TWh remains), and a level of spillage is more than halved from 770TWh to about 308TWh (208TWh in copperplate situation). This is a really high value of spillage, also considering the results of the other scenarios but this is a characteristic of the scenario 100% RES .

5.3.6. Final grid proposal for the scenario – final architecture

5.3.6.1. Map with final architecture

The final grid proposal for the scenario is shown on the map below, where reinforcements higher than 1 GW are presented :

Fig. 79: Map of the final grid proposal for the scenario X7

Final grid proposal encompasses 378 GW of reinforcements that are in total 22800 km long.

5.3.6.2. Annual benefit assessment

The table below summarizes the evolution of annual ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO₂ emissions and benefit of the reinforcements on these values :

	Copper plate	Starting grid	Final grid	Benefit (final – starting)
ENS (TWh)	0	51	0	-51
Spillage (TWh)	208	773	308	-465
Operating cost (b€)	6	49	10	-39
CO ₂ (Mt)	0	86	6	-80

Table 17 : Annual values of ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO2 emissions – X7

The annual reduction of total costs is made of :

- 39b€ reduction of operating costs,
- 510b€ reduction due to avoided ENS if the assumed cost of cost of ENS equals 10k€/MWh, or 51b€ if it equals 1k€/MWh.

So annual benefit is equal to 549b€ or 90b€, depending on the assumption for ENS cost.

5.3.6.3. Technology selection and cost/benefit analysis

The cost of the full architecture is calculated for 3 strategies (see details in chapter 2) : “new grid acceptance,” “re-use of corridors”, “status quo”. Then, the annuity of each strategy is compared to the annual benefits (see graphs below).

Fig. 80: Total investment cost and cost/benefit comparison – X7

Investment costs in strategy 3 are the highest since this strategy considers only DC cables and refurbishment of the existing OHLs, where possible. Investment costs in strategy 3 (345b€) is around 41% more expensive than the strategy 1 (245b€) and strategy 2 (247b€). Small difference between ST1 and ST2 is due to free extension of existing corridors.

Significant share in investment costs refer to subsea cables that is the same in all three strategies. In this scenario, investment costs of subsea cables are 183b€ (same in all three strategies) and investment costs for onshore reinforcements are between 62b€ and 162b€, depending on applied technologies and public acceptance of new lines.

Whatever the strategy and the cost of ENS (10k€/MWh or 1k€/MWh), the annual benefits (90b€ in the worst case) exceed easily the total investment annuities (between 14 to 20b€).

However, these investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary for the proper functioning of the system. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

6. Scenario Big and Market (“X-10”)

6.1. Presentation of the scenario

In this Scenario, a global agreement for climate mitigation is achieved. Thus, CO2 costs are high due to the existence of a global carbon market. Europe is fully committed to meet its 80-95% GHG reduction orientation by 2050 but it relies mainly on a market based strategy.

Moreover, in this scenario, there is a special interest on large scale centralized solutions, especially for RES deployment. Public attitude towards deployment of RES technologies is indifferent in the EU, while acceptance of nuclear and shale gas, as energy sources, is positive since being preferred to decentralize local solutions. CCS technology is also assumed mature in this scenario.

Among renewables, wind as centralized RES are preferred in this scenario. European demand is 4300 TWh which, compared to other scenarios, is neither high (due to low level of new uses) nor low (due to low efficiency level). The European energy mix (without grid constraints) is presented in Fig. 81.

Installed capacities, demand and imbalances per country are presented in Fig. 81 below.

Fig. 81 : European energy mix, installed capacities and imbalances per country – Big & Market

6.2. Constraints analysis

6.2.1. Annual results for the whole system

Overview of results

The comparison of the two situations (“copperplate” and “starting grid”), presented in Table 18 allows to overview how far the network without reinforcement is from copperplate situation in terms of unsupplied energy, non-optimal dispatch, spilled energy, CO2 emissions.

Annual data, expected	Units	„copper plate“	„starting grid“	Difference
Total generation	TWh/year	4290	4482	192
Demand	TWh/year	4283	4283	0
Run-of-river generation	TWh/year	284	284	0
WIND generation	TWh/year	1386	1386	0
SOLAR generation	TWh/year	434	434	0
BIOMASS generation	TWh/year	343	310	-33
NUCLEAR generation	TWh/year	818	749	-69
GAS generation	TWh/year	608	848	240
Coal generation	TWh/year	62	114	53
Lignite generation	TWh/year	85	87	2
Hydro reservoir generation	TWh/year	269	269	0
Unsupplied energy	TWh/year	0	12	12
Spilled energy	TWh/year	3	205	203
Loss of Load Duration	H/year	0	3913	3913
Overall costs of system operation	mil. Euro/year	56 360	197 672	141 312
CO2 emission	Mt/year	39	101	62

Table 18 : Annual results for the whole system – X-10

Level of security and spillage

In the “starting grid” situation :

- The system faces 12TWh of unserved load
- Loss of load duration is 3900 hours, which represents 45% of the year
- There is 203TWh of extra spillage compared to “copperplate situation”, which represents 5% of total demand.

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

Fig. 82: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation for the whole system – X-10

The increase in unsupplied energy (ENS) and lower dispatch efficiency (increased spillages, cheap generation decrease and increase in gas-fired generation) is illustrated in Fig. 82. Cheap generation, such as biomass and nuclear generation cannot be utilized to their full economical potential. Similarly, spillage increases. In order to compensate decrease in output of cheap generation and increase of spillage, expensive gas-fired generation is activated. Nevertheless, a significant volume of unsupplied energy persists.

Costs of the system operation

The increase of the annual overall cost of the system is significant and represents around 141 billion Euros, where 120 billion Euros is due to ENS¹² while 21 billion is due to thermal redispatching.

6.2.2. Annual results for the main countries at stake

Level of security and spillage

Particular attention is paid to the countries with high unsupplied demand (ENS) and high spillage variations (difference between spillages in starting grid and copper plate situations).

AREA	UNSP. ENRG (GWh)	LOLD (h)	Relative share (%)
Spain	8839	2486	76,6%
Ireland	1535	1753	13,3%
France	529	220	4,6%
UK	414	732	3,6%
Poland	71	39	0,6%
Portugal	67	73	0,6%
Italy	20	124	0,2%
Switzerland	13	3	0,1%
Greece	12	37	0,1%

¹² Within EH2050, ENS costs (costs for unsupplied demand) are estimated on the level of 10,000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe. But results are validated with a variation of this value - 1.000 Euro/ MWh.

Germany	10	3	0,1%
ALL AREAS	11537	3913	99,8%

Table 19: Countries with high annual ENS – X-10

Table above lists the top 10 countries with unsupplied energy (expected values) and corresponding loss of load duration (LOLD). These countries account for 99,8% of total ENS. Spain alone concentrates 77% of the total ENS volume. Ireland accounts for 13%, France and UK around 4% each. Other countries shares are less than 0,5%.

AREA	Spillage variation (GWh)	Relative share %
North Sea	142295	70,2%
UK	22798	11,2%
Ireland	10340	5,1%
Norway	7859	3,9%
France	2676	1,3%
Italy	2650	1,3%
Greece	2214	1,1%
Algeria	2195	1,1%
Libya	2037	1,0%
ALL AREAS	202659	96,2%

Table 20: Main countries with delta spillage X-10

Table 20: lists the 9 areas with the highest spillage volumes (3 areas outside Europe, and 6 countries in the European power system). These areas account for 96,2% of the total spillage variation.

The main share of spillage is in North Sea where 70% of total volume of spillage variation is generated. Considering other areas, the UK concentrates 11% of the total spillage, followed by Ireland who accounts for 5% of the spillage volume. North Africa PV generation represents only 2,5% share in total spillages.

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

Main countries with thermal positive redispatching are presented in Fig. 83.

Fig. 83: Main countries with thermal positive redispatching – X-10

The six countries in Fig. above represent 94% of the total amount of gas-fired generation increase, with shares distributed as follows: Spain (34,4%), Germany (22,8%), Italy (15,5%), Netherlands (11,6%), Belgium (7,2%) and Portugal (2,5%). Spain faces the biggest volume of ENS but also the big-

gest gas generation increase. Reinforcing the transmission capacity of corridors towards Spain would not only help to solve ENS, but also increase the operational efficiency of the power system.

Main countries with negative thermal redispatching are presented in Fig. 84.

Fig. 84: Main countries with negative thermal redispatching – X-10

The major decrease in thermal generation (mainly nuclear and biomass) occurs in UK and Sweden. To a lesser extent, thermal generation decreases in Finland, Lithuania, Denmark and France. In the Nordic countries and the Baltic States, cheap biomass and nuclear units are not used to their potential, most probably due to the inability of the transmission grid to bring this power down to West and South Europe. Moreover, the UK has a large share in spillage and faces significant reduction in nuclear, biomass and gas generation, which points to this country as an important “source” of energy. In France, there is a decrease of nuclear and biomass generation but also an increase of gas and coal generation : they either occur non-simultaneously or result from internal constraints.

Conclusions: country at stake

Based on comparison of average annual results for “starting grid” and “copperplate” situations the main conclusions are:

- The highest ENS values are observed in Spain (76,6% of ENS). Other countries with significant ENS (>3%) are Ireland (13,3%), France (4,6%) and UK (3,6%). Above countries have 98,7% of total ENS.
- Highest spillage is observed in North Sea area, where 70% of total spillage is concentrated. In Europe following countries have major share in spillage: UK, Ireland, and Norway.
- The potential in cheap thermal generation is mainly in UK and Sweden.

<u>Deficit areas</u>	<u>Surplus areas</u>
Spain	North Sea
Ireland	UK
France	Ireland
Germany	Norway
Italy	Sweden

Netherlands	
Belgium	

Table 21: Surplus and Deficit Areas – X10

6.2.3. Hourly results for the whole system

ENS and spillage issues are not only geographically concentrated, but they are also confined to specific periods of the year. Therefore, time distribution of hourly ENS and spillage volumes in the whole European power system (expected values over the 99 Monte Carlo years) are presented in this section. This allows limiting the scope of the analyses later in this study, to specific critical periods of the year.

Unsupplied energy

Fig. 85: ENS hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-10

The Fig. 85 shows expected ENS volume for the European power system in each hour. Weeks 47 and 48 entail together 18% of the total ENS volume. This is due to the combination of a high load (early cold spell), planned maintenance and a low RES-based production. A high volume of ENS is observed also in weeks 2 and 6 which represent together 11% of total ENS. ENS also occurs during the rest of the winter weeks, especially on working days. In total, 48% of the ENS volume is concentrated in the 12 weeks of winter.

- Winter weeks with high ENS can be represented by weeks 48 and 6.

Spilled energy

Fig. 86: Spillage variation, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-10

This Fig. 86 shows expected increase in spillages due to transmission constraints in each hour of the year for the European power system, including North Africa and the North Sea. It can be noted that there is a clear correlation between wind generation and increase of spillages. Around 52% of the total increase in spillages occurs in Winter (28%) and Autumn (24%) seasons.

- Weeks 25 and 43 are chosen as characteristic weeks for further analysis of high spillage occurrence, in addition to winter weeks 48 and 6 already chosen before for ENS considerations.

Thermal redispatching

Fig. 87: Thermal redispatching, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-5

Thermal redispatching shows seasonal but also daily characteristics, with highest volumes in winter season during night hours.

Conclusion

Based on comparison of average annual and weekly results for “starting grid” and “copperplate” situations the main conclusions are:

- The most difficult periods regarding security of supply are weeks 48 and 6 and their surrounding weeks, where highest ENS values are observed in and around evening peak load.

1. North Sea (70% of total extra spillage)

Fig 92: Spillage in North Sea, hourly values (MW) – X-10

The area which provides major share of spillage is North Sea. Huge capacity of wind off-shore installations and insufficient links to demand areas is the reason of spillages. The highest spillage is observed in Winter (week 2), Autumn (week 43) and Spring seasons (week 10). From these weeks the highest level of spillage is in week 2.

2. United Kingdom (11.2% of total extra spillage)

Fig 93: Spillage in UK, hourly values (MW) – X-10

In UK the highest spillage is in Winter (week 2, 3 and 52) and Autumn (week 37, 40 and 43) seasons. The highest value of spillage in this country is in week 43. This spillage in UK has very high values in comparison to Ireland and Norway.

3. Ireland (5.1% of total extra spillage)

Fig 94: Spillage in Ireland, hourly values (MW) – X-10

The Ireland has high spillage in Autumn (week 40 and weeks 43-48) and Winter (weeks 1-3 and 49-52) seasons. The highest value of spillage in this country is in week 3.

4. Norway (3.9% of total extra spillage)

Fig 95: Spillage in Norway, hourly values (MW) – X-10

The highest spillage in Norway is observed in the middle of the year, between week 22 and week 26. The highest value of spillage in this country is in week 23. This is a result of hydro generation excess.

6.2.5. Conclusion

The reduction of efficiency in operation due to grid constraints in the starting grid is summarized in the figure below.

Fig. 96 : Operation efficiency reduction in starting grid – X10

The analysis of the transmission requirements is further focused on characteristic weeks that are recognized on the basis of the above analyses:

Week	ENS	Spillage variation
25		High spillage variation in North Sea and in Nordic countries,
43		High spillage variation in North Sea and United Kingdom
48	High ENS (11% of total) in Spain, France, Ireland, United Kingdom and Poland	
6	High ENS (5.4% of total) in Spain, France, Ireland,	

Detailed analyses of the constraints in the starting grid for those weeks are presented in Annex of this report

6.3. Grid development

6.3.1. Introduction

The reinforcement process is based on the results of the constraint analysis. The final architecture is determined through an iterative process and evaluation of the annual benefits of the proposed reinforcements in each step. Process is stopped when remaining issues (ENS, spillage, redispatching) are sufficiently small and distributed.

6.3.2. Step 1

6.3.2.1. Constraints in starting grid and reinforcements in step1

At the end of the constraint analysis, a first set of transmission requirements was defined which is implemented as grid reinforcement in this step1.

The map below recalls:

- the main indicators for the starting grid in winter week (week 48, on which the first set of transmission requirements was mainly defined),
- the first set of reinforcements

Fig. 97: Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 with the starting grid, and reinforcements in step 1 – X10

The target of these first reinforcements is to:

- solve ENS in south continental Europe and France from North Sea and UK (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist) and
- help in ENS reduction in Spain
- solve ENS in East Poland
- help to reduce expensive thermal generation in continental Europe

1.1.1.1. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 98 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS by 2,5TWh**, the main reduction being in Ireland (1,5TWh decrease, there remains only 30GWh of ENS) and in France (0,4TWh decrease),
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 75TWh**, the main parts being a reduction of 49TWh in NS and a reduction of 16TWh in UK,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 83TWh** , the main reduction being in Germany (30TWh gas decrease, and also 7TWh coal decrease) and in Italy, Netherlands and France (11TWh gas decrease for each),
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 13TWh**, the main increase being in UK (12TWh).

NB : At each step, and before moving to the next one, the cost of the tested set of reinforcements is roughly assessed and compared with the benefits to verify that the investments are profitable.

6.3.3. Step 2

6.3.3.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 1 and definition of reinforcements in step 2

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying reinforcements proposed in step 1 (like in step 1, winter week 48 is the most characteristic week among the 4 selected in the

constraint analysis for assessing ENS remaining problems, although other 3 weeks were also studied in each step).

close to north west Germany.

Fig. 99 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 after step 1 and reinforcements in step 2 – X10

The main goal of step 1 was to connect distant areas with energy in excess to continental Europe ; while the main goal of step 2 is :

- to refine step 1 where it was not sufficient,
- to consider reinforcements inside west continental Europe to transport energy into the area with major problems of ENS and positive thermal redispatching : Spain.

There is positive thermal redispatching in central continental Europe (North and North East of France, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Hungary, Italy).

There is still reservoir of spillage and of cheap generation in UK and there is still spillage in NS clusters close to UK: links inside UK and UK-NS have already been reinforced in step1 but can be further reinforced; there is spillage in NS clusters

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step2 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below) :

- reinforcements at NS-UK, north UK– south UK and UK –France corridor applied in step 1 are further increased,
- reinforcements inside France and France - Spain are added to allow transport of energy from UK and France towards Spain (to solve ENS),
- reinforcements UK-BE and UK-NL are added to transport energy from UK (wind, nuclear, biomass) to Belgium and Netherlands, to reduce gas generation,
- reinforcement NS-DE is added to use wind from NS to reduce gas and coal generation in Germany.

6.3.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step2 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 100 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **drastically reduced the amount of ENS (from 9TWh to 0,35TWh), the reduction being almost completely in Spain (from 8,8TWh to 0,2TWh, thanks to the reinforcement UK-FR-ES),**
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 57TWh, the main parts being a reduction of 49TWh in NS,**
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 70TWh, the main reduction being in Spain (55TWh decrease).**
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 25TWh, the main increase being in UK (15TWh) and in France (11TWh).**

6.3.4. Step 3

6.3.4.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 2 and definition of reinforcements in step 3

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying reinforcement implemented in step1 and step 2.

The main goal of step 3 is :

- to refine step 1+2 where it was not sufficient,

Fig. 101 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 after step 2, and reinforcements in step 3 – X10

- to deal with remaining problems inside continental Europe.

In winter week 48, there is ENS remaining in Spain, in Madrid and Barcelona clusters. There is positive thermal redispatching remaining in Spain and central continental Europe (North East of France, Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Hungary, and Italy).

There is still a reservoir of spillage and of cheap thermal generation in Ireland ; there is a reservoir of cheap thermal generation in UK, South Portugal, and Baltic countries, Belgium, Sardinia and Sicilia.

In the characteristic summer week 25, there is spillage in NS clusters close to Denmark and in Norway while there is (as in winter week) positive thermal redispatching in Germany and Netherlands.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 3 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map):

- reinforcements Ireland-UK, north UK –south UK and UK-France-Spain implemented in previous steps are further increased, and reinforcement is lengthened until Madrid cluster to solve ENS,
- reinforcement south Portugal – south west Spain is added to transport cheap thermal from Portugal to south west Spain,
- reinforcement Belgium-north east France is added to allow energy arriving in Belgium from the north to go until France,
- reinforcement from Baltic countries to Poland is lengthened until Germany and Czech Republic to reduce gas generation,
- reinforcement from Norway to Netherlands is added to bring energy from Norway to north Continental Europe to reduce gas generation,
- reinforcement NS-Denmark is added and reinforcement Denmark-Germany is increased to transport energy from NS (wind) to North Germany to reduce positive thermal redispatching.
- reinforcement from Sardinia, Sicilia and Corsica to Italy is added to transport energy (wind, solar) from these islands and North Africa to Italy to reduce positive thermal redispatching.

6.3.4.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step 3 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 102 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- pursued the steady reduction of spillage (reduction by 36TWh), the main part being a reduction of 21TWh in NS,
- reduced the amount of gas generation by 30TWh, with reduction distributed in Spain (7TWh), Germany (6TWh), Italy (5TWh), Netherlands (5TWh),
- allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 5TWh, with main increase in UK (2,7TWh),
- almost finished the solving of ENS problems : ENS in Spain has been reduced from 0,2TWh to 0,08TWh, the total remaining European ENS is 0,11TWh

6.3.5. Step 4

6.3.5.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 3 and definition of reinforcements in step 4

At this stage the ENS has been almost solved, and the further reinforcements are aimed at reducing the cost of generation by replacing expensive thermal generation by RES or cheaper thermal generation that is close enough to remain profitable.

Fig. 103 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in summer week 25 after step 3, and reinforcements in step 4 – X10

The map below shows average values for summer week 25 after applying steps 1, 2 and 3 reinforcements (summer week 25 is the most characteristic week to illustrate the reasons for reinforcements of step 4, but determination of these reinforcements was based on all the characteristic weeks).

There is positive thermal redispatching in Spain, Portugal, Italy, Belgium, Netherlands and Germany, while there remains cheap generation in clusters rather close to these countries : there is still a reservoir of spillage in NS, Norway and Greece, and a reservoir of cheap thermal generation in UK and south Norway.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 4 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map above):

- reinforcement UK-France-Spain has been increased,
- reinforcement NS-Netherlands and NS-Belgium have been added and reinforcement NS-Germany has been increased to transport energy (wind) from NS to North Continental Europe,
- reinforcement from south Norway to Netherlands has been increased and reinforcement south Norway to north west Germany has been added to transport cheap energy (wind, biomass) from Norway to north Continental Europe,
- reinforcement from Greece to south Italy has been added to transport cheap energy (wind, solar) from Greece to reduce positive thermal redispatching in Italy,
- reinforcement from north west Spain to Portugal has been added to optimize thermal redispatching.

6.3.5.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step 4 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 104: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- reduced the spillage from 36TWh to 23TWh, the main part being a reduction of 8TWh in NS,
- reduced the amount of gas generation from 56TWh to 35TWh, with main decreases in Spain (5TWh), Italy (3,8TWh), Netherlands (3,8TWh),
- allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 7TWh, with main increase in UK (4,8TWh) and France (2TWh),
- still decreased ENS from 0,11TWh to 0,05TWh

After all 4 steps, significant issues have been solved with almost all ENS suppressed (only 0,05TWh remains), and a level of spillage drastically reduced from 205TWh to 22TWh (3TWh in copperplate situation). Remaining volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatching are small and spread, which left no room for easily detection of profitable new reinforcements.

6.3.6. Final grid proposal for the scenario – final architecture

6.3.6.1. Map with final architecture

The final grid proposal for the scenario is shown on the map below, where reinforcements higher than 1 GW are presented :

Fig. 105: Map of the final grid proposal for the scenario X10

Final grid proposal encompasses 255 GW of reinforcements that are in total more than 16000 km long.

6.3.6.2. Annual benefit assessment

The table below summarizes the evolution of annual ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO2 emissions and benefit of the reinforcements on these values :

	Copper plate	Starting grid	Final grid	Benefit (final – starting)
ENS (TWh)	0	11	0	-11
Spillage (TWh)	3	205	22	-182

Operating cost (b€)	56	82	60	-22
CO ₂ (Mt)	39	101	47	-54

Table 22: Annual values of ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO₂ emissions – X10

The annual reduction of total costs is made of :

- 22b€ reduction of operating costs,
- 114b€ reduction due to avoided ENS if the assumed cost of cost of ENS equals 10k€/MWh, or 11,4b€ if it equals 1k€/MWh.

So annual benefit is equal to 136b€ or 33,4b€, depending on the assumption for ENS cost.

6.3.6.3. Technology selection and cost/benefit analysis

The cost of the full architecture is calculated for 3 strategies (see details in chapter 2) : “new grid acceptance,” “re-use of corridors”, “status quo”. Then, the annuity of each strategy is compared to the annual benefits (see graphs below).

Fig. 106: Total investment cost and cost/benefit comparison – X10

Investment costs in strategy 3 are the highest since this strategy considers only DC cables and refurbishment of the existing OHLs, where possible. Investment costs in strategy 3 (216b€) is around 57% more expensive than the strategy 1 (138b€).

Significant share in investment costs refer to subsea cables that is the same in all three strategies. In this Scenario, investment costs of subsea cables are 115b€ (same in all three strategies) and investment costs for onshore reinforcements are between 23b€ and 101b€, depending on applied technologies and public acceptance of new lines.

Whatever the strategy and the cost of ENS (10k€/MWh or 1k€/MWh), the annual benefits (33b€ to 136b€) exceed easily the total investment annuities (8 to 13b€).

However, these investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

7. Scenario Large fossil fuel with CCS and nuclear (“X-13”)

7.1. Presentation of the scenario

In this scenario, a global agreement for climate mitigation is achieved and Europe is fully committed to its target of 80-95% GHG reduction. Thus, CO2 costs are high due to the existence of a global carbon market.

Europe is mainly following a non-RES strategy to reach this target. Acceptance of nuclear and shale gas as energy sources is positive. Nuclear and fossil fuel plants with CCS play pivotal roles in achieving the 80-95% GHG targets without large scale RES deployment. There is a low focus on development of RES and storage solutions.

This scenario is characterized with high demand that reaches 4700 TWh, the second highest demand among analyzed scenarios. The European energy mix (without grid constraints) is presented in Fig. 107

Installed capacities, demand and imbalances per country are presented in Fig. 107 below.

Fig. 107 : European energy mix, installed capacities and imbalances per country – Fossil & nuclear

7.2. Constraints analysis

7.2.1. Annual results for the whole system

The comparison of the two situations (“copperplate” and “starting grid”), presented in Table 23: allows overview of how far the network without reinforcement is from copperplate situation in terms of unsupplied energy, non-optimal dispatch, spilled energy and CO2 emissions. The table below shows the main output of the two simulations.

Overview of results

Annual data, expected	Units	„copper plate“	„starting grid“	Difference
Total generation	TWh	4699	4738	39
Demand	TWh	4699	4699	0
Run-of-river generation	TWh	290	290	0
WIND generation	TWh	814	814	0
SOLAR generation	TWh	252	252	0
BIOMASS generation	TWh	325	294	-31
NUCLEAR generation	TWh	1198	1167	-31
GAS generation	TWh	1262	1282	21
Coal generation	TWh	77	159	81
Lignite generation	TWh	198	197	-1
Hydro reservoir generation	TWh	284	284	0
Unsupplied energy	TWh	0	7	7
Spilled energy	TWh	0	42	42
Loss of Load Duration	H	2	2366	2364
Overall costs of system operation	mil. Euro	91 839	171 599	79 760
CO2 emission	Mt	40	78	38

Table 23: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation for the whole system – X-13

Level Security of supply and spillage

In the “starting grid” situation:

- The system faces greater risk and volumes of shortage : there is 7 TWh of unserved load
- The RES curtailment is higher and more often: there is 42 TWh of spilled energy more than in “copperplate” situation

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

Grid limitations lead to a suboptimal dispatch of 100 TWh. 42 TWh of renewable generation and 62 TWh of biomass and nuclear generation are compensated by 81 TWh of coal and 21 TWh of gas. The thermal redispatching can also be noticed on the graph below: due to congestions expensive generation (gas and coal) is generating instead of cheap (nuclear or biomass) or must run sources (RES).

Fig. 108: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation for the whole system – X-13

Cost of the system

Higher level of thermal generation as well as costs for unsupplied demand increase total costs of the system operation in starting grid situation. Difference in total costs is on the level of 80 billion Euro, where 10 billion is due to thermal redispatching while 70 billion is due to unsupplied demand¹³. This gives room for network investments to relieve the congestions.

7.2.2. Annual results for the main countries at stake

Level Security of supply and spillage

When comparing starting grid and copperplate situations, particular attention is paid to the countries with high unsupplied demand and high spillage variations. For other scenarios, countries or areas with high unsupplied demand and high spillages variation are analyzed from rather high thresholds (1TWh for ENS, 10 for spillage). Because volumes at stake are far lower in X-13 compared to the other scenarios, the top 10 countries are listed. Deeper analysis will be carried out for the top 5 countries.

Spain accounts for 89% of the total energy not served. Italy and France account respectively for almost 5% and 3% of the total energy not served. Below a ranking of the main countries with unserved energy :

Areas	UNSP. ENRG (GWh)	LOLD (h)
ES	6062	1769
IT	315	770
FR	172	494
PT	98	89

¹³ Within EH2050, ENS costs (costs for unsupplied demand) are estimated on the level of 10,000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe.

IE	51	106
PL	49	23
UK	25	68
DE	25	4
GR	16	26
HU	6e	3

Table 24: Top 10 countries with ENS – X-13

North Sea accounts for 77% of total spilled energy in the system. Norway and Ireland account respectively for 15% and 3% of the total spilled energy. Below a ranking of the main countries or areas with spilled energy:

Areas	SPIL. ENRG (GWh)	RES PROD. (GWh)
NS	32245	167592
NO	6345	155724
IE	1212	25807
SE	979	83210
UK	410	157015
ES	238	197967
FR	90	134454
FI	64	24296
LV	8	11887
EE	7	7004

Table 25: Top 10 countries/areas with spilled energy – X-13

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

In the overall system there is a decrease in nuclear and biomass production after grid limits are introduced while there is an overall increase in gas and coal production. Lignite production remains at the same level, but:

- Nuclear redispatch of 31 TWh is made with 11 TWh in UK, 10 TWh in France, and another 10 in Sweden and Finland.
- UK, France, Finland, Sweden, Denmark and Norway account for almost 100% of total biomass which is not dispatched because of congestions.
- Spain and Germany produce large volumes of extra gas and coal due to network limitations. This is also true for Italy and Poland but to a lower extent.

Countries with **high ENS**: ES, IT, FR, PT, IE and PL. These countries can be considered as main countries with lack of energy, main deficit areas. The total energy not served equals 6 TWh. Due to grid constraints the gas production for Spain, Italy, Portugal and Poland increases. For France, biomass, nuclear and gas generation decreases. The coal generation for Spain, Italy and Poland increases.

Countries with **high spillage variation**: NS, NO, IE, SE, UK and ES. These countries should be considered as main “sources” of energy. North Sea accounts for 77% of total spillage. This is provoked by very constrained connections with UK and continental Europe. Further reinforcement will release this excess of generation. Again, due to grid constraints there is a reduction in nuclear and biomass generation. For Spain gas production increases while it decreases for the United Kingdom and Ireland. A similar effect but to a smaller extent is true for coal generation.

The main conclusions from the results above are the following:

- **The countries with the highest ENS are: ES, IT, FR, PT, IE, PL. Spain alone accounts for 89% of total ENS.**
- **The countries with the highest spillage are: NS, NO, SE, UK, IE, and ES. 90% of the total amount of Spillage is located in the North of Europe.**
- **The countries with the highest negative redispatch are: UK, FR, SE, FI, CH, and HU. 60 TWh of nuclear and biomass are redispatched due to congestion in France, UK, Sweden and Finland.**
- **The countries with the highest positive redispatch are: DE, IT, NL, ES, PL, PT. Due to grid constraints mainly coal and some gas production is activated in the Iberian peninsula, Italy and Germany.**

Deficit areas	Surplus areas
Spain (89% of total ENS)	North Sea (77% of total Spillage)
Italy (5% of total ENS)	Norway (15% of total Spillage)
France (3% of total ENS)	Ireland(2.9 % of total Spillage)
Portugal (1.5% of total ENS)	Sweden (2.4 % of total Spillage)
Ireland (0.7 % of total ENS)	United Kingdom (1 % of total spillage)
Poland (0.7% of total ENS)	Spain (0.6 % of total Spillage)

Table 26: Surplus and Deficit Areas – X13

7.2.3. Hourly results for the whole system

ENS and spillage issues are not only geographically concentrated, but they are also confined to specific periods of the year. Therefore, time distribution of hourly ENS and spillage variations in the whole European power system (expected values over the 99 Monte Carlo years) are presented in this section. This allows us to limit the scope of the study later in this analysis to specific, critical period of the year.

Unsupplied energy

Energy not served takes mainly place during winter period. It reaches its maximum hourly value of 19 GW during week 48. ENS occurs mainly at morning peak (7-9am) and evening peak from 4 to 9pm. Because of this extra solar energy will not help to solve this problem. Since 89% of energy not served in the whole system belongs to Spain, the pattern displayed here is almost the one as it is in Spain.

Fig. 109: ENS hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Spilled energy

Spillage occurs mainly at the beginning and the end of the year and during summer. Further in this document it can be noticed that overall spillage is mainly due to North Sea. The increase in spillage during spring is caused by spillage in Northern Europe. Maximum spillage variation¹⁴ of 17 GW occurs during week 25. At that moment load is lower, solar energy is at maximum and on top of that North Sea wind and Scandinavian hydro are still present.

Fig. 110: Spillage variation, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

¹⁴ Average over 99 Monte Carlo years

Below graphs are given that represent the thermal dispatching (delta starting grid – copperplate)

Negative nuclear redispatching is higher during spring and summer. The maximum is reached at night and during weekends. These are typically moments with lower load hours.

Fig. 111: Nuclear redispatch, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Negative biomass redispatch is higher during spring and summer.

Fig. 112: Biomass redispatch, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Gas generation in starting grid is higher at winter evening peaks on weekdays. This positive gas redispatch can easily be noticed on the graph below. Due to congestions, gas is much more used in starting grid during spring and summer compared to copperplate.

Fig. 113: Gas redispatch, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Similar to gas, coal generation in starting grid is higher at winter evening peaks on weekdays. This positive gas redispatch can easily be noticed on the graph below. During week 48 and some other similar winter weeks, coal production is reduced compared to copperplate. This lower coal production due to congestions will result in more energy not served.

Fig. 114: Coal redispatch, hourly values (MW) for the whole system – X-13

Conclusions

Conclusions for the hourly results of the whole system are:

- The most critical season in terms of ENS is winter with week 48 as outlier. During this week the maximum value of 17 GW is reached and 16% of total annual unsupplied energy is observed.
- In periods of ENS, it is observed almost whole day and peaks during evening hours. This indicates it is driven by the higher load at these moments.
- Spillage during winter is driven by North Sea wind, during summer by Scandinavian hydro, lower load and higher solar production. Maximum spillage variation of 17 GW occurs during week 25.

- By introducing grid constraints, the cheaper fuel types in the merit order, like biomass and nuclear production, are replaced by more expensive coal and gas generation. This phenomenon reaches its peak in spring and summer. In the meantime there is an increase in gas and coal production.

7.2.4. Hourly results for the main countries at stake

Level of Security

- **Spain:** Energy not served for Spain mainly appears in the beginning of the year on weekdays and to a larger extent at the end of the year on weekdays as well as weekends. The energy not served reaches its maximum at 7pm, the moment of peak load. Following moment will be analyzed in greater detail - week 48 (15% of total ENS for Spain).
- **Italy:** Energy not served for Italy mainly appears in the beginning of the year, during summer and at the end of the year. The unsupplied energy takes mainly place on weekdays and reaches its maximum at 6 pm. Following moments will be analyzed in greater detail - week 26 (5% of total ENS for Italy).
- **France:** Energy not served for France mainly appears at the end of the year on all days of the week. The energy not served reaches its maximum around 7pm, the moment of peak load. Following moment will be analyzed in greater detail - week 48 (55% of total ENS for France).

Level of Spillage

Fig. 118: Spillage variation in North Sea (77% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

Fig. 119: Spillage variation in Norway (15% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

Fig. 120: Spillage in Ireland (3% of total spillage), hourly values (MW)

- **North Sea:** Spillage for North Sea mainly appears in winter. Therefore following moments will be analyzed in greater detail: Week 1-7 (20% of total North Sea spillage); Week 46-52 (19% of total North Sea spillage).
- **Norway:** Spillage for Norway mainly appears during late spring and beginning of summer. Therefore following moments will be analyzed in greater detail: Week 22-28 (86% of total Norway spillage).
- **Ireland:** There is no clear pattern for the spillage in Ireland. There is probably a surplus of energy on moments characterized by a lot of wind. Ireland should be better interconnected to export this energy.

7.2.5. Conclusion

The reduction of operation efficiency due to grid constraints in the starting grid is summarized in the figure below.

Fig. 121 : Operation efficiency reduction in starting grid – X10

The analysis of the transmission requirements is further focused on characteristic weeks that are recognized on the basis of the above analyses:

Week	ENS	Spillage variation
22-28		Particularly important for an analysis of spilled energy
26	High ENS (1.4% of total), particularly high in Spain and Italy	
48	High ENS (16.5% of total), particularly high in Spain	

Detailed analyses of the constraints in the starting grid for those weeks are presented in Annex of this report

7.3. Grid development

7.3.1. Introduction

The reinforcement process is based on the results of the constraint analysis. The final architecture is determined through an iterative process and evaluation of the annual benefits of the proposed reinforcements in each step. Process is stopped when remaining issues (ENS, spillage, redispatching) are sufficiently small and distributed.

7.3.2. Step 1

7.3.2.1. Constraints in starting grid and reinforcements in step1

At the end of the constraint analysis, a first set of transmission requirements were defined. These were implemented and benefits have been evaluated. Furthermore, in the steps below the reinforcements could be slightly different than initially proposed. The reason for this is to be coherent with reinforcements in other scenarios.

The map below recalls :

- the main indicators for the starting grid in winter week (week 48, based on which the first set of reinforcements was mainly defined),
- a first set of reinforcements

Fig. 122 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 with the starting grid, and reinforcements in step 1 – X13

The target of these first reinforcements is to :

- Bring cheap and available thermal generation (nuclear) from UK to France and then to Spain to solve ENS problems
- Collect spilled wind generation in Ireland and in the North Sea and transport it to France and Spain
- Start solving redispatching issues in continental central Europe by increasing the connection to North Sea and UK

1.1.1.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 123: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS by 5TWh**, the reduction in Spain is 6TWh but at the same time there is an increase of 2 TWh in Italy. This means there is kind of a shift in energy not served due to this reinforcement.
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 13TWh** , the main part being a reduction of 12TWh in NS.
- **reduced the amount of coal generation by 20TWh**, the main reduction being in Germany, Italy and Spain.
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 20TWh**, the main increase being in UK and France (per 10TWh).

NB : At each step, and before moving to the next one, the cost of the tested set of reinforcements is roughly assessed and compared with the benefits to verify that the investments are profitable.

7.3.3. Step 2

7.3.3.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 1 and definition of reinforcements in step 2

The map below shows average values for summer week 26 after applying step1 reinforcements.

The main aim of step 1 was to connect UK which has energy in excess with Spain; while the main aim of step 2 is :

- to evacuate spillage and cheap thermal generation from Scandinavia and the Baltic states to The Netherlands, Germany and Poland
- to solve energy not served in Poland
- to solve energy not served in the South of Italy

There is positive thermal redispatching in central continental Europe and southern Europe (Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Poland, Spain and Italy).

There is still reservoir of spillage and of cheap generation in UK and Scandinavia, there is still spillage in NS clusters.

Fig. 124 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 26 after step 1, and reinforcements in step 2 – X13

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step2 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below) :

- reinforcements from Norway to the Netherland and to Denmark
- reinforcements from Sweden to Germany and to Poland
- reinforcements from North sea to the Netherlands
- reinforcements from Finland to Poland through the Baltic states
- reinforcements from Hungary to the South of Italy through Austria

7.3.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step2 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 125: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- further reduced the amount of ENS (from 2TWh to 0,5TWh) due to the reduction in Italy
- reduced the amount of spillage by another 20TWh, the main parts being a reduction in North Sea and Norway,
- reduced the amount of coal generation by more than 20TWh, the main reduction being in Germany (27TWh decrease).
- allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 10TWh, the main increase being in Sweden (5TWh).

7.3.4. Step 3

7.3.4.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 2 and definition of reinforcements in step 3

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying step1 and step 2 reinforcements.

The main aim of step 3 is :

- to solve some final ENS in Spain, Portugal, Italy and South of Germany
- to reduce expensive thermal generation in Spain, Italy and Germany
- to further reduce spillage in North Sea
- to transport cheap thermal generation in the UK to continental Europe
- to transport cheap thermal generation in Greece to the South of Italy

In winter week 48, there is ENS remaining in Spain, Portugal, Italy and South of Germany. There is positive thermal redispatching remaining in Spain, Italy and Germany.

Fig. 126 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 after step 2, and reinforcements in step 3 – X13

There is still a reservoir of spillage and of cheap thermal generation in Ireland; there is a reservoir of cheap thermal generation in UK and Greece and there is still spillage left in North Sea.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step3 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below) :

- reinforcements UK-Belgium to further evacuate cheap thermal generation to continental Europe
- reinforcements North Sea to Netherlands to further reduce spillage
- reinforcements Germany-Austria to reduce expensive thermal generation
- reinforcements between Spain and Portugal to solve ENS

7.3.4.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step3 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 127: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- further reduced the amount of ENS, to 0,2TWh
- further reduced the amount of spillage, to 10 TWh
- reduced slightly more the amount of coal generation
- reduced slightly more the amount of nuclear generation

7.3.5. Step 4

7.3.5.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 3 and definition of reinforcements in step 4

At this stage the ENS has been almost solved, and the further reinforcements are aimed at reducing the cost of generation by replacing expensive thermal generation by RES or cheaper thermal generation close enough to each other to remain profitable.

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying steps 1, 2 and 3 reinforcements.

There is positive thermal redispatching in Spain, Portugal, Italy, Germany, Poland and Croatia. There is still a reservoir of spillage in NS and Ireland and a reservoir of cheap thermal generation in UK and South-East-Europe.

Fig. 128 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 for ENS, after step 3, and reinforcements in step 4 – X13

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 4 :

- reinforcement Ireland-France to reduce spillage in Ireland
- reinforcement North Sea-Germany to further decrease thermal redispatch thanks to spilled wind
- reinforcement Romania-Hungary and Bulgaria-Serbia to transport cheap thermal from the east of Europe to the center

7.3.5.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this step 4 on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 129: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, coal redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- further reduced the amount of ENS, almost to 0
- further reduced the amount of spillage, almost to 0 (1 TWh)
- further reduced the amount of coal generation slightly
- further increased the amount of nuclear generation to the level reached in copper plate

After all 4 steps, significant issues have been solved with almost all ENS suppressed (only 0,05TWh remains), and a level of spillage drastically reduced from 42TWh to 1TWh (0TWh in copperplate situation). Remaining volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatching are small and spread, which left no room for easily detection of profitable new reinforcements.

7.3.6. Final grid proposal for the scenario – final architecture

7.3.6.1. Map with final architecture

The final grid proposal for the scenario is shown on the map below, where reinforcements higher than 1 GW are presented :

Fig. 130: Map of the final grid proposal for the scenario X13

Final grid proposal encompasses 253 GW of reinforcements that are in total 21000 km long.

7.3.6.2. Annual benefit assessment

The table below summarizes the evolution of annual ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO2 emissions and benefit of the reinforcements on these values :

	Copper plate	Starting grid	Final grid	Benefit (final – starting)
ENS (TWh)	0	7	0	-7
Spillage (TWh)	0	42	1	-41

Operating cost	92	103	92	-11
CO ₂ (Mt)	40	78	42	-35

Table 27: Annual values of ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO₂ emissions – X13

The annual reduction of total costs is made of :

- 11b€ reduction of operating costs,
- 70b€ reduction due to avoided ENS if the assumed cost of cost of ENS equals 10k€/MWh, or 7b€ if it equals 1k€/MWh.

So annual benefit is equal to 81b€ or 18b€, depending on the assumption for ENS cost.

7.3.6.3. Technology selection and cost/benefit analysis

The cost of the full architecture is calculated for 3 strategies (see details in chapter 2) : “new grid acceptance,” “re-use of corridors”, “status quo”. Then, the annuity of each strategy is compared to the annual benefits (see graphs below).

Fig. 131: total investment cost and cost/benefit comparison – X13

Investment costs in strategy 3 are the highest since this strategy considers only DC cables and refurbishment of the existing OHLs, where possible. Investment costs in strategy 3 (211b€) is around 70% more expensive than the strategy 1 (121b€).

Significant share in investment costs refer to subsea cables that is the same in all three strategies. In this scenario, investment costs of subsea cables are 93b€ (same in all three strategies) and investment costs for onshore reinforcements are between 28b€ and 118b€, depending on applied technologies and public acceptance of new lines.

Whatever the strategy and the cost of ENS (10k€/MWh or 1k€/MWh), the annual benefits (18b€ to 81b€) exceed easily the total investment annuities (7 to 12b€).

However, these investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

8. Scenario Small and local (“X-16”)

8.1. Presentation of the scenario

In the scenario *Small & local*, the global community has not succeeded in reaching an agreement for climate mitigation. Yet, Europe is fully committed to meet its target of 80-95% GHG reduction. Compared to the other scenarios, the European member states have chosen a bottom-up strategy mainly based on small-scale/local solutions to reach this target.

Common agreements/rules for transnational initiatives regarding the operation of an internal EU market, EU wide security of supply and coordinated use of interconnectors for transnational energy exchanges do not exist. In this scenario, there is a high focus on deployment of de-centralized storage and RES solutions (including biomass), while nuclear and CCS are not considered as options to reach the GHG emission reduction target. The public attitude towards the deployment of local de-centralized RES technologies is positive in the EU.

60% of the demand is covered by decentralized RES, while centralized RES fulfil 25% of the demand. Fossil fuel-fired power plants and nuclear power plants cover 5%, respectively 10% of the demand. X-16 is the scenario with the lowest annual demand (3200 TWh per year) amongst the scenarios considered in the e-highway2050 project. The European energy mix (without grid constraints) is presented in Fig. 132.

Installed capacities, demand and imbalances per country are presented in Fig. 132 below.

Fig. 132 : European energy mix, installed capacities and imbalances per country – Small & local

8.2. Constraints analysis

8.2.1. Annual results for the whole system

Overview of results

Table 28: summarizes the results of the so-called ‘copper plate’ and ‘starting grid’ simulations.

Annual data, expected	Units	„copper plate“	„starting grid“	Difference
Total generation	TWh/year	3263	3312	48
Demand	TWh/year	3202	3202	0
Run-of-river generation	TWh/year	289	289	0
WIND generation	TWh/year	901	901	0
SOLAR generation	TWh/year	752	752	0
BIOMASS generation	TWh/year	593	583	-10
NUCLEAR generation	TWh/year	315	304	-11
GAS generation	TWh/year	132	200	68
Coal generation	TWh/year	0	1	1
Lignite generation	TWh/year	0	0	0
Hydro reservoir generation	TWh/year	282	282	0
Unsupplied energy	TWh/year	0	5	5
Spilled energy	TWh/year	54	107	53
Loss of Load Duration	H/year	0	1884	1883
Overall costs of system operation	mil. Euro/year	32 638	88 283	55 644
CO2 emission	Mt/year	43	68	24

Table 28: Annual results for the whole system – X-16

Security of Supply

As can be seen from Table 28: , network limitations lead to 5 TWh of ENS per year. Loss of load or ENS occurs during approx. 1900 hours of the year.

Variation in generation dispatch

Furthermore, the spillages of RES-based generation roughly double (+ 50 TWh/year). The additional spillage of RES represents a significant share of the total available RES generation (2.4%) and the demand (1.65%).

These spillages, as well as some decreases in production from cheap thermal generation, are in part compensated by rather expensive gas-fired generation (+68 TWh).

Indeed, cheap generation, such as biomass and nuclear generation cannot be utilized to their full economical potential. In order to compensate for these decreases and the extra spillage of renewable expensive gas-fired generation is activated.

Fig. 133: Annual generation, spillage and ENS variation for the whole system – X-16

Costs of the system operations

The increase of the annual operational cost of the system is significant: it amounts to 54 billion Euro and more than doubles compared to a copper plate simulation. This gives room for network investments to relieve the congestions.

Out of a total increase of 55 billion Euros/year, roughly 45 billion Euros/year is due to ENS¹⁵. The remaining increase in operational costs, 10 billion Euros/year, is due to the reduced dispatch efficiency.

8.2.2. Annual results for the main countries at stake

Level of Security of supply and spillage

Before analyzing the hourly results of the simulations, a closer look has been made at the geographical dispersion of the ENS, spillage and re-dispatching issues. As shown below, the problems are concentrated in a limited number of countries.

Table 29: lists the countries with a loss of load duration (LOLD) of at least 10 hours and at least 10 GWh of ENS per year (expected values). Combined these countries account for 98% of all ENS. Italy alone concentrates 64% of the total ENS volume. France takes up 18%, Germany and Poland almost 5% each. Especially in Italy, spillages, increases in gas-fired generation and ENS-issues seem to occur

¹⁵ Within EH2050, ENS costs (costs for unsupplied demand) are estimated on the level of 10,000 Euro/MWh for the whole Europe.

simultaneously. One could wonder if these are the result of internal congestion. If this is the case, reinforcing the local transmission grid would optimize the dispatch. However, as we will show later in this report, these phenomenon occur mostly non-simultaneously.

	Unsupplied Energy (GWh)	Loss of load duration (h)
IT	2943	1644
FR	836	805
GE	214	51
PL	196	133
ES	169	96
UK	97	45
SE	13	12

Table 29: The countries with over 10 GWh of unsupplied energy and a LOLD of at least 10 hours-X-16

In Table 30, the 8 countries with the highest spillage variation volumes in the European power system are presented. Combined, these countries account for 90% of the spillage variation in the European power system.

Italy concentrates 30% of the total spillage variation, followed by Spain with 19%. In Italy and Spain, as well as for the countries in North Africa, the high increases of spillage are probably due to PV-generation which cannot be absorbed by local demand or the transmission grid.

In the North Sea (6TWh), as well as Norway, wind energy is probably spilled. In Northern Europe, this might also be due to the abundant availability of hydro power when the snow in the North and the mountains is melting.

Remarkably, Italy and Spain exhibit high spillages and large increases in thermal generation, mainly gas-fired. One could ask the question if these issues occur simultaneously due to internal congestion (see above). Note the relative size of the spillage volumes in the North Sea & Norway compared to the spillages of e.g. solar energy in Italy and Spain.

	Spillage variation (TWh)
IT	15
ES	10.4
NO	10.3
NS	6
SE	2.3
LY	1.7
Morocco	1.6
DZ - Algeria	0.9

Table 30: The top-8 countries with the highest spillage variation volumes – X-16

Thermal redispatching and other generation redispatching

The increase in spillages is compensated by dispatching (expensive) gas-fired generation. Almost all of the increases in gas-fired generation occur in Spain (24%), Italy (24%), UK (16%), France (16%), Germany (14%) and the Netherlands (5%). Note that Italy and Spain are characterized by high spillages and large increases in gas-fired generation.

With the exception of the Netherlands, these countries correspond to the countries that concentrate 98% of the ENS in Europe. This indicates that the transmission grid, connecting these countries to the outside world, is also congested outside of the periods characterized with ENS. Reinforcing the transmission capacity of corridors would probably not only aid to solve ENS, but also increase the operational efficiency of the power system during dispatch.

The major decreases in thermal generation (gas, biomass and nuclear) occur in Finland and Sweden. To a lesser extent, thermal generation decreases in Greece, Hungary, Latvia and Lithuania. In the Nordic countries and the Baltic States, mainly cheap biomass and nuclear units are not used to their potential, due to the inability of the transmission grid to bring this power down to West and South Europe. In Greece, Latvia and Lithuania a significant reduction in the amount of gas-fired generation is observed. This is probably due to grid congestion during moments of peak demand, in which these gas-fired units were used (in the unconstrained case) to support high demands in West, Southern and Eastern Europe. However, note the difference in scale between Fig. 134 and Fig. 135. In total, thermal generation increases by 47 TWh to cope with the increased RES-spillages.

Fig. 134: Spain, The Netherlands, Germany, the UK, France and Italy concentrate almost all of the increase in gas-fired generation.

Fig. 135: Hungary, Finland, Sweden, Greece, Latvia and Lithuania concentrate the largest decreases in thermal generation.

The main conclusions from the results above are the following:

- As the analysis above shows, the ENS-issues are mainly concentrated in six countries: Italy, Spain, Germany, Poland, the UK and Sweden. These countries concentrate 98% of all ENS. Italy alone hosts 64% of the total ENS volume and will be of major concern in the grid development process.
- Increases in spillages due to the grid constraints are more distributed. Ten countries are responsible for 88% of the spillages. In the Nordic countries and North Sea, RES-based generation is spilled due to a limited interconnection to the UK and Central -Western Europe, preventing this power to get to the load centers during peaks in the production from wind and hydro. In the South (North Africa, but also Italy and Spain), peaks in solar energy production trigger RES-based generation spillages. Interesting to note is the fact that Italy and Spain are jointly responsible for 33% of the spilled energy.
- These spillages are compensated for by increases in thermal generation, mainly gas-fired. This increase in gas-fired generation occurs almost solely in six countries: in Spain (24%), Italy (24%), UK (16%), France (16%), Germany (14%) and the Netherlands (5%).

Deficit areas	Surplus areas
Italy (64% of total ENS)	Italy (19% of total Spillage)
France (18% of total ENS)	Spain(14 % of total Spillage)
Germany (5% of total ENS)	Norway (14% of total Spillage)
Poland (4% of total ENS)	North Sea (8 % of total Spillage)
Spain (4% of total ENS)	North Africa (6 % of total Spillage)
UK (2 % of total ENS)	Sweden (3 % of total spillage)

Table 31: Surplus and Deficit Areas – X16

8.2.3. Hourly results for the whole system

ENS and spillage issues are not only geographically concentrated, but they are also confined to specific periods of the year. Therefore, the distributions of ENS and spillage volumes over time in the whole European power system (expected values over the 99 Monte Carlo years) are presented in this section. This allows us to limit the scope of the study later in this analysis to specific, critical period of the year.

Unsupplied energy

Fig. 136 shows the expected ENS volume in each hour for the European power system. From this figure, it is clear that ENS issues are concentrated in some weeks of the year. Week 48 entails 17% of the total ENS volume. This is due to the combination of a high load (early cold spell), the end of some planned outages due to planned maintenance and a low RES-based production. ENS also occurs during the rest of the winter weeks, especially on working days. In total, 44% of the ENS volume is concentrated in the 12 weeks of winter. The peaks in ENS, i.e. the highest generation deficits, are concentrated on the evening peaks. During spring, ENS is absent due to the abundant availability of RES (wind, solar, but also hydro as snow is melting) and a decreasing load (increasing temperatures). During summertime, some ENS occurs during weekdays, in the afternoon. This might be due to the combination of a higher load (due to cooling), reversed flow patterns on the European transmission system (triggering congestion in other parts of the grid) and scheduled outages for maintenance.

Fig. 136: The expected ENS volume (MWh) in each hour for the European power system.

Spilled energy

Fig. 138 shows expected increase in spillages due to transmission constraints in each hour of the year for the European power system, including North Africa and the North Sea. Note the difference in magnitude compared to the ENS volumes in Fig. 137.

From Fig. 138, it is clear that there is a correlation between PV and increase of spillage. Around 40% of the total increase in spillages occurs between 9 a.m. and 3 p.m. in the period March-September. The highest spillage volumes occur during springtime at midday.

During some periods at the end of spring and the beginning of summer, increase of spillage occurs throughout the day. This might be due to a combination of a low load and abundantly available RES-based generation (wind, solar, hydro due to melting snow in Scandinavia). As the analysis for ‘week 26’ in the second part of the report will show, congestion in the southern part of Europe does not allow this power to reach the load centers (e.g. Italy).

Fig. 138: The expected increase in spillage volumes due to transmission constraints (MWh) in each hour for the European power system.

Conclusions

From the analysis above, it is clear that most of ENS issues are concentrated during evening peaks in winter time. Especially week 48 is of critical importance for understanding ENS issues: almost one-fifth of the total ENS volume is concentrated in this week.

In terms of the increase in spillages, the correlation between PV and spillages stands out in Fig. 138. In addition, there is some period of the year at the end of spring in which there is an increase in spillage throughout the day. Both phenomena will be analyzed in depth in some typical spring and summer weeks.

8.2.4. Hourly results for the main countries at stake

From the countries at stake, seven countries with high ENS values (>1TWh): Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Poland, UK and Sweden are analyzed and the hourly distribution of the main indicators is presented:

Unsupplied energy

As shown above, ENS issues are concentrated in seven countries: Italy, France, Germany, Poland, Spain, the UK and Sweden. In each of these countries different effects may be at play. Therefore, we analyze the hourly, expected patterns of ENS in each of these countries.

In Italy (Fig. 139), ENS issues are mainly concentrated on week days between 4 p.m. and 8 p.m. – i.e. the evening peaks. Domestic spillage, mainly due to PV (see above and below), will therefore not be a candidate to resolve these issues. Interconnections will be needed. Furthermore, there is no obvious seasonal effect in the ENS issues in Italy. Only in spring, Italy is free of ENS issues, probably due

to the abundant availability of hydro-based power in the Alps due to the melting snow. These issues will be analyzed in detail based on some particular winter, summer and autumn week.

Fig. 139: The expected hourly ENS volumes in Italy (MWh) throughout the year.

In France (Fig. 140), the ENS volumes are much more concentrated. ENS occurs mainly in winter time (week 6 and week 48). During these weeks, a high load (electric heating) and low RES availability triggers load shedding throughout the day. In Germany (Fig. 141), Poland (Fig. 142) and Spain (Fig. 143), the ENS patterns look similar as the one in France. However, the ENS solely occurs in week 48 and is more concentrated on the evening peaks. Similarly, in the UK (Fig. 144), ENS occurs in week 48, with some peaks during some particular evening peaks.

In Sweden (Fig. 145), ENS occurs in week 48 and week 12. In week 48, similar effect as in the above-mentioned countries may be at play. In week 12, almost all ENS issues are concentrated in Sweden. At this time, demand is high in the North of Europe due to a cold spell and the maintenance period starts. In the rest of Europe, (RES-based) power is abundantly available; shortages only occur in the Nordic countries. The transmission constraints that prevent this power to reach the load centers in Sweden will be identified via a detailed analysis in the second part of this report.

Based on this analysis, weeks 48, 6, 12, 26 and week 36 are chosen for a deeper analysis. In these weeks, most of the ENS issues are concentrated. Moreover, these weeks can represent 'similar' weeks – we will refer to these weeks as 'week packages'. Each of these packages then represents a certain share of the total annual ENS volume. As such, week package 48 represents 44% of the total ENS, week 36 11%, week 26 14%, week 12 8% and week 6 20%.

Spilled energy

As shown above, it is clear that the increase in spillages is more dispersed across Europe. Furthermore, it was clear that there is a correlation between spillages and solar power. For the six countries with an increase in spillage of at least 5 TWh/year, we will analyze the expected, hourly values of spilled energy in detail below. Note that we here show the volume of spilled energy, not only the increase in spillage.

In **Italy**, where 25% of the increase in spilled energy is concentrated, one observes a clear correlation between PV and spillages (Fig. 146). During spring and summer, spillages occur around noon. The peak in spillage occurs during weekends, around midday, when the peak production of solar PV coincides with a low demand. Similar trends are to be observed in Spain (Fig. 147). Although not shown below, similar spillages profiles are to be observed in North Africa.

Fig. 146: Expected, hourly delta spillage volumes in Italy (MWh).

Fig. 147: Expected, hourly delta spillage volumes in Spain (MWh).

In **Norway**, spillages are concentrated in a very specific period in the year (end of spring – early summer) (Fig. 148). During this period, the melting snow in the mountains and the northern part of the country cause a large increase in the output of the hydro power plants, causing an excess in the domestic electricity supply. Congestion on the European transmission grid leads to spillages.

Fig. 148: Expected, hourly delta spillage volumes in Norway (MWh).

Fig. 149: Expected, hourly delta spillage volumes in North Sea (MWh).

In the **North Sea**, energy is spilled throughout the year. During periods of low demand, combined with a high output of RES-based generation (e.g. beginning of the year), wind energy is spilled throughout the day. When solar power is abundantly available in Europe, spillages in the North Sea increase substantially, as congestion patterns in Europe change and/or this power cannot be used to further optimize the dispatch.

Based on the presented analysis, we decide to further analyze week 26, week 36 and week 15. In week 26, we recorded spillages in throughout Europe, including Norway. In week 15, the highest weekly spillage volume occurred. Lastly, week 36 captures the spillage effects during a typical autumn week.

Conclusions

With regard to the ENS issues, especially week 48 turns out to be very challenging for the European system. A combination of a cold spell, the end of the maintenance period and low RES availability triggers ENS throughout Europe, especially during the evening peaks. In Italy, ENS occurs mainly during week days between 4 p.m. and 8 p.m., i.e. the evening peaks throughout the year. In Scandinavia, a high demand, low RES output and the beginning of the maintenance period triggers some ENS in week 12.

Similarly, the spillage patterns in the six countries with the highest spillage volumes were analyzed. Spillages are clearly correlated with solar energy production, especially in Spain, Italy and North Africa. In the North Sea spillages occur throughout the year in periods of the year characterized with a low demand. In Scandinavia, in particular Norway, spillages are concentrated in a very specific period of the year (end of spring – early summer), triggered by an abundant availability of hydro power due to melting snow in the North.

8.2.5. Conclusions

The reduction of efficiency in operation due to grid constraints in the starting grid is summarized in the figure below.

Fig. 150: Overview of the reduction of efficiency in operation due to grid constraints in the starting grid.

Based on constraint analysis, characteristic weeks can represent other similar surrounding weeks, leading to the following shares of ENS for each “week package” :

Week pack- age	ENS	Spillage
Week 48	High ENS (44% of total), particularly high in many countries (FR, IT, PL, UK, DE, ES).	
Week 36	High ENS (11% of total), particularly high at 16:00-20:00, in Italy	
Week 26	High ENS (14% of total), particularly high at 16:00-20:00, in Italy	
Week 12	High ENS (8% of total), particularly high in Scandinavia	
Week 6	High ENS (20% of total), particularly high in France	
Week 15		The week with the highest spillage

Table 32: Characteristic weeks – X-16

Detailed analyses of the constraints in the starting grid for those weeks are presented in Annex of this report.

8.3.2.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 152: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage and gas redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the amount of ENS by over 4 TWh**, the main reduction being in Italy (2.8 TWh decrease) and in France (0,7 TWh decrease),
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 20 TWh**, the main parts being a reduction of 9 TWh in Norway and reduction of 2 TWh in Italy,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 37 TWh**, the main reduction being in the UK (11.6 TWh decrease) and Germany (6.2 TWh gas decrease),
- **allowed an increase of nuclear generation by 8.3 TWh**, the main increase being in Finland (5.5 TWh).

NB : At each step, and before moving to the next one, the cost of the tested set of reinforcements is roughly assessed and compared with the benefits to verify that the investments are profitable.

8.3.3. Step 2

8.3.3.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 1 and definition of reinforcements in step 2

The map below shows average values for winter week 48 after applying step1 reinforcements. Similar as in step 1, winter week 48 is the most characteristic week among the 4 selected in the constraint analysis for assessing ENS remaining problems. Note that the other 3 weeks were also studied in each step.

Fig. 153 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in winter week 48 after step 1 and reinforcements in step 2 – X16

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 2 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below) :

- The backbone of the transmission grid in Italy is reinforced and connected to the islands;
- A 'radial' grid is deployed in Spain, collecting RES-based generation and bringing it to Madrid, from where it is transported to South-West France.

8.3.3.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this 'step 2' of reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

The main aim of step 1 was to connect distant areas with energy in excess to continental Europe while the main aim of step 2 is :

- to collect further spilled RES-based generation in Spain to solve ENS issues in the Barcelona region and further optimize the dispatch in Spain, Portugal and France;
- To strengthen the backbone of the grid in Italy in order to further address the ENS issues in Italy and to optimize the dispatch.

There is positive thermal redispatching in central continental Europe (France, Germany, and Italy) and the UK. Spillage persists in the North Sea and North Africa, as well as on the Italian islands.

Fig. 154: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage and gas redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have:

- **further reduced the amount of ENS (by 0.3 TWh)**, the reduction being almost completely in Italy,
- **reduced the amount of spillage by 12 TWh**, the main parts being a reduction of 8TWh in Italy and 5 TWh in Spain¹⁶,
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 14 TWh**, the main reduction being in Spain (8TWh decrease) and Italy (5 TWh).

8.3.4. Step 3

8.3.4.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 2 and definition of reinforcements in step 3

The map below shows average values for summer week 25 after applying step1 and step 2 reinforcements.

¹⁶ Spillages increase elsewhere (e.g. Norway), limiting the net spillage decrease to 12 TWh on the European level.

Fig. 155 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in summer week 25 after step 2, and reinforcements in step 3 – X16

The main aim of step 3 is :

- to refine step 1+2 where it was not sufficient,
- to optimize the dispatch in France by a stronger connection to Spain and the UK;
- to deal with spillages in the North Sea.

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 3 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below):

- reinforcements North Sea to Belgium, Germany and UK (London)
- reinforcements between Spain (Madrid) and France and extension to the UK to optimize the dispatch in Spain, France and the UK (positive re-dispatching).

8.3.4.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of these ‘step 3’ reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Fig. 156: Annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas redispatch and nuclear redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- pursued the steady reduction of spillage (reduction by 6TWh), the main part being a reduction of 5TWh in NS,
- reduced the amount of gas generation by 5TWh, with main decrease in Spain (1.7TWh)
- reduced the ENS volume almost to 0 (22 GWh).

8.3.5. Step 4

8.3.5.1. Analysis of remaining constraints after step 3 and definition of reinforcements in step 4

At this stage the ENS has been almost solved, and the further reinforcements are aimed at reducing the cost of generation by replacing expensive thermal generation by RES or cheaper thermal generation, close enough to each other to remain profitable.

The map below shows average values for summer week 25 after applying steps 1, 2 and 3 reinforcements. Positive re-dispatching remains an issue in the UK, Italy and France. Spillages persist in the North Sea, while cheap thermal generation (mainly biomass) remains available in the Baltic States, Belgium and the Netherlands, some parts of Germany, Demark, Poland and Eastern Europe.

Fig. 157 : Average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in summer week 25 for ENS after step 3, and reinforcements in step 4 – X16

Based on these results and values of the Marginal Cost Variations, the following reinforcements are implemented in step 4 (new reinforcements are drawn in bold on the map below):

- reinforcement UK- Norway has been increased, to enable better utilization of solar and wind generation in UK
- collection of spilled wind energy in the North Sea, connected to the UK, Germany and Denmark;
- reinforcement of the connection Sweden-Germany and Lithuania-Poland;
- reinforcement of the connection between France and Germany
- strengthening and expanding the connection Italy – Greece - Bulgaria;
- connecting Austria – Italy – Germany to further optimize the dispatch in Italy;
- reinforcements in eastern Europe in order to optimize the dispatch in Hungary, Slovenia and Serbia.

8.3.5.2. Annual benefit assessment

The effect of this ‘step 4’ of reinforcements on the annual volumes of ENS, spillage, gas and nuclear redispatch is shown in the graphs below :

Figure 158 : Annual volumes of ENS, spillage and gas redispatch (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years)

The reinforcements have :

- **reduced the spillage for another 7,7 TWh**, the main part being a reduction of 3 TWh in Italy and 2,8 TWh in Norway;
- **reduced the amount of gas generation by 7 TWh**, with the main decrease in the UK (5 TWh);
- **further decreased ENS from 0,022TWh to 0,007TWh**

After all 4 steps, all significant issues have been solved, with almost all ENS suppressed (only 0,007 TWh remains), and the level of spillage has drastically reduced from 107 TWh to 60 TWh (54 TWh in the copperplate situation). Remaining volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatching are small and spread, which leaves no room for easily detectable profitable new reinforcements.

8.3.6. Final grid proposal for the scenario – final architecture

8.3.6.1. Map with final architecture

The final grid proposal for the scenario is shown on the map below, where reinforcements higher than 1 GW are presented :

Fig. 159: Map of the final grid proposal for the scenario X16

Final grid proposal encompasses 190 GW of reinforcements that are in total 16000 km long.

8.3.6.2. Annual benefit assessment

The table below summarizes the evolution of annual ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO2 emissions and benefit of the reinforcements on these values :

	Copper plate	Starting grid	Final grid	Benefit (final – starting)
ENS (TWh)	0	5	0	-5
Spillage (TWh)	54	107	60	-47
Operating cost	33	43	33	-10
CO ₂ (Mt)	43	68	44	-23

Table 33: Annual values of ENS, spillage, operating costs and CO2 emissions – X16

The annual reduction of total costs is made of :

- 10b€ reduction of operating costs,
- 50b€ reduction due to avoided ENS if the assumed cost of cost of ENS equals 10k€/MWh, or 5b€ if it equals 1k€/MWh.

So annual benefit is equal to 60b€ or 15b€, depending on the assumption for ENS cost.

8.3.6.3. Technology selection and cost/benefit analysis

The cost of the full architecture is calculated for 3 strategies (see details in chapter 2) : “new grid acceptance,” “re-use of corridors”, “status quo”. Then, the annuity of each strategy is compared to the annual benefits (see graphs below).

Fig. 160: Total investment cost and cost/benefit comparison – X16

Investment costs in strategy 3 are the highest since this strategy considers only DC cables and refurbishment of the existing OHLs where possible. Investment costs in strategy 3 (192b€) is around 65% higher than the strategy 1 (116b€).

A significant share of the investment costs refer to subsea cables that is the same in all three strategies. In this Scenario, investment costs of subsea cables are 87b€ (same in all three strategies) and investment costs for onshore reinforcements are between 29b€ and 105b€, depending on applied technologies and public acceptance of new lines.

Whatever the strategy and the cost of ENS (10k€/MWh or 1k€/MWh), the annual benefits (15b€ to 60b€) exceed the total investment annuities (7 to 11b€).

However, these investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

9. Cross comparison of the scenarios

The five e-Highway2050 scenarios were defined to encompass a wide range of possibilities. As a result, they have very different levels of demand, types and localization of generation. It results in different transmission requirements but nevertheless, common conclusions can be drawn. This part of the report analyses the difference and common points between the five scenarios.

Fig. 161 : Main differences between the five scenarios

9.1. Demand and generation in the scenarios

9.1.1. Demand

Fig. 162 : European demand in the scenarios

The European demand varies significantly between the scenarios. The scenario *Small & local* has the smallest one (3200 TWh), close to the 2013 level (3277 TWh). On the contrary, the demand in the scenario *Large Scale RES* (5200 TWh) is almost doubled in comparison to 2013. The three other scenarios are in between.

9.1.2. European energy mix

Fig. 163 : energy mixes in the scenarios and in 2013

The share of renewable energy sources varies from 40% to 100% in the different scenarios. Wind generation is especially significant in scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES* with 40-50% of the generation. Solar plays a major role in the scenarios *100% RES* and *Small & local* with around 25% of the total generation.

Nuclear represents 20% or more of the total generation in three of the five scenarios: *Large Scale RES*, *Big & market* and *Fossil & nuclear*. Indeed, nuclear helps to achieve the EU target to reduce CO2 emissions by 95%. The scenario *100% RES* is nuclear free.

Fossil energy sources are significant in the scenarios *Big & market* and *Fossil & nuclear* with respectively 20% and 30% of the generation. Indeed, in those scenarios the technology of Carbon Capture Storage (CCS) is assumed to be mature. The share of fossil generation in the other scenarios is below 5%.

9.1.3. European installed capacities

Fig. 164 : European installed capacities in the e-Highway2050 scenarios

The installed capacities of renewable significantly increase in all the scenarios compare to today. Wind capacity ranges between 270GW and up to 900GW with a capacity in the North sea from 15GW to 115GW. For PV, the capacities go from 190 to 690 GW in Europe. Solar generation in North Africa is very high in the scenario *Large Scale RES*, it covers 7% of the European demand for an installed capacity of 116GW. In the scenario 100% RES, it covers 3% of the European demand and less than 1% for the other scenarios.

Fossil thermal capacity decreases compared to 2012 in all the scenarios.

Nuclear capacity increases compared to 2012 in the scenarios *Fossil & nuclear* and *Large Scale RES* up to 169 GW and 157 GW. It decreases in the other scenarios.

9.1.4. Installed capacities per country and copper plate imbalances

Fig. 165 to Fig. 170 present the installed capacities, the average demand and the copper plate imbalance for each country and each scenario. Values for 2013 are also given for comparison (ENTSOE data). The imbalances are defined as the ratio between the annual generation and demand of the country.

Some countries are net exporters over the year in all the scenarios, this is for example the case for Sweden, Norway, Finland, Romania, Bulgaria and Greece. These countries combine high RES potentials and relatively low demand. On the contrary Spain, Italy, Germany, Belgium and the Netherlands are importers in all the scenarios due to their high demands compared to their local RES resources. For countries like France, UK or Poland, the balance depends on the scenario.

Fig. 165 : 2013 installed capacities and imbalances [ENTSOE]

Fig. 166 : Large Scale RES - installed capacities and imbalances

Fig. 167 : 100% RES - installed capacities and imbalances

Fig. 168 : Big & market - installed capacities and imbalances

Fig. 169 : Fossil & nuclear - installed capacities and imbalances

Fig. 170 : Small & local - installed capacities and imbalances

9.2. Cross analysis of the level of constraints in the starting grid

9.2.1. Annual overview for Europe

The following tables and figures summarize the differences between the copperplate and the starting grid simulations for the five scenarios in terms of annual volumes and costs, in other words the impacts of the limitations induced by the existing network capacities. Values from the copperplate situation are used as reference case and considered as the optimal situation¹⁷:

Per year	Large Scale RES	100% RES	Big & market	Fossil & nuclear	Small & local
Energy not served (TWh)	23,4	50,7	11,5	6,8	4,5
Loss of load duration (hours)	3200	3866	3913	2366	1883
Extra spillage (TWh)	571	565	203	42	53
Gas re-dispatch (TWh)	+564	+176	+240	+21	+68
Nuclear re-dispatch (TWh)	-91	-	-69	-31	-11
Biomass re-dispatch (TWh)	+45	+333	-33	-31	-10
Coal re-dispatch (TWh)	+22	-	+53	+81	+1
Extra CO2 emissions (Mt)	211	82	62	38	24
Increase of operating cost (b€)	87	43	26	12	10
Increase of total cost with an ENS cost of 10k€/MWh (b€)	321	550	141	80	56

Table 34 : Difference in generation dispatching between starting grid and copperplate (annual values)

The annual loss of load duration in the copper plate case is less than 3 hours in all the scenarios, but the grid limitations of the starting grid result in values from 1900 hours in the best case (*Small & local*) to more than 3000 hours in the worst cases (*Large Scale RES*, *100% RES* and *Big & market*). The corresponding energy not served ranges from 5 TWh (*Small & local*) to 51 TWh (*100% RES*). Assuming a cost of ENS of 10 000€/MWh, it means an extra-cost for the system from 45 b€ to 500 b€ per year.

Grid limitations are responsible for an increase of spilled generation. It is limited to around 50TWh in the scenarios *Fossil & nuclear* and *Small & local*, but it goes up to more than 500TWh per year in the scenarios *100% RES* and *Large Scale RES*, representing around 10% of the European annual demand. The increase of the operating cost due to the non-optimal dispatch ranges from 10 to 87 b€ per year.

¹⁷ Given Values in this chapter can be understood as $Value_{Starting-Grid} - Value_{Copperplate}$

Fig. 171 : Unsupplied energy, extra spillage and increase of operating costs in the different scenarios, before grid reinforcements

100% RES is by far the most critical scenario regarding ENS. Large scale RES is very critical as well due to high load, spillage and redispatching costs. ENS is also significant in this scenario. Fossil & nuclear and Small & local face smaller but still significant issues.

9.2.2. Main deficit and surplus areas

Table 35 presents the main countries in deficit (facing ENS and/or positive redispatch due to grid constraints) and the main countries in surplus (facing extra spillage and/or negative redipstach due to grid constraints) through the different scenarios. It should be noted that a country can be a net exporter over the year and still lacks power during some periods and thus be called an “area in deficit”. Similarly, a country can be both “in deficit” and “in surplus” as those phenomena can occur during different periods.

			ES	DE	IT	PL	FR	UK	GR	SE	NO	NS
Large scale RES	DEFICIT	ENS	Red	Red		Red						
		Redispatch +		Orange	Orange							
	SURPLUS	Extra spillage							Green	Green	Green	Green
		Redispatch -					Blue	Blue		Blue		
100% RES	DEFICIT	ENS		Red		Red	Red	Red				
		Redispatch +	Orange	Orange	Orange		Orange					
	SURPLUS	Extra spillage					Green		Green	Green	Green	Green
		Redispatch -										
Big & market	DEFICIT	ENS	Red				Red					
		Redispatch +	Orange	Orange	Orange							
	SURPLUS	Extra spillage							Green		Green	Green
		Redispatch -					Blue	Blue		Blue		
Fossil & nuclear	DEFICIT	ENS	Red		Red		Red					
		Redispatch +	Orange	Orange	Orange							
	SURPLUS	Extra spillage									Green	Green
		Redispatch -					Blue	Blue		Blue		
Small & local	DEFICIT	ENS		Red	Red		Red					
		Redispatch +	Orange		Orange		Orange	Orange				
	SURPLUS	Extra spillage	Green		Green						Green	Green

		Redispatch -																		
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Table 35 : Summary of the main deficit and surplus countries in the scenarios

Spain and Italy are in deficit in all scenarios, they face high level of ENS and/or positive redispatch. Italy is an importing country in all the scenarios due to a limited potential of wind generation and no nuclear generation. Spain is more balanced than Italy, but is a net importer as well in almost all the scenarios. This is mainly due to a very high Spanish demand in comparison to today's level. Spain and Italy being peninsulas, they can receive a limited support from the rest of Europe in the starting grid, as a result, they face high ENS and positive thermal re-dispatch. The situation is the most critical for Spain which is less inter-connected.

In the scenario *Small & local*, Spain and Italy are also in surplus due to high PV generation around mid-day.

Germany is an area in deficit in all the scenarios. Indeed, Germany has a very high demand which cannot be satisfied locally if CO2 emissions are reduced and nuclear phase-out is assumed. It imports energy from North sea clusters and from the rest of Europe in all the scenarios. The grid limitations in the starting grid thus result in ENS and positive redispatch. However, being in the center of Europe and close to main energy sources (North Sea and Scandinavia), the situation in Germany is less critical than in Spain and Italy. This is also true thanks to the North-South DC corridors in Germany (assumed in the starting grid) which transport energy from the north to the south of the country.

France is in surplus in the scenarios with a high level of nuclear generation (*Large Scale RES, Big & market, Fossil & nuclear*). Indeed, France has the highest nuclear capacity in Europe and cannot export it if interconnections are not sufficient. However, France is also in deficit in four of the five scenarios, mainly due to high peaks of demand in winter. The interconnections in the starting grid are then insufficient or internal constraints appear.

UK is a major area in surplus in the scenarios with a high level of nuclear generation (*Large Scale RES, Big & market, Fossil & nuclear*). Indeed, UK then combines very high wind and nuclear generations which could be exported to continental Europe if the interconnections were less limited.

In the scenarios with less or no nuclear, UK is in deficit during certain periods even if it is not a net importer over the year. The critical periods occur when local generation (mainly wind) is not sufficient to cover the demand : the limited interconnections with continental Europe then do not allow enough imports.

Norway and Sweden are major countries in surplus in all the scenarios. Indeed, they have a rather limited demand but a very high hydro generation and also some wind generation. In Sweden, nuclear plants are also assumed in some scenarios.

The **North Sea** offshore clusters are of course in surplus in all the scenarios. Indeed, they have to export all their generation but the starting grid assumes connections to the shores up to around only half of their generation capacity. The increase of these connections is part of the study.

Other countries face less significant issues or are critical in only one scenario.

9.2.3. Seasonal and cluster overview

Fig. 172 to Fig. 176 present the major issues at cluster level for one of the most critical winter week for all the scenarios. Fig. 177 to Fig. 181 give an overview of the issues in a summer week for all the scenarios. They emphasize and refine the conclusions drawn at country level in the previous section.

Fig. 172 : X-5 Large Scale RES - constraints in the starting grid for a winter week

Fig. 173 : X-7 100% RES - constraints in the starting grid for a winter week

Fig. 174 : X-10 Big & market - constraints in the starting grid for a winter week

Fig. 175 : X-13 Fossil & nuclear - constraints in the starting grid for a winter week

Fig. 176 : X-16 Small & local - constraints in the starting grid for a winter week

Fig. 177 : X-5 Large Scale RES - constraints in the starting grid for a summer week

Fig. 178 : X-7 100% RES - constraints in the starting grid for a summer week

Fig. 179 : X-10 Big & market - constraints in the starting grid for a summer week

Fig. 180 : X-13 Fossil & nuclear - constraints in the starting grid for a summer week

Fig. 181 : X-16 Small & local - constraints in the starting grid for a summer week

NB: in summer, it can be noticed that some clusters face both spillage and positive thermal redispatching which seem conflicting. Actually, these two phenomenon do not happen at the same period of the day : spillage occur around midday due to high PV generation whereas positive redispatch occur the rest of the time.

9.3. Cross comparison of final architectures

9.3.1. Overview of the final architectures

Fig. 182 provides an overview of the transmission requirements developed in each scenario .

At first glance one can easily identify the predominance of “North to South” corridors. Indeed in all scenarios there are a lot of reinforcements that collect energy from the north of the system (North Sea, Scandinavia, UK, Ireland) to transport it at the limits of the continental synchronous area (northern Germany, Poland, Netherlands, Belgium and France) with opportunity for submarine routes. Major corridors also enable to collect energy from Southern countries like Spain and Italy but also to support them with the generation coming from the North.

As foreseen in the analysis of the constraints the scenarios *100%RES* and *Large Scale RES* induce much more transmission requirements (size and distance) than *Small & Local* and *Fossil Fuel & Nuclear* scenarios.

All scenarios, except *Small & local*, reveal the need for a reinforcement from Norway to North Continental Europe. A reinforcement from Norway to UK is necessary in scenarios *100%RES* and *Small & Local*, but not in the three other ones. In fact, UK is an area with energy in surplus in *Large scale RES*, *Big & market*, *Fossil & nuclear* thanks to the nuclear generation available there, while in *Small & local* and *100% RES* - with respectively very little or no nuclear - UK belongs to the “top 3” of countries with ENS. It is also worth noting that connection between UK and Norway in *Small & local* scenario is provoked by high level of solar in the south of UK which have to be exchanged with hydro generation from Norway and utilized during night peak hours. The reinforcement North-South UK is also present in all scenarios except *Small & local* because the four other scenarios have cheap energy to collect from Scotland.

A common north/south backbone in western Europe from England to Spain through France appears in all scenarios. There is an almost similar architecture in North of Spain for *Large Scale RES*, *Big&Market* and *Fossil&Nuclear* in order to solve ENS and optimize the generation in Catalonia and Madrid. It is different in *Small & local* because there is lot of spillage in Spain (solar, wind) and the reinforcements in Spain aim at collecting energy for northern countries.

Three scenarios have a huge capacity of off-shore wind installed in North Sea : *Large scale RES* (103GW installed), *100% RES* (114GW installed) and *Big & market* (76GW installed). This leads to huge needs for reinforcement from the North Sea offshore clusters for these scenarios while the reinforcements are smaller in the two other scenarios.

A couple of GW are necessary to secure and to optimize dispatch in mainland Italy, either through a solid backbone and/or support from the Balkans (Greece) and from North Africa through Sicilia and Sardinia. Thus, a backbone is needed from south Italy to North Italy (2 to 11GW) for all scenarios except in *Big&market* where there are high local thermal capacities in Italy and only the interest to collect cheaper energy from Sicilia, Sardinia and Greece.

Large scale RES and *100% RES* show important needs in major infrastructures in the middle of the continental system on top of the peripheral network required in all scenarios : the volumes of renewable in both scenarios, especially coming from North Sea, are such that full corridors from these sources to major load centers need to be reinforced.

In Germany the existing HVDC corridors, which are already part of the starting grid, help to transport energy from Scandinavia and the North Sea to the center of continental Europe. Depending on the particular scenario reinforcements within Germany or interconnection capacities are needed. But with an increasing share of renewable energy sources, as is depicted in scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES* the transmission corridors from north to south are not sufficient anymore and further reinforcements are required.

Central East Europe presents less need in reinforcements.

National borders are often subject to reinforcement. Especially in scenarios that assume a strong European cooperation guided by a political perspective, increased exchange capacities between the countries are inevitable for a sufficient overlay system.

Large scale RES

Fig. 182 : Transmission requirements identified in each scenario (GW)

Fossil & nuclear

Big & market

100% RES

Small & local

The following map (Fig. 183) presents the similarities between scenarios only keeping the corridors that have been reinforced in at least two scenarios. The map also displays a reminder of the range of the size of the corridors developed.

Fig. 183 : Common reinforcements (widths are according to average reinforcement capacity and the color represents the number of scenarios where the reinforcement is needed)

Fig. 183 highlights the common need of reinforcements among the scenarios :

- from North Sea, Scandinavia (Sweden, Finland), Ireland, UK to the outskirts of the continental synchronous area,
- Ireland-France (1 to 6GW),
- South UK –France (3 to 17GW) – Spain,
- Sardinia-Italy (1 to 8GW), Sicilia-Italy (1 to 9GW), Greece-south Italy (2 to 9GW)

As shown above, there are many common corridors. Nevertheless, there are large spans regarding sizes, which underline the differences in scenarios (local generation/ large scale centralized generation...).

Nota Bene: A Transmission requirement (“TR”) provides the needed increase of capacity in a given corridor with the purpose to solve SoS issues and/or to optimize dispatch. Sometimes more than one path¹⁸ is possible to reach the same objective, a mix of different paths is even possible. However, the definition of the optimal path was not possible in the e-Highway project due to the geographical scale of the study and the related uncertainties on cost. As a result, it may be possible to identify other paths than those suggested in the study that fulfil the same needs and are cheaper or more feasible.

9.3.2. Detailed analyses of the common corridors

Hereafter, the significance and behavior of the corridors common to all scenarios are detailed : main drivers of the TR developed and main trends of flows (direction, intensity, seasonality) are explored.

These behaviors are here analyzed based on average flows (over 99 Monte Carlo years in simulations) on a yearly basis, but also for specific month (thus season) and specific period (midday, outside midday).

Even if a TR is said to be used, in average, on a yearly basis from North to South for instance, that does not mean the link is never used the opposite way (it very often is the case). A more detailed analysis could be done on the huge data base for each link in each scenario, but priority has been set on highlighting the structural use of the TR to enable a synthetic understanding and comparison.

Under each map hereafter, some key drivers, triggering events of the transmission requirements in each scenario are given. When increase figures are displayed for instance in installed capacity or demand, these represent increase from year 2014's situation.

¹⁸ The meaning of « path » here is the list of clusters which are linked to provide the transmission requirement. For example, the most direct path from Greece to North Italy is to go from South to North Italy (link the following clusters : 68_GR - 55_IT – 54_IT – 53_IT – 52_IT), but another path could go through Balkan clusters and Slovenia.

9.3.2.1. UK – France - Spain

Fig. 184 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – UK-Spain-France

From Scotland, down to London area.

Except for the scenario *Small and local*, in all other scenarios, wind generation from northern UK and North Sea as well as nuclear power (when any) and Norwegian support in *100%RES* scenario, are collected and brought to the main load centers (Birmingham and London areas) and to continental Europe.

Flows are globally unidirectional: North to South, with maximum values reached in winter with a total flow ranging from 8 (*100% RES*) to 15/19GW (*Big and Market*) **in average** all day.

In the *Small and local* scenario no major reinforcement is implemented in Scotland or northern England due to limited wind and nuclear installed capacities. Support from Norway is directly injected in main load area (Birmingham and London) with additional 6GW extra capacity from north used to secure the supply mainly in winter.

Between UK and France

The reinforced link (South-east England to Normandy : + 3GW in *Large Scale RES* up to +15GW in *Fossil & Nuclear*) is used in both directions but with a clear predominant southbound flow, with even some congestion¹⁹ (from 10 to 30% of the year). Maximum flows between UK and France occur in winter (from 2GW up to 12GW in average) bringing support from UK to continental Europe. The link is used northbound, or at 0-flow, in spring especially at midday when PV generation in continental Europe is at its maximum. In *Small and local* and *100% RES* scenarios where PV volumes installed are maximum, France to UK flows can also be observed at noon in summer and even at noon in winter for *Small and local*. Additional capacity is also developed between UK and the northern French cluster (+3GW to +12 GW). This link behaves as the link described here before. It is very often congested southbound (40% in average in all scenarios). Reverse flows are rare, except for the *Small & local* scenario.

Through Western France

Between Normandy to Aquitaine (clusters 22, 17 and 14 in France) the extra grid capacity developed ranging between 4 to 17 GW depending on the scenarios, is used mainly southward especially in winter. Smaller flow or even an inversion of flows is observed in spring and summer especially around midday.

Between clusters 14 and 15 in France (South West), an additional capacity ranging from 3 to 10 GW is developed in 3 scenarios (*100% RES*, *Big & Market*, *Fossil & Nuclear*). This capacity is used almost exclusively from 14 to 15 with biggest flows encountered in *Big and Market*, *Fossil Fuel & Nuclear* scenarios in winter and summer when load in Catalonia needs to be secured. In *100% RES* this link is used both ways from west to east in winter and in the opposite direction when PV is high in Spain and North Africa.

Between France and Spain

The reinforced corridor in the west ([+5 GW; +8GW] is used in average from France towards Spain, but congestion can occur in the opposite direction as well. Maximum southbound flows are observed in summer outside midday. Indeed, at this period, there is no or few solar generation in Spain but there are available wind and/or nuclear generation in the north of Europe which cannot be completely consumed there as it is the case in winter, due to a smaller load. As a result, this cheap generation is exported to Spain to avoid the start-up of local expensive thermal generation as it is done in winter. Maximum northbound flows are measured in Spring at midday (PV surplus sent up north). In the scenario *Small & local*, these northbound flows to avoid PV spillage in Spain are the main drivers of this reinforcement.

The interconnection Spain-France is reinforced on the **eastern border** in all scenario but *Small and Local* [+8GW to 14GW]. It is intensively used southbound with maximum flows in summer (same explanation as the previous one), and in winter especially outside the midday period (9 GW in average) to serve load of Catalonia. Flows are minimal in spring, especially at noon, and may even go from Catalonia to France in *100%RES* scenario and *Small & local* scenario.

¹⁹ When the link is used at its full capacity

Inside Spain: Catalonia (cluster 06), central east (cluster 11), Madrid (cluster 07).

In all scenarios, a 2 GW up to 9 GW capacity is added between Catalonia and central east Spain. This capacity is used in both directions in all 4 scenarios. Nevertheless in 100% RES the link is predominantly used northbound (towards Catalonia; almost 100GW of additional PV in Spain). Otherwise the link is used southbound in winter and summer especially outside noon and in the opposite direction in spring.

The additional capacity between Madrid and Central East (especially in *Large Scale RES* and *Fossil Fuel and Nuclear* where 2 and 5 GW are added) is used in both directions : from Madrid to Central East when PV is high, in the opposite direction especially in *Fossil Fuel & Nuclear* scenario in winter, to secure load in Madrid.

Additional remarks :

Given the size of the corridor added across France in scenario *Big and Market* and *Fossil fuel & nuclear*, one could wonder if this 14-17 GW corridor could be put for instance in the sea with no required interaction with the French clusters along the way. Actually, part of it could but at least 50 up to 70 % should go through these clusters to enable positive/negative injection from existing AC grid. In summer, mostly positive injections from existing AC grid to the corridor are at stake, meaning extra competitive generation from these French cluster join English support towards Spain. In winter, large volumes flowing on the corridor need to be injected in to secure the load, especially in scenario *Fossil and nuclear*, for instance in central west France (cluster 17).

It can be surprising that no major south to north flows occur in summer around midday in the scenarios with high PV generation. Actually, it should be noted that, in those cases, there is already a significant PV generation in the center of Europe and especially in France resulting in average to a couple of GW of spillage in these countries around midday. As a consequence, the PV generation in Spain is spilled as well and is not transported to the North.

It should be noted that in all the scenarios, the demand increased significantly more in Spain than in the other countries. This is due to the historical trends used to estimate the national demands. This high demand leads Spain to import electricity thanks to major North to South flows. Lower assumptions for the Spanish demand would result in the predominance of South to North flows to export PV surplus from Spain to the North of Europe, especially in spring and fall. The Spain-France-UK corridor would then still be very profitable, however its size in the scenarios with limited PV (*Big & market* and *Fossil & nuclear*) might be over-estimated by some GWs.

9.3.2.2. Ireland-UK- France

Fig. 185 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – Ireland-UK-France

The level of installed capacity in wind farms in Ireland together with the load increase are the clear driver for the level of interconnection between Ireland and UK or France.

These links enable the Irish wind generation to reach load centers in continental Europe and UK, but also to secure the Irish load, in case of no wind.

In all scenarios the links developed are used in both directions, in average energy flows from Ireland to France or UK, in winter, and in the opposite direction in spring and summer (especially around midday), when wind in Ireland weakens and PV in the south of Europe is high.

9.3.2.3. Sweden to continental Europe

tion installed +9GW Hydro -3 GW Nuclear Capacity added Sweden to Germany or Denmark = 12 GW	tion installed +15GW hydro Less demand -9GW Nuclear +6GW biomass Capacity added Sweden to Germany = 15 GW	+2 GW Hydro +3 GW biomass Capacity added Sweden to Germany and Poland = 6 GW	+3 GW biomass +7GW (Wind/PV/Hydro) Capacity added Sweden to Germany and Poland = 8GW	No nuclear +6 GW biomass +10GW (Wind/PV/Hydro) Capacity added Sweden to Germany : +6GW
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Fig. 186 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – Sweden-Continental Europe

In all scenarios, the corridors reinforced inside Sweden accommodate North to south flows, that are maximal in winter and summer when energy is needed south (SoS, and optimal dispatch). Sweden is indeed a clear surplus area in all scenarios.

South to north flows occur in early spring at noon when PV is high in continental Europe (especially in *Small and Local* and *100% RES* scenarios). This is particularly true in southern Sweden. In summer at noon the flows are moderate but remain in average oriented to the south due to significant run of river generation. Hydro generation with reservoir from Scandinavia is shifted to hours when PV is not available, yet generation is needed, especially early mornings and evenings.

The links between Sweden and continental Europe are mainly used southbound with maximum flows in winter and summer (especially outside midday). But opposite flows also occur in early spring when flows can reach in average 3GW (resp. 5) between northern Germany and Sweden in scenario *100% RES* (resp. *Small and local*).

In the scenario *Big and Market* the link between Sweden and Germany is more used in summer than winter.

9.3.2.4. Norway to continental Europe and UK

Fig. 187 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – Norway-Continental Europe

Norway is in 2050 an area with a high potential for export in all scenarios. The level of grid development by 2050 for Norway is naturally led by the installation of new hydro capacity and wind generation. In *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES*, huge capacities are deployed in Norway leading to intensive needs for interconnections (>12GW).

In *Big & Market* and *Fossil Fuel & Nuclear* scenarios, extra connections are significant with a total of 4 to 6 GW additional capacities to northern continental Europe.

In all scenarios except *Big & Market*, reinforcements in northern Norway are necessary from 2 up to 5GW, and used from north to south, with maximum values in winter and summer (average flow of 3000 MW in *100% RES* and *Large Scale RES* scenarios) to bring down hydro generation or wind to the southern clusters in Norway (where the load is), continental Europe or UK.

In *100%RES* (resp. *Small & Local*) a 5GW (resp. 12 GW) capacity is developed to connect southern Norway to central UK. In these 2 scenarios, UK faces risk of shortage or lacks of competitive energy. The link is used from Norway to UK, in winter and summer especially outside midday. Flows are minimal in spring or even reversed at noon throughout the year due to PV generation (in UK and continental Europe) making support from Norway less needed, enabling more pumping in Norway.

In all scenarios except *Small & Local*, Norway’s connections to continental Europe (Germany, Netherlands and Denmark) are also increased especially in *100%RES* and *Large Scale RES* where more than 20 GW are added. Southbound flows are maximal in winter and summer (average flows to continent greater than 15 GW). Flows are minimal in spring at midday. For the reinforcement from Norway to North continental Europe, several routes are possible, as illustrated in the different scenarios (through North Sea clusters and/or Denmark and/or none of them; see Nota Bene on the different possible paths in the § 9.3.1 “Overview of the final architecture”).

9.3.2.5. *Finland – Baltic states - Poland*

Fig. 188 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – Finland-Baltic States-Poland

Large renewable capacities are installed in Finland (hydro, wind generation), Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania (wind and biomass), but also nuclear in Lithuania in 4 scenarios. In the meantime load increases rapidly in Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia (x2).

Transmission requirements estimated in this study enable these areas to export competitive energy to continental Europe, especially to Poland with a potential ranging from 2 to 8 GW of additional grid capacity.

²⁰ All=: Finland + Estonia + Lithuania+ Latvia

Flows are oriented southbound in average, from Finland to Poland, they grow stronger going through Estonia, Latvia, and mainly Lithuania, collecting available generation along the way. Flows to Poland from Lithuania are maximal in winter in all scenarios.

9.3.2.6. North Sea

Fig. 189 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – North-Sea connections

In all scenarios, part of North Sea wind generation is brought to continental Europe to solve ENS and optimize thermal redispatching.

In the initial grid, the capacities of the radial links are only around half of the installed North Sea off-shore wind capacities (cf §3.1.3) and there is no initial meshing (except the skeleton of a circular meshing with 1MW capacity), in order to enable further radial (from off-shore clusters to on-shore cluster) and/or circular (between off-shore North Sea clusters) reinforcements. As illustrated in the following examples, several paths are possible to reach the same purpose.

Some off-shore clusters with huge volumes of wind power are not close to clusters in deficit of energy. For example, the off-shore cluster near west Denmark is interesting for providing energy to north continental Europe rather than Denmark which doesn't need it. In this case, there are several possible routes to go from off-shore cluster to a cluster with deficit in energy (Germany for example):

- either through Denmark (radial connection to DK + extra capacity DK-DE)
- and/or through a circular meshing between off-shore North Sea clusters (Off shore cluster close to Denmark -> Off shore cluster close to Germany -> cluster in North Germany).

Another example concerns an off-shore cluster close to South UK : a huge part of its wind power is useful for North Continental Europe through Belgium : the path could be :

- either through UK,
- either through a circular meshing between off-shore North Sea clusters (Off shore cluster close to UK -> Off shore cluster close to Belgium -> Belgium).
- or directly to Belgium.

The optimal choice between those possible paths requires a detailed analysis of the costs, including detailed possible routes. It is not feasible in the e-Highway2050 project.

The reinforcements of radial links Norway off-shore cluster - Norway in 100% RES and Sweden off-shore cluster – Sweden in Large Scale RES and Fossil fuel & nuclear aim at collecting North Sea wind generation for continental Europe (through on-shore Norway and Sweden clusters).

Part of North Sea wind generation is brought to UK in all scenarios. In 100% RES and Small & Local, it mainly helps UK which faces risk of shortage or lacks of competitive energy, while in the other scenarios it is further transmitted through UK to continental West Europe.

Finally, all radial links are reinforced at least in one scenario. The total volumes of reinforcement in North Sea ranges between [7GW, 65GW], consistent with wind installed capacity in North Sea for each scenario.

Maximum radial flows occur in winter (when load factor of wind power are maximum).

9.3.2.7. Italy

Fig. 190 : Detailed view on link in scenarios – Pan Italian Link

From Greece to South Italy

In all scenarios, RES and thermal cheap generation from Greece (and North Africa) is brought to Italy to secure load and replace expensive thermal generation.

The extra grid capacity developed for that purpose, ranging from 2 to 9GW (depending on the scenarios), is used mainly from Greece to South Italy, with biggest flows encountered in *100%RES* in winter (8GW **in average** all day), when load in Italy needs to be secured. Smaller flows (or even an inversion of flows in *Small & Local* and *Fossil fuel & nuclear*) are observed in summer around mid-day when Italian high capacity of solar is at its maximum.

From Sicilia and Sardinia to South Italy

Except for the scenario *Fossil fuel & nuclear* (which has no connection with North Africa), solar generation from North Africa is brought to Italy through Sicilia and Sardinia to replace expensive thermal generation and only part of ENS (during the periods of highest ENS, at evening peaks in winter, regarding solar, only part of Concentrated Solar Power is still available). Average flows are always northward.

In *Fossil fuel & nuclear*, average flows are always southward to Sicilia and Sardinia to secure Sicilian load and bring cheaper generation to Sicilia and Sardinia coming downward through Italy from eastern Europe.

From South Italy to North Italy

Except for the scenario *Fossil fuel & nuclear*, solar generation from North Africa is brought through Italy northward to supply main cities in the north of Italy and also further in northern Europe.

In the scenario *Fossil fuel & nuclear*, cheaper generation from Eastern Europe is brought downward through North Italy to main cities in Italy (in the north and in the center).

The Italian backbone is reinforced in all scenarios ([2GW; 11GW]) but Big & Market in which there is more cheap thermal capacity. It is intensively used northbound in *Large scale RES*, *100%RES* and *Small & Local*, with maximum flows in April mid-day to serve load thanks to solar generation from the south. Some congestions occur (up to 30%). However, all the scenarios, the northern part of the backbone from North Italy to Tuscany, Umbria and Marches (from 52 to 53) is used southward in summer out of mid-day. This is due to available wind and/or cheap thermal generation in the North and West Europe which can be used in the evening in summer instead of starting expensive thermal in Italy. In winter, this generation is consumed locally and cannot reach Italy.

In *Fossil fuel & nuclear* the northern part of the reinforced backbone from North Italy to Lazio, Abruzzi and Campania (corridor 52-53-54) is used southward in average while the extreme south part (link 54-55) is used northward.

From Austria to North Italy

Between Austria and North Italy, the extra grid capacity developed (except for *Big&Market*), ranging between 2 to 8GW is used in both directions (northward mainly in mid-day periods -solar generation available- in spring and summer). Some congestions occur in both directions (up to 30-50%).

9.3.3. Cross comparison of costs and benefits

9.3.3.1. Cross comparison of costs

Fig. 191 gives the total investment costs for each scenario as well as their corresponding annuities. For the three less critical scenarios (*Big & market*, *Fossil & nuclear*, *Small & local*), the total cost ranges between 120 and 220b€ depending on the public acceptance of new overhead lines and therefore the available reinforcement technologies. In the scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES*, the architectures are almost twice as expensive with a total cost around 250 b€ in the case of new grid acceptance and around 390 b€ with DC cables in case of status quo.

Fig. 191 : Investment costs and annuities of the final architectures for each scenario

NB : Only the grid costs are assessed in the study. As a consequence, these results should not be used to identify a preferable scenario.

9.3.3.2. Cross comparison of benefits

Fig. 192 compares the benefits provided by the architectures in each scenario, with a focus on SoS, and optimal dispatch.

Fig. 192 : Unsupplied energy, extra spillage and increase of operating costs in the different scenarios, before and after grid reinforcements

For all scenarios, almost all ENS has been solved, and generation redispatch has been drastically reduced. Remaining volumes of ENS, spillage and redispatching are very small and spread, which left no room for easy detection of profitable new reinforcements.

Table 37 summarizes the benefits of the grid reinforcements in each scenario. As it can be expected, the benefits are more important in the scenarios which faced the most critical issues (*Large scale RES* and *100% RES*), it corresponds also to the scenarios with the most significant transmission requirements identified. The reduction of ENS goes from 5 TWh (*Small & local*) up to 50 TWh (*100% RES*). It results in an annual benefit of 50-500 b€ for an ENS cost of 10 000€/MWh or 5-50b€ for an ENS cost of 1000€/MWh. Spillage reduction ranges between 40 TWh (*Fossil & nuclear*) and 465 TWh (*100% RES*). Without ENS costs, the reduction of the annual operating cost of the European system (which includes CO₂ costs) ranges from 10 b€ (*Small & local*) to 79b€ (*Large Scale RES*) which justifies almost the architectures by itself.

PER YEAR	Large scale RES	100% RES	Big & market	Fossil & nuclear	Small & local
Reduction of ENS (TWh)	23	51	11	7	5
Reduction of spillage (TWh)	521	465	182	41	47
Reduction of the operating cost (b€)	79	39	22	11	10
Reduction of CO ₂ emissions (Mt)	192	80	54	35	23
Total annual benefit (assuming ENS=10k€/MWh)	309	549	132	81	60

Total annual benefit (assuming ENS=1k€/MWh)	102	90	33	18	15
Range of total investment cost (b€)	[255-384]	[245-345]	[138-216]	[121-211]	[116-192]
Range of investment annuities (b€)	[14-21]	[14-20]	[8-13]	[7-12]	[7-11]

Table 36 : Benefits of the grid reinforcements for each scenario

The total annual benefits in each scenario can be compared to the annuities of investment. Even with the strategy “status quo” (DC cables) and with an ENS cost of 1000 €/MWh, the architectures identified in each scenario are profitable. Assuming a cost of ENS of 10 000€/MWh, the architectures in the scenarios *Large Scale RES* and *100% RES* are even profitable within one year, what is explained by the tremendous amount of congestions. The reinforcements are more significant in those two scenarios - the investment cost is doubled compared to the others- , but they are also much more profitable : their benefits are three to nine times higher.

These investments don't take into account the additional reinforcements inside clusters which will be necessary for the proper functioning of the system. Nevertheless, these additional reinforcements will be significantly less expensive than the reinforcements between clusters and so they should only slightly reduce the profitability.

10. Summary and Conclusion

The results provided by this study are two-fold : the methodology applied and the final architectures at 2050.

Methodology

A new methodology for long-term grid development at European level was developed and carried out successfully within WP2. It relies on Monte-Carlo simulations which embed a detail modeling of both the generation and the grid for around hundred clusters in Europe. First, a detailed analysis of the system inefficiencies induced by grid limitations is performed. It points towards critical weeks and areas which are then at the core of the grid development. Reinforcements are suggested through an iterative process. Their benefits are computed from the annual gain in the generation cost and the annual reduction of the unssupplied energy cost. A simplified cost/benefit analysis finally ensures that the complete suggested architecture is profitable even with the most expensive technological solutions.

This methodology proved to be very efficient for long-term studies where the level of generation and demand are completely different from the current ones and its locaton is object to high uncertainties. It enables a real European approach as the whole system is simulated at once and reinforcements are identified considering all the European issues and solutions. The systems simulations performed ensure the robustness of the results thanks to the Monte-Carlo approach and their relevance thanks to the detailed modeling. The methodology was applied successfully by five different partners of the project, proving its feasibility. It could now be applied for studies with different assumptions, time horizon or geographical scope.

Architectures at 2050

The simulations performed during the study of the five e-Highway2050 scenarios showed a high need of transmission grid in 2050 to fulfil the European de-carbonization target : from 50 to 500 TWh of generation is inefficiently used annually without grid investment. The scenarios with the highest renewable generation are those where more reinforcements were identified (up to 400 b€ of investment costs), but they are also those with the highest profitability brought by the grid development (with an ENS cost of 10 000/MWh, the investment can be paid back within one year). This is explained on the one side by the highly fluctuating in-feed of renewables that can be balanced throughout Europe if the grid does support this power exchanges. And on the other hand it lowers the costs of generation thanks to “cheap” production from renewables and not required thermal dispatch. Even in the scenarios with less renewable or with a distributed vision, significant transmission requirements are profitable.

Despite the huge differences in the assumptions of the five scenarios, common and significant transmission requirements appeared :

- from Scandinavia to northern continental Europe
- from Finland to Poland through the Baltic states

- from UK to Spain through France
- From Greece to Italy

Even if a profitability in 2050 does not prove a profitability for today, these reinforcements are for sure good candidates for additional analysis.

It must be pointed out that the defined structures rely on the realization of the projects announced in ENTSO-e's Ten Years Network Development Plan. The complete development plan has been assumed as available in a starting grid and it cannot be guaranteed that the final grid solutions from e-Highway 2050 are sufficient without them. Especially in the projects that can already be understood as first steps towards an overlay-system, e.g. the HVDC corridors in Germany, seem indispensable for a sufficient transmission capacity in 2050. Furthermore, as described above, the aim of the grid development task was to identify the minimal required grid extensions, which have proven to be beneficial under severe circumstances ("no-regret investments"). Beyond those it seems very likely that additional projects can be beneficial, but have not been considered here due to above mentioned reasons. The results must therefore be understood as a *lower bound* for the future transmission system.

Within e-Highway 2050, only the network investment costs are assessed in each scenario. The investment costs for distribution, generation, storage and demand side management are out of the scope of the study but are for sure of interest to get a comprehensive view of the whole electrical system.

Further studies within the project

The results of task 2.3 and the grid development process are further used in other parts of the study e-Highway 2050 to further assess and amend the outcomes. In detail this means:

- **Check for implementation and operation:**
In **Task 2.4 and 4.1** the developed structures are assessed in terms of the ability to be implemented and operated in the existing 220kV/ 380kV transmission system. It is planned to identify problems in the cluster internal grid and suggest counter measures to enable a safe operation.
- **Identification of R&D Efforts:**
The main target of task 2.3 was the identification and dimensioning of transmission corridors throughout Europe, which support the existing transmission system. Among the *state-of-the-art* technology 380kV AC several new ones can be suggested, that are not part of the interconnected European system today such are higher AC-voltage levels (550 kV) and DC technologies in $\pm 320\text{kV}$, $\pm 600\text{kV}$. Latter for instance require a meshing and therefore the existing of dc-breakers, which are not maturely available today. **Working package 3** will further discuss these different solutions and determine R&D needs to be addressed to the manufactures.
- **Environmental Impacts:**
Beside the public acceptance of the new infrastructure it is also expected that environmental issues will play an increasing role in grid development. The effects of the suggested structures and their severity to the environment are analyzed in Task 4.1.
- **Intermediate Steps an modular development:**
Analyzes in task 2.3 focused on the year 2050 only. It was determined what additional investments are required beyond the TYNDP 2014 starting grid in 2030, depending on the scenario. The

development path towards 2050 and the modular implementation of corridors are assessed in **Task 4.3 and 4.4.**

- **Governance model Realization:**

It was shown that the suggested grid architectures provide a benefit throughout the assumed uncertainties in 2050. Besides the technical points of grid development it is also a question who are stakeholders to finance and operate these systems. **Working Package 5** therefore suggests governance options that deal with these aspects.

- **Comprehensive Costs-Benefit-Assessment:**

To assess the benefit of new transmission corridors task 2.3 applied a simplified costs benefit analyses where the annual costs of new reinforcements were compared with their benefit in terms of decreased generation costs and prevented energy not supplied. **Working package 6** has developed a detailed methodology to consider further aspects and will use this to assess the costs and benefits of the suggested structures in an entire frame.

Annex A : Abbreviations

Country and region abbreviations:

Code	Country
AL	Albania
AT	Austria
BA	Bosnia-Herzegovina
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CH	Switzerland
CZ	Czech Republic
DE	Germany
DK	Denmark
EE	Estonia
ES	Spain
FI	Finland
FR	France
GR	Greece
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
IT	Italy
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
ME	Montenegro
MK	FYROM
NL	Netherlands
NO	Norway
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
RO	Romania
RS	Serbia
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovak Republic
UK	United Kingdom
NS	North Sea
NA	North Africa

DZ	Algeria
MA	Morocco
MI	Middle East
TN	Tunisia
LY	Libya

Other abbreviations:

ENS	Energy Not Supplied (unsupplied energy or unsupplied demand)
LOLD	Loss Of Load Duration (adequacy indicator-length of shortfalls)
Spilled energy	Potential generation from RES (non-dispatchable generation) that is not utilized to supply the demand
MCV	Marginal Cost Variation = Decrease of the system's overall cost that would be brought by the optimal use of an additional MW to the transmission capacity (in both directions).
MC	Monte-Carlo
GTC	Grid Transfer Capacity
PSP	Pumped storage power plant
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
Res Hydro	Hydro power plants with Reservoirs
RoR Hydro	Run-Of-River hydro power plants
TYNDP	Ten Years Network Development Plan; published by ENTSO-e on a bi-annual basis

Annex B : Assignment to TYNDP '14 and its projects

The project e-Highway 2050 aimed at performing the analyses and grid development planning for the year 2050 as close to the real transmission system as possible. Given the fact that not only ENTSO-e as the Head-Association but also 15 TSOs are partner of the project and Working Package two, it was decided to use the most recent grid data available within ENTSO-e. The simplified grid model used has been developed starting at the beginning of 2013. For the purpose of task 2.2, where it was build, it was necessary to freeze the most current grid data, which was identical with the dataset used in the TYNDP 2014 – Status April 2013.

Since April 2014 the TYNDP 2014 and the e-Highway 2050 project progressed in parallel. During the TYNDP the grid development revealed new projects that are included in the final report and removed other projects from the common dataset. This is why a discrepancy exists between the projects considered in the starting grid of e-Highway 2050 and the final TYNDP 2014. The following table gives some projects that differ between the two processes (this list is not exhaustive):

Project	From <-> To Cluster	Capacity in e-Highway Starting Grid	Capacity in final TYNDP '14	Comment/ Effect on e-Highway results
FAB	22FR<->91UK	---	1.400MW – DC	The e-Highway 2050 analyses revealed an need for increased interconnection capacity between Great Britain and France. This Capacity is already partly considered in the final TYNDP '14 projects.
Eleclink	26FR<->90UK	---	1.000MW –DC	
BRITIB	17FR<->91UK	---	1.000MW –DC	
INELFE	15FR<->06FR	1.000MW –DC	2.000MW –DC	This link is a necessary reinforcement throughout all scenarios in e-Highway 2050. An increase in capacity, as has foreseen already by the TYNDP '14 can be supported.
Biscay Gulf	14FR<->04ES	1.000MW –DC	2.000MW –DC	The analyses revealed an need for increased interconnection

BRITIB	17FR<->04ES	---	1.000MW –DC	capacity between Spain and France. This Capacity is already partly considered in the final TYNDP '14 projects.
principle project FR-DE	25FR<->36DE	1.000MW –DC	0 MW (discarded)	Though the project was eventually discarded in the final version of the TYNDP '14, e-Highway 2050 has determined a need for increased capacity in 3 out of 5 scenarios (beyond these 1.000GW). If It is not included the required capacity in analyses of e-Highway2050 between France and Germany is likely to increase even further and it will proves necessary in most scenarios.
HVDC connection Italy to Croatia	53IT<->62HR	1.000MW –DC	0 MW (discarded)	This link has been discarded in the TYNDP '14. Yet during the analyses in this project it turned out to be highly profitable to have a connection between Balkan region and Italy.
HVDC connection Italy to Greece	55it <->68GR	1.000MW –DC	500MW	An increase of this link by 500 MW was analyzed in the TYNDP '14, but discarded at the end. Yet additional exchange capacity between Greece and Italy has been beneficial throughout all e-Highway 2050 scenarios. A realization of an capacity increase can be supported.

Annex C : Transmission requirements in all the scenarios (MW)

Links	Rein- forced/new	Large scale RES (X5)	100% RES (X7)	Big & market (X10)	Fossil & nuclear (X13)	Small & local (X16)
01_es - 02_es	reinforced	0	2000	0	0	1000
01_es - 03_es	new	0	0	0	2000	0
01_es - 12_pt	reinforced	1000	1000	1000	1000	0
02_es - 07_es	new	0	0	0	0	1000
02_es - 08_es	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
02_es - 12_pt	reinforced	1000	1000	0	0	0
03_es - 04_es	reinforced	2000	2000	0	0	0
03_es - 07_es	reinforced	2000	1000	0	0	1000
04_es - 07_es	new	0	0	0	0	7000
04_es - 14_fr	reinforced	5000	5000	6000	7000	8000
05_es - 07_es	new	0	0	0	0	1000
06_es - 07_es	new	0	0	0	0	2000
06_es - 11_es	reinforced	4000	2000	6000	9000	0
06_es - 15_fr	reinforced	10000	8000	14000	13000	0
07_es - 08_es	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	3000
07_es - 11_es	reinforced	2000	0	1000	5000	1000
07_es - 12_pt	new	0	0	0	0	2000
08_es - 09_es	reinforced	0	0	0	0	1000
08_es - 10_es	reinforced	0	0	0	0	1000
08_es - 13_pt	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	1000
09_es - 13_pt	reinforced	2000	2000	2000	2000	0
10_es - 11_es	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
106_ns - 110_ns	new	2000	0	6000	5000	0
106_ns - 90_uk	reinforced	10000	14000	11000	7000	1000
107_ns - 92_uk	reinforced	3000	8000	4000	2000	1000
108_ns - 93_uk	reinforced	1000	0	0	1000	0
109_ns - 94_uk	reinforced	1000	2000	0	1000	0
110_ns - 28_be	reinforced	2000	7000	6000	6000	1000
111_ns - 30_nl	reinforced	2000	1000	4000	2000	0
112_ns - 113_ns	new	9000	12000	0	1000	0
112_ns - 30_nl	new	0	0	0	2000	0
112_ns - 31_de	reinforced	10000	5000	7000	3000	3000
112_ns - 33_de	new	0	6000	0	0	0
113_ns - 30_nl	new	0	5000	0	0	0
113_ns - 38_dk	reinforced	9000	0	4000	1000	1000
114_ns - 116_ns	new	1000	0	0	0	0
114_ns - 72_dk	reinforced	2000	0	0	1000	0
115_ns - 79_no	reinforced	0	5000	0	0	0
116_ns - 88_se	reinforced	1000	0	0	1000	0
12_pt - 13_pt	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
14_fr - 15_fr	reinforced	0	3000	8000	10000	0
14_fr - 17_fr	reinforced	4000	6000	14000	15000	7000

14_fr - 18_fr	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
15_fr - 16_fr	reinforced	8000	4000	2000	1000	0
16_fr - 19_fr	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
16_fr - 20_fr	reinforced	1000	0	0	2000	0
17_fr - 21_fr	reinforced	1000	3000	0	0	0
17_fr - 22_fr	reinforced	3000	6000	14000	17000	7000
18_fr - 19_fr	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
18_fr - 24_fr	reinforced	2000	0	0	1000	0
19_fr - 20_fr	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
19_fr - 52_it	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
20_fr - 25_fr	reinforced	0	3000	0	0	0
20_fr - 52_it	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
21_fr - 96_ie	reinforced	6000	5000	1000	2000	2000
22_fr - 23_fr	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
22_fr - 26_fr	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
22_fr - 90_uk	reinforced	4000	4000	14000	15000	3000
24_fr - 25_fr	reinforced	0	0	0	1000	0
25_fr - 28_be	reinforced	0	3000	3000	0	2000
25_fr - 35_de	reinforced	0	5000	0	0	0
25_fr - 36_de	reinforced	1000	0	0	2000	1000
26_fr - 90_uk	reinforced	9000	8000	12000	7000	1000
28_be - 30_nl	reinforced	0	10000	0	0	0
28_be - 33_de	reinforced	0	5000	0	0	0
28_be - 90_uk	reinforced	4000	4000	2000	2000	0
30_nl - 31_de	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
30_nl - 38_dk	reinforced	3000	0	0	0	0
30_nl - 79_no	reinforced	7000	14000	4000	3000	0
30_nl - 90_uk	reinforced	4000	0	3000	0	0
31_de - 32_de	reinforced	0	1000	0	0	0
31_de - 33_de	reinforced	12000	0	0	0	0
31_de - 37_de	reinforced	4000	0	0	0	0
31_de - 38_dk	reinforced	11000	0	6000	1000	0
31_de - 72_dk	new	4000	0	0	0	0
31_de - 79_no	reinforced	17000	9000	2000	0	0
31_de - 89_se	reinforced	0	4000	0	4000	0
32_DE - 38_DK	new	0	0	2000	0	0
32_de - 72_dk	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
32_DE - 89_SE	new	8000	11000	3000	2000	6000
34_de - 35_de	reinforced	0	5000	0	0	0
34_de - 37_de	reinforced	0	4000	0	0	0
34_de - 44_pl	reinforced	3000	10000	2000	0	0
36_de - 37_de	reinforced	0	0	0	2000	0
37_de - 39_cz	reinforced	1000	0	0	2000	0
37_de - 49_at	reinforced	1000	8000	0	2000	1000
38_dk - 72_dk	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
38_dk - 79_no	reinforced	2000	0	0	1000	0

38_dk - 88_se	reinforced	0	0	0	0	4000
39_cz - 40_cz	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
39_cz - 44_pl	new	0	2000	0	0	0
40_cz - 43_pl	reinforced	5000	0	2000	0	0
40_cz - 46_sk	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
40_cz - 51_at	reinforced	5000	0	0	0	0
41_pl - 43_pl	reinforced	4000	0	2000	0	0
41_pl - 44_pl	reinforced	0	6000	0	0	0
41_pl - 77_lt	reinforced	8000	8000	7000	2000	6000
42_pl - 46_sk	reinforced	3000	0	0	1000	0
43_pl - 44_pl	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
44_pl - 45_pl	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
45_pl - 89_se	reinforced	0	0	3000	2000	0
46_sk - 58_hu	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
49_at - 50_at	reinforced	4000	0	0	2000	0
49_at - 52_it	reinforced	4000	8000	0	2000	2000
50_at - 51_at	reinforced	4000	0	0	2000	0
51_at - 58_hu	reinforced	1000	0	0	2000	1000
52_it - 53_it	reinforced	11000	8000	0	2000	11000
53_it - 54_it	reinforced	11000	8000	0	2000	11000
53_it - 99_fr	reinforced	0	0	2000	1000	0
54_it - 55_it	reinforced	11000	8000	0	2000	8000
54_it - 64_me	reinforced	1000	2000	0	0	0
54_it - 98_it	reinforced	8000	3000	2000	1000	3000
55_it - 56_it	reinforced	9000	2000	2000	1000	4000
55_it - 68_gr	reinforced	6000	9000	2000	2000	6000
57_si - 58_hu	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	1000
58_hu - 59_ro	reinforced	1000	2000	0	2000	0
58_hu - 65_rs	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	1000
59_ro - 61_ro	reinforced	0	2000	0	0	0
65_rs - 66_bg	reinforced	0	0	0	2000	0
65_rs - 67_mk	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
66_bg - 68_gr	reinforced	0	1000	0	0	1000
67_mk - 68_gr	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
72_dk - 89_se	reinforced	4000	0	0	0	0
73_ee - 75_fi	reinforced	5000	4000	3000	2000	5000
73_ee - 78_lv	reinforced	5000	4000	3000	2000	5000
74_fi - 75_fi	reinforced	0	0	1000	2000	2000
74_fi - 85_no	reinforced	1000	0	0	0	0
75_fi - 88_se	reinforced	3000	0	0	0	0
77_lt - 78_lv	reinforced	5000	3000	4000	2000	5000
77_lt - 88_se	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
79_no - 80_no	reinforced	3000	4000	2000	5000	0
79_no - 81_no	reinforced	17000	12000	2000	0	0
79_no - 92_uk	new	0	5000	0	0	0
80_no - 82_no	reinforced	0	1000	2000	4000	0

81_no - 83_no	reinforced	7000	7000	0	0	9000
81_no - 90_uk	new	0	0	0	0	12000
82_no - 83_no	reinforced	0	0	0	3000	0
82_no - 88_se	reinforced	2000	0	0	0	0
83_no - 84_no	reinforced	5000	5000	0	3000	2000
84_no - 85_no	reinforced	0	1000	0	0	0
86_se - 87_se	reinforced	5000	4000	1000	3000	5000
87_se - 88_se	reinforced	8000	9000	4000	4000	8000
88_se - 89_se	reinforced	9000	7000	4000	5000	5000
90_uk - 92_uk	reinforced	13000	5000	19000	10000	6000
92_uk - 93_uk	reinforced	13000	4000	13000	9000	0
92_uk - 96_ie	reinforced	1000	2000	4000	1000	0
93_uk - 94_uk	reinforced	9000	6000	6000	5000	0
93_uk - 95_uk	reinforced	1000	0	1000	1000	0
95_uk - 96_ie	reinforced	1000	2000	0	0	0
98_it - 99_fr	reinforced	800	0	0	0	0
TOTAL		451800	378000	255000	253000	190000

Annex D : Constraints analysis on critical weeks

In this section of the report, maps with main indicators of the system's operation and flow patterns in the starting grid for the selected weeks are presented for each scenario. They were used to suggest first transmission requirements.

Values and colors used to present main indicators on the maps are the following:

1. **ENS – Average power (annual or weekly) in average MW per year or week**
ENS is presented only if > selected threshold
2. **deltaSpillage – Average power (annual or weekly) in average MW per year or week**
deltaSpillage is presented only if > selected threshold
3. **Positive thermal redispatching+ - Average power (annual or weekly) in average MW per year or week**
Thermal redispatching+ is presented only if > selected threshold
4. **Negative thermal redispatching- - Average power (annual or weekly) in average MW per year or week**
Thermal redispatching- is presented only if > selected threshold
5. **MCV – Average value (annual or weekly) in Euro/MW**
MCV is presented only if > selected threshold

Large Scale RES WEEK 48

WEEK 48 - Average

Fig. 193: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching in week 48 (average MW per week) – X-5

LEGEND:

ENS > 20 MW

Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h

Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h

Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h

Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh

WEEK 48 – Worst year

Fig. 194: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching and MCV in week 48 & “worst” year (average MW per week) – X-5

LEGEND:

ENS > 20 MW

Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h

Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h

Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h

Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh

Clusters with highest ENS are clusters in Germany, eastern part of Poland, western part of France, Spain (southern part and Catalonia). Excess of energy that is spilled or limited can be seen in Nordic countries, Baltic countries, UK, IE, Greece, and North Sea and North Africa.

Bulgaria and Romania can be also recognized as surplus areas of competitive thermal generation.

Indicators on the map points to links with MCV > 200 Euro/MWh:

- Links between Nordic countries and continental Europe
- Links between Baltic countries and Poland
- Links between Greece& Balkan countries and Italy
- Links between Portugal and Spain
- Links between Spain and France
- Links between UK & Ireland and continental Europe

Fig. 195: Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 48 – X-5

- Reinforcements of the corridors from North of Nordic countries towards Germany and Poland, as seen in this week (week 48) are mainly used to solve ENS, by utilization of spilled energy and available competitive thermal generation.
- Similar is the role of reinforcements from UK&IE to France and Portugal to Spain, although in this case, surplus of energy are mostly competitive thermal power plants.
- Reinforcements from south France to Spain are considered as a corridor for transfer of power from North Africa (Algeria).
- Similar is with reinforcements in Italy, that enable transfer of power from the south (Greece and North Africa) to Central Europe, but also enable reduction of expensive thermal generation in Italy and reduction of costs.

As it can be seen, there is a significant excess of thermal generation in South-Eastern Europe for which suitable reinforcements will be analyzed and assessed in next steps.

WEEK 47

WEEK 47 - Average

Fig. 196: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching in week 47 (average MW per week) – X-5

LEGEND:

- ENS > 20 MW
- Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h
- Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h
- Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h
- Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh

WEEK 47 – Worst year

Fig. 197: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching and MCV in week 47 & “worst” year (average MW per week) – X-5

LEGEND:

- ENS > 20 MW
- Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h
- Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h
- Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h
- Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh

Week 47 seems to be more critical than week 10, with ENS and spillages of higher magnitude, so week 47 has been used as a representative of weeks with high ENS in Spain. This week can be considered as characteristic also for Italy, where high thermal redispatching can be observed.

Fig. 198: Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 47 – X-5

WEEK 10

Week 10 has been used as a representative of weeks with high ENS in Italy, but is also very similar to week 47.

WEEK 10 - Average

Fig. 199: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching in week 10 (average MW per week) – X-5

WEEK 10 – Worst year

Fig. 200: Map with ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching in week 10 & “worst year” (average MW per week) – X-5.

<p>LEGEND:</p> <p>ENS > 20 MW</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h</p> <p>Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h</p> <p>Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh</p>	<p>LEGEND:</p> <p>ENS > 20 MW</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh/h</p> <p>Increase spillage > 20 MWh/h</p> <p>Link: MCV>200Euro/MWh</p>
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The analysis of week 10 suggests similar reinforcements to those identified for week 47 but with smaller sizes for some of them :

Fig. 201: Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 10 – X-5

WEEK 25

Week 25 is recognized as the week with highest spillage and negative thermal redispatching. Maps with specific indicators for week 25 are presented in sequel.

Week 25 is different in comparison to week 48, but still clusters that can be recognized as the main surplus areas are the same, pointing to high excess of energy in Nordic countries, Baltic countries, UK, Greece, and North Sea and North Africa. In this week, there is ENS only in few clusters in Sardinia, Corsica, Italy and Spain, with average ENS reaching 35MW, while maximum delta spillage is 8 GW.

Several clusters have high positive thermal redispatching. These clusters are the same clusters recognized as deficit areas in week 48.

Fig. 204: Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 25 – X-5

Week 40: average 99 MC years

Week 40 is a week with high ENS outside winter.

Similar to week 25, there is ENS in Spain and in Italy, but at higher level. Beside this, in comparison to week 25, in the regions near Spain, there is lower negative thermal redispatching in south of France (although it is higher in western coast of France and UK, which is far away from Spain) and no spillages in Portugal. Similar situation is in Italy. Thus, week 40 is more critical than week 25. Transmission requirements recognized in week 40 are presented in Fig. 205.

Fig. 207: Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 40 – X-5

Conclusions

Based mainly on the results for week 48 and “worst” year, but also all other weeks, sizes of the transmission requirements recognized in the first step are assessed and presented in Fig. 208.

Reinforcements in red box are used in this first step to :

- solve ENS in Germany from Norway and Sweden (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist) and
- further help in continental Europe (BE, NL, FR, IT...)

Reinforcements in light blue box are used to:

- solve ENS in Poland from Finland and Baltic states (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist)

Reinforcements in dark blue box are used to:

- solve ENS in France from UK & IE (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist)

Fig. 208: Assessed 1st set of transmission requirements – X-5

Reinforcements in violet box are used to:

- solve ENS in Spain from Portugal (where excess of thermal capacity exist)
- solve ENS in Spain from France (where excess of thermal capacity exist)

Reinforcements in green box are used to:

- solve ENS and to enable more economic dispatch in Italy from Greece (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist) and excess of solar generation from North Africa

100% RES

WEEK 2

It can be noticed that situation in week 2 is really critical: clusters that in the annual balance present characteristics of net importer or net exporter are in this week more “radicals” with more extreme situations. In the following images similar reasoning of the ones related to the annual analysis can be draw.

Analyzing the results, it can be seen that:

- links on corridors from Norway to continental Europe should collect excess of energy along the way;
- Baltic countries and Poland should collect energy to bring towards Germany;
- the link between Greece and Italy seems really interesting for a possible expansion;
- The connection of United Kingdom from North to South, and then to Europe is relevant.

WEEK 50

The analysis carried out brings us to see the behavior of the system in week 50. As it can be seen in the following Figures, the situation is less critical with respect to week 2, but in any case energy not provided is still really high, and at the same time spillage is present in North Europe.

Analyzing the results, it can be seen that:

- Similar to week 2, links on corridors from Norway to continental Europe should collect excess of energy along the way;
- Baltic countries and Poland should collect energy to bring towards Germany;
- the link between Greece and Italy seems really interesting for a possible expansion;
- The connection of United Kingdom from North to South should enable reduction of ENS in UK first. Interconnection with continental Europe is also promising.

Fig. 214 - definition of new interconnection on the basis of the results of week 50

WEEK 25

The analysis of the most interesting weeks lead us to see in detail the characteristics of week 25 for summer, because in this week occurs a lot of spillage.

With respect to the situation in the winter period, it has been chosen to start the reinforcement on the basis of the winter solutions, and analyze in further steps, if necessary, the reinforcement needs for the summer period.

Conclusions

Based mainly on the results for week 2 and “worst” year, but also all other weeks, sizes of the reinforcements proposed for the first step are assessed and presented in Fig. 217.

In this first step reinforcements are used to :

- solve ENS in Germany and Central Europe from Norway and Sweden (where high spillage exist)
- further help in continental Europe (BE, NL, FR, IT...)

Big & market

In this section of the report, maps with main indicators of the system's operation and flow patterns on the European transmission grid in the selected weeks are presented.

Results of the constraints analyses show that there are several corridors which should be reinforced with the aim to enable exchange of energy, primarily reduction of ENS, but also reduction of overall operating costs. With the aim to define links that should be reinforced but also to assess the size of each reinforcement, week 48 is further analyzed on the 99 years average results and also on the MC-year (Monte Carlo Year) in which ENS is the highest ("worst" year).

In addition to this week, more detailed analyses are also carried out for weeks 6, 25, 43.

Values and colors used to present main indicators on the maps are explained in Section 2.4 (Scenario X-5)

WEEK 48

<p>ENS > 50 MW</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh</p> <p>Increase spillage > 10 MWh</p> <p>MCV [€/MWh]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 100-200 ▶ 200-500 ▶ 500-1000 ▶ 1000-2000 ▶ 2000-100000 	<p>Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh</p> <p>Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh</p> <p>Increase spillage > 10 MWh</p> <p>MCV[€/MWh]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 100-200 ▶ 200-500 ▶ 500-1000 ▶ 1000-2000 ▶ 2000-100000
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Huge amounts of unsupplied energy are located across Spain, in France (mainly in West part), in Ireland, south UK and East Poland.

Positive thermal redispatching of expensive generation is located in Spain and north, central and south continental Europe.

Huge amounts of excess of spilled energy or of thermal negative redispatching are located :

- In NS clusters close to south UK clusters (wind spillage),
- In Northern UK (Spillage, nuclear and biomass),
- In all Sweden (nuclear),
- In Finland and Baltic (spillage, biomass, cheaper gas)
- In Denmark (biomass).

Based on these elements, first transmission requirements are suggested :

Reinforcement of links between 2 NS clusters close to south UK clusters will bring energy from NS to UK (and then continental Europe).

Reinforcement of the corridor from north UK to North of France will collect energy from North UK and NS clusters to help solve problems in West continental Europe (ENS in France and Spain, expensive thermal redispatching in continental Europe). A reinforcement between UK and Ireland will help to solve ENS in Ireland.

Reinforcement of the corridor going from north Finland to North Poland will collect energy all along the path (in Finland clusters and Baltic countries) to solve ENS in Poland and reduce expensive thermal generation in continental Europe.

Reinforcement of the corridor going from north Sweden to North East Germany and North Poland will collect energy all along Sweden clusters to solve ENS in Poland and thermal positive redispatching in Germany and more generally continental Europe.

The link between western Denmark and North Germany will allow bringing excess of biomass generation in Denmark to Germany.

These reinforcements are summarized in the figure below :

Fig. 220 : Map with corridors recognized as a 1st set of reinforcements, based on week 48 – X10

These corridors mainly present connections between distant areas and continental Europe and because of that, reinforcement of these corridors can be applied in one first step assuming that there is no mutual impact between applied reinforcements. Reinforcements inside continental Europe will be considered in further steps, depending on the effect of the first step.

WEEKS 6, 25 and 43

Week 25 - average

Fig. 223 : Map with average hourly values on the 99 Monte Carlo years in week 25 or ENS, spillage variation, thermal redispatching, MCV – X-10

LEGEND :

ENS > 50 MW

Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh

Thermal re-dispatch < -20 MWh

Increase spillage > 10 MWh

MCV[€/MWh]:

- ▶ 100-200
- ▶ 200-500
- ▶ 500-1000
- ▶ 1000-2000
- ▶ 2000-100000

Week 6 is close to week 48 in terms of location of ENS, spillage and thermal redispatching, with smaller volumes.

In week 43 there is on average only ENS in one eastern cluster in Spain. Areas in excess of energy are located mainly in North Sea, UK, Scandinavia, Baltic countries and western France (except Britain) while areas with lack of energy are located in Spain, central and east continental Europe and Italy. First reinforcements for this week 43 would aim at bring energy from northern countries (North Sea, UK, Scandinavia, Baltic countries) towards north continental Europe to reduce expensive thermal generation. These reinforcements already belong to the list proposed for week 48.

Week 25 presents the same locations of areas with excess of energy and areas with lack of energy as week 43, with higher level of spillage in Scandinavia. So the first reinforcements for week 25 would be the same as for week 43, which already belong to the list proposed for week 48.

Conclusions

Based mainly on the results for week 48 (average on the 99 Monte Carlo years and “worst” year), and confirmed also by other characteristic weeks, transmission requirements are presented in Fig.2245.

Fig. 225 : The first set of transmission requirements – X10

Reinforcements on the UK corridor proposed in the first step are aimed to :

- solve ENS in south continental Europe and France from North Sea and UK (where high spillage and excess of thermal capacity exist) and

- further help in Spain

Reinforcements on the corridor from Sweden and Finland proposed in the first step are aimed to:

- solve ENS in East Poland
- further help to reduce expensive thermal generation in continental Europe

Reinforcements on the corridor from Denmark proposed in the first step are aimed to:

- help to reduce expensive thermal generation in continental Europe

Fossil & nuclear

WEEK 48

For this period the focus is on Spain, Italy, France and Portugal which are facing high energy not served.

Week 48 - Average over the 99 MC years

While there is energy not served in Spain, France and Portugal during this period, there is spillage of wind energy in North Sea. To a lesser extent there is also some spillage in Portugal, South of France and Ireland. It can be noticed that the total amount of spillage will not be sufficient to cover the total amount of ENS, even if they happen at the same time. North Sea can be a source of energy for the deficit areas in Southern Europe but this also will not be enough. The light blue negative thermal redispatching Figures show that there is a huge potential of the thermal generation in the United Kingdom. More interconnection with the UK will help to solve the ENS in Spain and Portugal. It can

be noticed that the MCVs (Marginal cost variation) are particularly higher for the France-Spain border and interconnection from UK and Ireland to continental Europe. This confirms the prior analysis, competitive and available generation could be shipped from UK to continental Europe and down to Spain.

Week 48 - Worst year

For this moment of analysis the most extreme year of all Monte Carlo years was also chosen. The total energy not served amounts 14 TWh, the double of the average of all Monte Carlo years. In this most extreme year there is energy not served spread over whole Europe except for Scandinavia and the UK. Spillage energy in North Sea can only contribute very little to solve the ENS. Therefore the negative thermal redispatching energy should again be used. The margin on thermal, the thermal capacity that is not used is indicated in purple. This should also be taken into account to solve the ENS. It is doubtful that all energy not served will be solved when using the available capacity and spillage. However, it should be stressed that this is the most extreme Monte Carlo year with the double of total energy not served than the average over all Monte Carlo years.

Week 48 - Suggested corridors

Depending on the time stamp, Ireland is both a deficit and a surplus area. The UK is the nearest source for Ireland. To evacuate the spilled energy from North Sea a link to continental Europe is suggested. To use the thermal potential in the UK, a link is suggested from the North to the South of UK, crossing North Sea and reaching continental Europe in France. Because the spilled energy in North Sea will not always be enough to solve the ENS in continental Europe, connection with the UK and its thermal potential can serve as backup solution. This energy from North Sea and UK should go through France down to Spain. Between Spain and Portugal, another reinforcement is suggested

Recognized links to be reinforced are presented in the figure below.

Fig. 228: Map with suggested corridors for week 48– X-13

WEEK 26

For this period the focus is on Italy. As conclusions are similar to week 48, analysis for this week will be described less detailed.

<u>Week 26 – Average</u>	<u>Week 26 – Worst year</u>
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Fig. 229: Map with ENS, spillage variation, positive and negative thermal redispatching (average MW for week 26) and MCVs – X-13

LEGEND:

ENS > 50 MW

Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h

Thermal re-dispatch < -10 MWh/h

Increase spillage > 5 MWh/h

Link: MCV>1000Euro/MWh

Fig. 230 : Map with ENS, spillage variation, positive and negative thermal redispatching (average MW for week 26 worst MC) and MCVs – X-13

LEGEND:

ENS > 50 MW

Thermal re-dispatch > 100 MWh/h

Thermal re-dispatch < -10 MWh/h

Increase spillage > 5 MWh/h

Link: MCV>1000Euro/MWh

While there is some energy not served in Spain and Sicilia during this period there is spillage of energy in North Sea and Scandinavia, and large volumes of thermal (biomass, nuclear) generation that are limited by network constraints in UK, France and Scandinavia. This energy should be used to solve the ENS and the positive thermal redispatch in the area Belgium, The Netherlands and Germany on one hand and Italy and the Iberian peninsula on the other hand.

It can be noticed that the cost are particularly higher for the France-Spain border and for internal lines of Spain, Portugal and Italy.

The in-depth analysis on this week has shown that competitive thermal margins and renewable generations should be shipped from Scandinavia, UK, France and Eastern Europe to Central North Europe (Germany, Netherlands, and Belgium) and down to Italy, Spain and Portugal. Therefore, on the map below, a first set of corridors is suggested to solve the problems of week 26.

Fig. 231: Map with suggested corridors for week 26 (GW) – X-13

WEEK 22-28

This period is chosen to focus on spillage energy in Sweden and Norway during summer. Due to grid constraints this energy cannot be exported and gas and coal production elsewhere in Europe increases. Similar to the analysis for week 26, there is also cheaper thermal potential in UK, France, Eastern Europe and Scandinavia.

Map for week 22-28 is presented below (whole day, ENS >50 MW in red, Spillage > 10 MW in green, MCV >50 Euro/MW)

Fig. 232: Map with ENS, spillage variation (average MW for week 22-28) and MCVs – X-13

The in-depth analysis on this week has shown that competitive thermal margins and renewable generations should be shipped from Scandinavia, UK, France and Eastern Europe to Central North Europe (Germany, Netherlands, and Belgium) and down to Italy, Spain and Portugal. Therefore, on the map below, a first set of corridors is suggested to solve the problems for this week. The suggested corridors follow a similar way as suggested from the analysis of week 26. The difference is that some capacities should be higher. From this analysis there seems to be more potential in the UK. Compared to week 26, there is less potential in Scandinavia. The link from Norway to the Netherlands can even be replaced with a link from North Sea to the Netherlands and Germany.

Fig. 233: Map with suggested corridors for week 22-28 (GW) – X-13

Conclusions

Combining the outcomes from the analyses above results in a first set of candidate corridors. These are shown in Fig. 234.

Assessment of the size of reinforcement is based on minimum of:

- Maximal hourly value of ENS in cluster which connection is to be reinforced
- Corresponding hourly value of spillage + negative thermal redispatching in cluster which provides energy to be transferred to the clusters with ENS

The size of the corridors also takes into account possibility to collect excess of energy along the corridor.

Proposed links should be considered as 1st proposals that are checked in further steps.

Fig. 234: Map with suggested corridors (GW) – X-13

Small & local

WEEK 48 – ENS in whole Europe

Week 48 – Average over the 99 MC years (Fig. 235)

As highlighted above, week 48 concentrated 17% of the total ENS volume. This number increases to 44% if we assume that week 48 is representative for the 12 winter weeks (December – February). During week 48, the western France and Italy account for more than 50% of the total ENS. The remainder of ENS-issues is concentrated around the major cities in Italy, Spain, Germany, Poland and the UK. Fig. 235 shows the average, hourly expected variation of spillages, ENS and thermal re-

dispatching in week 48. Furthermore, it shows the MCV (marginal cost variation) of the transmission corridors. From Fig. 235, one can see that the system tries to minimize the amount of ENS with positive thermal re-dispatching in France and Germany (near or in the clusters with ENS) compared to the copperplate simulation. This shows that transmission grid reinforcements might not only solve ENS-issues in these clusters, but also would allow for an increase in operational efficiency in the dispatch.

Week 48 – Worst year (Fig. 236)

To get information on the magnitude and the synchronicity of ENS, spillages and re-dispatching, the Monte Carlo year with the highest ENS volume in week 48 is analyzed. The flow patterns are visualized in this Monte Carlo year in Fig. 236. The ENS issues, as well as potential surplus areas as identified in the average year are confirmed. Based on the worst-case analysis presented above, one could identify a first set of transmission requirements that could alleviate ENS-issues in Europe during week 48. The first set of transmission requirements entails (solid lines in Fig. 237)

- Greece to Italy (5 GW);
- Finland to Poland, collection power in the Baltic states (5 GW);
- Sweden to northern Germany and Denmark (8 GW);
- Portugal to Spain, where Madrid and Barcelona are connected (2 GW);
- Norway to the UK (9 GW).

A first estimate of the size of these transmission corridors is presented in Fig. 237 (and between brackets above). This value is merely a first estimate and should be regarded as an upper bound for the transmission requirement between those clusters. Furthermore, note that these transmission requirements or corridors may represent multiple or equivalent solutions. Multiple grid architectures may correspond to these transmission corridors. On the other hand, various transmission requirements may address the same issues, making them equivalent solutions.

Additional reinforcements shall be needed, especially to solve ENS issues in France and Germany. However, ENS issues in Central Europe will be affected by the reinforcement of the transmission corridors listed above. Therefore, the effect of the increased transmission capacity on these corridors must be first investigated before sizing or testing the reinforcement on other transmission corridors, such as, but not limited to (see dotted lines in Fig. 237.):

- Ireland to France;
- Spain to France;
- The UK to France;
- Serbia to Poland and Southern Germany.

Fig. 237: A first set of transmission requirements that might solve the ENS issues during week 48.

WEEK 6 – ENS in France & Italy

Week 6 and the weeks with a similar pattern concentrate around 20% of the annual ENS. During these weeks, major ENS issues occur in France (especially the south-west), Italy and (to a lesser extent) Poland. During week 6, there is some positive thermal re-dispatching in the UK, Germany and France. Reinforcements might help not only to solve ENS issues, but also to increase the operational dispatch efficiency.

Note that the congestion patterns and MCVs from week 48 are partly ‘confirmed’ in week 6. Especially between Italy and the Balkan and Greece, congestion patterns are very similar.

The worst-case analysis confirms the patterns drawn from the average hourly results, although the effects are more pronounced. Especially thermal re-dispatching in the UK, Northern Germany, Bel-

gium and France is prominently present. MCVs and congestion patterns increase, also in Northern Europe, highlighting the importance of adequate grid reinforcements during ‘worst-case’ situations.

Based on this analysis, a first set of transmission requirements is proposed to alleviate ENS issues during week 6 (solid lines in Fig. 240):

- Greece to Italy (6 GW);
- Finland to Poland, collecting power from the Baltic States (4 GW).

In a second step, possible transmission requirements to solve ENS problems in France and Germany could be (dotted lines in Fig. 240):

- Portugal to Spain and France;
- North Sea to France, via the UK or Denmark and Germany;
- Serbia to Germany.

Note that the transmission corridors passing through the UK or Denmark and Germany might yield a more efficient dispatch.

Fig. 240: A first set of transmission requirements that might solve the ENS issues during week 6.

WEEK 12 – ENS in Italy and Scandinavia

Week 12 and the weeks with a similar pattern jointly represent 8% of the annual ENS volume. ENS mainly occurs in Italy and Scandinavia. In Scandinavia, ENS is less frequent. This ENS issue is due to the end of winter, the beginning of maintenance of thermal assets and a high demand (cold spell).

To alleviate these ENS issues, power source in the vicinity of Italy and Scandinavia could be

- Thermal capacity in Greece;
- Thermal capacity in the Baltic countries;
- Thermal capacity in Eastern Europe;
- Spillages in the North Sea and Northern Germany.

Note that the congestion patterns on the interconnections between Italy and the Balkan and Greece again re-appear in week 12. The flows on the transmissions system in the Northern part of Europe however reverse: power tends to flow from continental Europe to Scandinavia, while in other periods of the year this typically is reversed.

A ‘worst case’ analysis on the Monte Carlo year that exhibits the highest ENS volume in week 12 highlights the ENS issues in Scandinavia. In Finland, most ENS occurs during the night and peaks early in the morning around 6 a.m. Similarly, in Norway ENS peaks at 8 a.m. In Italy and Northern Sweden, ENS peaks during the evening peak (up to 4 GW in Italy, up to 100 MW in Sweden). The power surpluses as listed above persist during the worst Monte Carlo year, as well as the congestion patterns, indicating flows from continental Europe to Scandinavia.

To alleviate ENS issues in week 12, a first set of transmission requirements (solid lines in Fig. 243) that could be considered consists of connections between

- Greece and Italy (4 GW);
- Germany, via Denmark, to Sweden (5 GW);
- The Baltic states, where thermal margin is available, to Finland (4 GW).

In a second step, the latter link could also collect thermal generation margin from Poland (dotted lines in Fig. 243).

Fig. 243: A first set of possible transmission requirements to alleviate ENS in week 12.

WEEK 26 & 36 – ENS in Italy

As week 26 and 36 showed similar congestion, ENS and spillage patterns, results for only week 26 are discussed in detail. The weeks with similar characteristics as week 26 represent around 14% of the total ENS volume. During these weeks, ENS occurs in Italy between 4 and 8 p.m.

To address these ENS issues, possible power surplus include

- Spilled wind and hydro power in Austria and Scandinavia;

- Thermal margin in Greece, the Balkan area and Hungary.

Note that we do not include spilled solar power from North Africa, Spain or Italy as ENS occurs asynchronously (not at the same moment in time) with these spillages. Furthermore, note that the thermal margin selected above was not used in the ‘copperplate simulation’ (no negative re-dispatching values). This thermal capacity may therefore be more expensive (compared to the cheap biomass that is re-dispatched in the Baltic States and Scandinavia).

In Monte Carlo year with the highest ENS volumes in week 26, ENS volumes in Italy reach up to 7 GWh/h. Simultaneously, high spillages volumes are recorded in Austria (up to 6 GWh/h), while a significant amount of cheap thermal generation and spillages in Scandinavia and the Baltic states is available. Thermal generation (which is more expensive than the capacity in Scandinavia) is available in Greece (7 GW), the Balkan (1 GW in Croatia, 1 GW in Bosnia Herzegovina) and Hungary.

Therefore, the different possible reinforcements that would solve the ENS issues in Italy include

- Hungary via Austria to Italy (up to 6 GW);
- Croatia to Italy (1 GW);
- Bosnia Herzegovina (1 GW);
- Greece to Italy (up to 6 GW);
- Norway – Sweden via Germany and Austria to Italy (up to 6 GW).

Note that the latter reinforcement would not only help to solve the ENS issues in Italy, but would also allow for a greater operational efficiency in the dispatch.

Fig. 246: A first set of possible reinforcements to solve ENS in week 26 in Italy

WEEK 15 – highest increase in spillages in Europe

Although ENS reduction will be treated in priority (given the value attached to ENS), especially in the early phase of the grid development, it is interesting to analyze the flow patterns in Europe during periods of large increases in spillages. The transmission requirements to solve ENS as identified above may correspond to those needed to transport excess RES-based generation to the load centers.

During week 15, the increase in spillages is the highest. In the South, solar energy is spilled. Especially in Sicily, Sardinia, Italy and southern Spain high volumes of solar energy are curtailed. To a lesser extent, solar energy is unutilized in North Africa. Wind energy is mainly spilled in and around the North Sea, especially in the clusters connected to Germany. Simultaneously, positive re-dispatching occurs in the UK, Ireland and Central-West Europe (France, Belgium, the Netherlands and Germany). This increase in thermal generation is mainly an increase in expensive gas-fired generation.

The high MCV values show some hints on some congestion between the South of Europe/North Africa and continental Europe and the UK. Note the high MCV values for the connections between Italy and Greece and the Balkan, as well as on the internal connections.

Fig. 247: Expected, average hourly results on the 99 Monte Carlo years on week 15.

Based on the analysis above, one can identify the following corridors:

- North Sea to Germany;

- Southern Spain via Madrid to Belgium;
- Sardinia and Sicily, via Italy, to Southern Germany.

These corridors are important and their reinforcement may lead to an economically more efficient dispatch, by connecting RES-based generation to the major load centers in Europe. The demand in these load centers would otherwise be satisfied by running expensive gas-fired units.

Fig. 248: A first set of possibly economically interesting transmission requirements for week 15.

Overall Conclusions

Based on the analysis above, one can identify a number of common transmission requirements among the different representative weeks. These are shown in Fig. 249.

The transmission requirement between the UK and Norway amounts to 9 GW. This connection collects hydro, wind and cheap thermal generation from Norway to satisfy the demand in load centers in the south of the UK (especially in weeks like 48).

Similarly, the analysis for week 48 showed that there is an additional transmission requirement of 8 GW between Sweden and Denmark and Northern Germany. This transmission corridor could allow solving ENS issues in continental Europe by transferring spilled energy and cheap thermal generation to Denmark and Germany. In the analysis performed for week 12, this transmission corridor could be beneficial to solve ENS issues in Scandinavia. During these weeks, the transmission requirement would however be lower (about 5 GW). Furthermore, this corridor could help to improve the efficiency of the dispatch (e.g. see the analysis for week 6).

The connection between Finland and Poland, via the Baltic States, could solve ENS issues in Scandinavia and Poland. During winter weeks, ENS issues in Poland could be addressed by importing spilled energy and cheap thermal generation from Finland and the Baltic states. During weeks similar to week 12, the thermal generation in the Baltic States could be a cost-efficient option to meet the load in Finland and the rest of Scandinavia. The transmission requirement is set by the analysis for week 48, leading to a capacity requirement of 5 GW.

To address ENS-issues in Spain, the analysis for week 48 showed that a transmission corridor between Portugal and Barcelona, via Madrid, could be beneficial. This transmission corridor would collect thermal power from Portugal to meet the load in the big cities. The transmission requirement is once more set by week 48 and amounts to 2 GW.

Italy showed to be the country with the highest ENS volume, amounting to 64% of all ENS. A first transmission requirement that could address the issues in Italy would be the interconnection between Greece and Italy. The North of Greece would be connected to the South of Italy, but the transmission corridor should connect all clusters in Italy as well. Based on the analysis presented above, the size of this corridor is estimated to be 6 GW.

Note that the analysis presented above showed multiple alternatives to solve ENS issues in Italy (e.g. see the analysis for week 26). However, the selected solution seems beneficial in all studied weeks, therefore it is selected first.

In Central-Western Europe, we have not yet found any 'evident' transmission corridors that would solve the ENS issues in e.g. France. The transmission requirements presented above may already address some of the ENS issues in CWE. The remaining ENS volumes, spillages and re-dispatching issues will have to be analyzed taking into account the effect of the transmission requirements presented above.

The presented set of transmission requirements is a first set that could help to decrease ENS, spillage and re-dispatching volumes in Europe. However, the presented measures will not be sufficient to bring ENS-volumes to acceptable levels or to optimize the dispatch. To identify the transmission corridors and their respective sizes to achieve these goals, one first needs to study the impact of the first set of transmission requirements.

Fig. 249: The first set of transmission requirements-X-16.

Annex E : Refurbishment of existing Over-Head Lines

The measure of refurbishment in the analyses is seen as the possibility to use the tower-system of an existing OHL and replace the mounted conductors and insulation. The transmission capability of an OHL can be increased in two ways. The voltage level of the circuit can be increased or the maximal current is increased by increasing the ampacity of the single conductors. What is feasible depends strongly on the different situations. An increase of the voltage level requires higher insulation and safety distances and thus is limited by the size of the towers and the width of the corridor. To increase ampacity it is usually necessary to mount conductors with thicker cross-sections that can be utilized with higher currents. This possibility also is limited by the load-carrying limitations of the towers. But also in case of high temperature conductors which do not necessarily increase the weight of a conductor section latter way is limited by thresholds for electro-magnetic emissions an OHL is allowed to emit.

In today's transmission grid we find AC voltage levels of up to 380kV throughout Europe. For the analysis in task 2.3 it is therefore assumed that all lines can be refurbished with this technology – either by increasing the number of conductors or by switching to high-temperature conductors. For shorter term grid planning (up to ~10years) precise information is available for the OHLs at stake. This means one can decide on a case to case situation what is the best possibility to increase the transmission capacities of existing OHLs. Here also higher voltage levels, which go beyond today's level of 380kV are an option. Depending on the circumstances it provides advantages to not increase the current to realize an increased transmission capacity but to increase the voltage level. The integration of higher AC voltage level in the 380kV system is connected with an additional investment in new transformers. Yet these extra costs are exceeded by benefits in operation and the lower losses on longer transmission distances. 550kV and 750kV AC connections are already used in different regions of the world and should definitively be considered for the grid development planning on a shorter time horizon. From a European perspective 550kV seems the more suitable alternative. In comparison to 750kV this voltage level requires smaller insulation distances, thus smaller tower systems, which are in the same order of magnitude as 380kV lines. Also the cabling of 550kV holds less technical challenges than with 750kV. Both points lead to lower problems with public acceptance of 550kV. 750kV connections are mainly designed for very long distance OHL connections for bulk power transmission, which is not required in this dimension in the meshed European transmission system.

An alternative towards higher AC voltage levels is given by DC transmission systems. These technologies are mainly designed for long distance transport of high capacities, thus are a considerable option for refurbishment. Voltage levels today in discussion are $\pm 320\text{kV}$, $\pm 500\text{kV}$ and $\pm 600\text{kV}$. Also here we find the possibility to use existing transmission corridors and towers systems, thus increasing public acceptance for new transmission lines. Yet the combined operation of AC and DC voltage circuits on one tower system holds operational challenges due to electromagnetic interferences on these hybrid-systems. DC voltage has its advantages for long distances, especially when a high share of cabling is desired. Also with DC transmission the situation is that insulation distance and therefore tower dimensions are increased when rated voltages increase.

An exhaustive discussion of the technology alternatives is made in WP3. Here the technical characteristics of the transmission technologies are described in detail and their suitability for the transmission system is assessed.